

Study of the performance of the first Large-Sized Cherenkov telescope of CTA, the relevance of fluorescence in the Cherenkov technique and the multiwavelength emission from the blazar 1ES 0647+250

Estudio del comportamiento del primer telescopio Cherenkov de gran tamaño de CTA, la relevancia de la fluorescencia en la técnica Cherenkov y la emisión multilongitud de onda del blázar 1ES 0647+250

Memoria para optar al grado de Doctor
presentada por

Daniel Morcuende Parrilla

UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID

FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS FÍSICAS

Directores

Jaime Rosado Vélez, José Luis Contreras González, Wystan Benbow

Programa de Doctorado en Astrofísica

Febrero 2023

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank everyone with whom I have worked and shared these years. First and foremost, I want to thank my supervisors, José Luis Contreras and Jaime Rosado, for allowing me to be a part of this business and for their guidance, trust, and unwavering support. Thanks also to Wystan Benbow, my co-supervisor, for his willingness to help make this thesis a reality. I gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM-Harvard, CT17/17-CT18/17).

I want to express my gratitude to the High Energy Physics Group members with whom I have shared an outstanding working environment: Fernando, Juan Abel, Marcos, Dani, Luis Ángel, Lab, David, Alberto, Mireia, Pablo, John, Valeria, Andrés, Isidro, Tjark, Alejandro, Álvaro, María Láinez, Nuria, Atreyee, Victor, Alba, Adithiya y María Cividanes. To the MAGICians, with whom I have collaborated on several projects. A special thanks to the 1ES 0647+250 paper team: Jorge Otero, Daniela Dorner, David Paneque, and Vandad Fallah Ramazani. Thank you also to the members of the LST collaboration analysis group, in particular Abelardo Moralejo, Rubén López Coto, Seiya Nozaki, and Thomas Vuillaume, with whom I worked on the LST-1 performance paper and from whom I learned a great deal.

Thank you to everyone I met on the MAGIC and LST-1 data-taking shifts for making them such “wow” experiences. I would also like to thank Wystan for the opportunity to stay at the Whipple Observatory. I am grateful to Lab, Bill, Qi, and Jack for considering me as one of their own.

Gracias a mis amigos del pueblo Javi, Álvaro y Fernan por hacerme disfrutar de los Montes de Toledo en la mejor compañía. También a Edgar, Miguel, Pablo, Álvaro, Yoli, Carlos, Jaime, Rubén y Luis por vuestra amistad y hacer de Leganés mi segunda casa. Gracias a Mario, Ángela, Paloma y Óscar con quien también he compartido amistad y muy buenos momentos durante estos años.

Finalmente, quiero agradecer a mi familia, en especial a mi madre, padre y hermano por su apoyo y ayuda inagotables. Mis últimas palabras son para Laura, gracias por estar a mi lado a lo largo de este camino y ser un apoyo imprescindible.

Contents

Resumen	iv
Abstract	vii
Preamble	x
1 Introduction	1
1.1 A brief history of cosmic ray research	2
1.2 Sources in the high-energy sky	3
1.3 Extensive air showers	6
1.3.1 Cherenkov radiation	9
1.3.2 Fluorescence emission	11
1.4 Detection principles	14
1.5 The MAGIC telescopes	16
1.6 The Cherenkov Telescope Array	17
1.6.1 Large-Sized Telescope prototype	21
2 Simulation of fluorescence emission in extensive air showers	27
2.1 CORSIKA	30
2.1.1 Workflow	30
2.1.2 Cherenkov subroutine	33
2.2 Implementation of fluorescence emission in CORSIKA	36
2.3 Fluorescence contamination in the Cherenkov technique	37
2.3.1 General features of the light distribution on ground	40
2.3.2 Energy dependence	44
2.3.3 Dependence on shower zenith angle	46
2.3.4 Fluorescence contamination in off-axis observations	48
2.4 ShowerModel	49
2.5 Operation with Cherenkov telescopes in fluorescence mode	52

2.6	Conclusions	54
3	Analysis of Cherenkov telescope data	55
3.1	CTA analysis framework	56
3.1.1	Data levels	56
3.1.2	<code>ctapipe</code>	59
3.2	Calibration	61
3.3	Event reconstruction and selection	61
3.4	High level analysis	62
3.4.1	Detection significance and sky maps	62
3.4.2	Spectrum and light curve	63
3.4.3	Gammapy	65
3.5	MAGIC data analysis chain	67
3.5.1	Low-level analysis and reconstruction	67
3.5.2	High-level analysis	70
4	Analysis of LST-1 data	73
4.1	Analysis library for the LST-1 data	74
4.1.1	Calibration	74
4.1.2	Event reconstruction and selection	75
4.1.3	Contributions to the development of <code>cta-lstchain</code>	77
4.2	On-site analysis pipeline for the LST-1	82
4.2.1	Motivation	83
4.2.2	Description	84
4.2.3	LST-1 on-site data processing	92
4.2.4	Discussion	97
5	Performance of the Large Size Telescope prototype	102
5.1	Context	103
5.2	LST-1 observations and data-quality selection	103
5.3	Monte Carlo simulations	105
5.4	Analysis	110
5.5	Comparison between simulations and observations	115
5.6	Performance metrics	117
5.7	Crab Nebula spectrum and light curve	124
5.8	Conclusions	131

6	Multiwavelength study of the emission from the blazar 1ES 0647+250	134
6.1	Introduction	135
6.2	Multi-wavelength data sample	137
6.3	Variability analysis	142
6.4	Cross-band correlation	147
6.5	Spectral analysis	150
6.6	Redshift estimation	154
6.7	Broadband SED	157
6.8	Discussion	161
6.9	Conclusions	168
7	Conclusions	170
7.1	Fluorescence relevance in the Cherenkov technique	171
7.2	Development of the on-site analysis pipeline for LST-1	172
7.3	Performance of the LST-1 from Crab Nebula observations	173
7.4	Long-term MWL characterization of the BL Lac object 1ES 0647+250	174
A	Analysis of other blazars within MAGIC Collaboration	176
A.1	1ES 1959+650	177
A.1.1	Multi-wavelength observations and analysis	177
A.2	BL Lacertae	182
A.2.1	Multi-wavelength observations and analysis	183
B	Stay at Whipple observatory: VERITAS and pSCT-CTA	187
	Bibliography	x

Resumen

Esta tesis se enmarca en un contexto a caballo entre dos generaciones de telescopios Cherenkov terrestres de rayos gamma de muy alta energía. Los instrumentos actuales, en operación desde hace unos 15 años, se encuentran en un estado de gran madurez tanto operacionalmente como en términos de explotación científica. Los telescopios prototipos de la nueva generación que conformará el observatorio Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) se han construido recientemente y actualmente se encuentran en fase de puesta a punto, comenzando incluso a producir resultados científicos. En este sentido, el trabajo de la tesis se ha desarrollado en dos frentes distintos:

- Un lado técnico en el que se ha desarrollado software tanto de simulación como de análisis para la reconstrucción, reducción de datos tomados por estos instrumentos y la caracterización de estos.
- Otro lado científico en el que se ha caracterizado la emisión multi-frecuencia concentrada en chorros relativistas de un AGN tipo blazar, los objetos más numerosos en el cielo de rayos gamma de muy alta energía.

Las técnicas de reconstrucción de las señales detectadas por estos instrumentos se fundamenta en detalladas simulaciones de Monte Carlo de las cascadas atmosféricas de partículas iniciadas por rayos gamma y rayos cósmicos energéticos, así como su detección por medio de la radiación Cherenkov producida como consecuencia del paso de partículas cargadas ultrarelativistas por la atmósfera. Dichas cascadas también producen emisión de luz de fluorescencia, pero debido a su menor intensidad y diferente distribución angular isótropa a diferencia de la emisión de luz Cherenkov concentrada a lo largo de la cascada, su contribución a la señal registrada por los telescopios Cherenkov se desprecia. Por tanto las simulaciones se enfocan principalmente en un detallado tratamiento de la emisión de luz Cherenkov dejando a un lado el componente de fluorescencia. No obstante con la venida de la nueva generación de arrays de telescopios de Cherenkov (como CTA) a escalas kilométricas, se espera que la contribución de la

fluorescencia a la señal detectada por los telescopios alejados de la cascada alrededor de 1 km no sea del todo despreciable.

En este sentido, una de las partes de la tesis ha consistido en implementar con un gran nivel de detalle la emisión de fluorescencia dentro del software de simulación de cascadas atmosféricas más usado por los instrumentos diseñados para detectar radiación cósmica, CORSIKA. Los primeros resultados obtenidos gracias a estas simulaciones apuntan a que la contaminación de la luz de fluorescencia en la señal detectada por telescopios Cherenkov de imagen a distancias de aproximadamente 1 km es aproximadamente del 5%. Por otro lado, en detectores de Cherenkov de gran campo de visión, la contribución puede llegar a ser en torno al 40%.

Otra gran parte de la tesis ha estado centrada en la puesta a punto del nuevo telescopio LST-1 que formará parte del observatorio CTA norte. Mi contribución se ha centrado en el desarrollo de la cadena de análisis on-site que se encarga de estandarizar el procesado de los datos tomados por el telescopio el día posterior a ser tomados. Esto ha permitido el análisis de una ingente cantidad de observaciones usando de forma eficiente el centro de cómputo instalado al lado del telescopio, haciendo disponibles los datos reducidos al resto de la colaboración. En este contexto, también hemos contribuido a la caracterización del telescopio mediante el análisis de simulaciones y observaciones de la Nebulosa del Cangrejo tomadas durante la fase de puesta a punto. Hemos evaluado el área efectiva de colección de rayos gamma, la resolución angular, y en energía y la curva de sensibilidad del telescopio. Además hemos obtenido el espectro y curva de luz de la Nebulosa del Cangrejo (considerada fuente de calibración a las más altas energías) compatible con medidas anteriores de otros instrumentos. Todo ello valida el correcto funcionamiento del telescopio y supone el trabajo de referencia para el análisis de cualquier otra fuente observada por este telescopio.

Por último, en cuanto al estudio de blazares en un contexto multi-longitud de onda, hemos caracterizado la emisión a lo largo del espectro electromagnético del objeto BL Lac 1ES 0647+250, monitoreado durante una década. Esta extensa muestra nos ha permitido caracterizar la variabilidad y encontrar indicios de correlación entre las distintas bandas de energías. Encontramos que la emisión en radio sufre un retraso de unos pocos cientos de días respecto a la emisión en el óptico y rayos gamma. Lo cual sugiere que la emisión no es co-espacial en las diferentes energías. También estimamos el redshift de esta fuente cuyo valor aún está en debate en la literatura. Por último modelamos la emisión espectral multilongitud de onda dentro del escenario leptónico.

Este trabajo concluye que:

- Con la sofisticación y mejora de la sensibilidad de los nuevos instrumentos, las simulaciones Monte Carlo tienen que ser cada vez más detalladas e incluir procesos hasta ahora despreciados como la radiación de fluorescencia con el fin de minimizar los errores sistemáticos de los análisis.
- El desarrollo de software para la cadena de análisis de datos del LST-1 ha sido especialmente importante y útil durante la puesta en marcha del telescopio, especialmente asistiendo en la subsanación de errores detectados durante la toma de datos y facilitando la generación de resultados en la época de ciencia temprana. Con ello, determinamos que el comportamiento de este nuevo telescopio es el esperado y está preparado para obtener resultados científicos fiables. No obstante, notamos que los nuevos instrumentos que están comenzando sus andaduras en solitario aún no son tan competitivos como los actuales por el hecho de no operar todavía en modo estereoscópico.
- Finalmente, los estudios de la emisión multilongitud de onda a partir de muestras de datos que abarcan varios años son especialmente relevantes en la caracterización de la variabilidad y correlación entre las diferentes bandas, dando lugar a restricciones sobre las regiones de emisión.

Abstract

This thesis is framed in a context between two generations of ground-based Cherenkov telescopes for very high energy gamma rays (VHE, > 50 GeV). The current instruments, in operation for about 15 years, are in a shape of great maturity regarding operations and scientific exploitation. The prototype telescopes of the new generation that will be part of the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) are currently in their commissioning phase. Some are even starting to produce scientific results. In this sense, the work of the thesis has been developed on two different fronts:

- A technical side, in which both simulation and analysis software was developed for the reconstruction and analysis of the data and the characterization of these instruments.
- On the scientific side, we have characterized the multi-frequency emission concentrated in relativistic jets of a blazar AGN, the most numerous objects in the sky with very high energy gamma rays.

The reconstruction techniques of the signals detected by these instruments are based on detailed Monte Carlo simulations of atmospheric particle showers initiated by gamma rays and energetic cosmic rays, as well as their detection through Cherenkov radiation produced as a consequence of the passage of ultrarelativistic charged particles through the atmosphere. These showers also produce fluorescence light emission, which has a lower intensity and isotropic angular distribution as opposed to the Cherenkov light emission concentrated along the shower axis. Consequently, fluorescence contribution to the signal recorded by the Cherenkov telescopes is neglected, and the simulations focus mainly on the detailed treatment of the Cherenkov light emission leaving aside the fluorescence component. However, with the new generation of Cherenkov telescope arrays (such as CTA) at kilometer scales, it is expected that the contribution of fluorescence to the signal detected by telescopes far from the shower at around 1 km is not entirely negligible.

In this sense, one of the parts of the thesis has consisted in implementing with a high level of detail the fluorescence emission within the atmospheric shower simulation software most used by the instruments designed to detect cosmic radiation, CORSIKA. Initial results from these simulations indicate that the contamination of fluorescence light in the signal detected by imaging Cherenkov telescopes at distances of about 1 km is about 5%. On the other hand, in wide field-of-view Cherenkov detectors, the contribution can be as high as about 40%.

Another major part of the thesis focuses on the commissioning of the new LST-1 telescope that will be part of the CTA north observatory. My contribution has been focused on developing the on-site analysis chain that is in charge of standardizing the processing of the data taken by the telescope the day after they were taken. This work has allowed the analysis of a huge amount of observations using efficiently the computing center installed next to the telescope, making the reduced data available to the rest of the collaboration. In this context, we have also contributed to the telescope characterization by analyzing simulations and observations of the Crab Nebula taken during the commissioning phase. We have evaluated the effective gamma-ray collection area, the angular and energy resolution, and the flux sensitivity of the telescope. We have also obtained the spectrum and light curve of the Crab Nebula (considered a calibration source at the highest energies) compatible with previous measurements from other instruments. All this validates the correct operation of the telescope. This work is the reference for analyzing any other source observed by the LST-1.

Finally, regarding the study of blazars in a multiwavelength context, we have characterized the emission along the electromagnetic spectrum of the BL Lac 1ES 0647+250 object, monitored for a decade. This extensive sample has allowed us to characterize the variability and find indications of correlation between the different energy bands. We find that the radio emission is delayed by a few hundred days with respect to the optical and gamma-ray emissions, suggesting that the origin of the radio emission is not co-spatial to other bands. We also estimate the redshift of this source, whose value is still under debate in the literature. Finally, we model the multiwavelength spectral emission within the leptonic scenario.

This work concludes that:

- With the sophistication and improved sensitivity of new instruments, new MC simulations have to be more detailed and therefore include so far neglected processes such as fluorescence radiation to minimize systematic errors in the analyses.

- The development of software for the LST-1 data analysis chain has been particularly important and useful during the telescope's commissioning, especially assisting in debugging errors detected during data acquisition and facilitating the generation of results in the early science epoch. In doing so, we determined that the performance of this new telescope is as expected and is ready to obtain reliable scientific results. However, we note that the new instruments starting their solo runs are not as competitive as the current generation because they are not yet operating in stereoscopic mode.
- Finally, studies of multiwavelength emission from data samples spanning several years are especially relevant in characterizing the variability and correlation between the different bands, leading to constraints on the emission regions.

Preamble

It is difficult to fit the work done in this thesis in a unifying thread. Technical developments are constantly occurring in gamma-ray astrophysics, a relatively young field of research born just a few decades ago. When an instrument is built and commissioned for stable and reliable operation, one is already thinking about improvements and planning the development of the next generation of instruments. Of course, in the meantime, the instruments must be exploited scientifically, which is the ultimate goal.

In the technical part of the thesis, I have worked on developing software for simulation programs and analyzing data from Cherenkov telescopes, both pillars in the reconstruction and interpretation of the detected signals to be able to do gamma-ray astronomy ultimately.

On the scientific side, this thesis has focused on the study of blazar-type AGN, those potentially observable at the highest energies. The processes that give rise to the energy emission from these objects are still under debate, as well as the region in which this radiation originates. In particular, gamma-ray observations allow us to study the innermost part of AGNs. During these years, I have been working on the temporal and spectral characterization of the multi-band emission of the object 1ES 0647+250, observed for a decade by many instruments along the electromagnetic spectrum, a project led by MAGIC Collaboration. The extensive dataset allows us to study the variability of the emissions and inter-band correlation, bringing some insight to the open questions just mentioned about the jetted emission in AGNs.

This document is organized into seven chapters and two appendices:

Chapter 1. We briefly introduce the field of cosmic ray research and very high-energy gamma-ray astronomy performed by ground-based instruments. The extensive atmospheric cascades initiated by cosmic rays are presented, focusing on Cherenkov and fluorescence emission. Detection techniques using these two types of radiation are presented. In addition, the two atmospheric imaging Cherenkov telescope systems

that I have worked with in this thesis, MAGIC and LST-1, prototype telescope for the future CTA gamma-ray observatory, are introduced.

Chapter 2. The work carried out on the study of the fluorescence emission of atmospheric cascades in detection techniques based on Cherenkov light is presented. First, the main simulation tool used in this work, CORSIKA, is described. Then, the implementation of fluorescence emission in this code is detailed. Simulation-based results on the relevance of Cherenkov light in detection techniques based on recording Cherenkov light and their implications for possible new modes of observation are presented. Finally, a modeling tool complementary to the simulations is introduced.

Chapter 3. The procedure and general concepts of the analysis of data obtained by Cherenkov telescopes in the context of CTA and MAGIC are described.

Chapter 4. The analysis library and on-site data processing chain for the LST-1 are presented. My contributions to these programs and processing the first data taken by LST-1 during its commissioning phase are described.

Chapter 5. The evaluation of LST-1 performance using Monte Carlo simulations and Crab Nebula data during the commissioning phase is described. The spectrum and light curve of this object are presented as a validation test of the instrument for its scientific exploitation.

Chapter 6. The characterization of the multi-wavelength emission of the BL Lac 1ES 0647+250 object after a decade of observations is described. We discuss the evolution of the emission state, its variability, and the possible correlation between the different energy bands. In addition, we obtain a new value of the redshift of this source. Finally, the multi-wavelength emission from this object is modeled assuming a leptonic scenario.

Chapter 7. The conclusions of each work collected in the previous papers are summarized.

Appendix A. Preliminary analyses of other blazars observed by MAGIC telescopes in the context of multi-wavelength observing campaigns are presented.

Appendix B. It contains a summary of the activities carried out during my three-month stay at the Whipple Observatory, working on the VERITAS and pSCT-CTA Collaborations.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 A brief history of cosmic ray research

The history of Cosmic Rays (CR) is about one hundred years old. However, its first origins can be traced even further. The experiments of Coulomb already revealed that the charge accumulated by bodies is lost with time. Later, it was shown that this effect, the discharge of electroscopes, was happening even if it was enclosed in a crystal bottle. This effect was dubbed the *dark current* and attributed to some kind of ionization effect present in the atmosphere.

Around 1911-13, Victor F. Hess investigated the origin of the *dark current* using electroscopes aboard balloons. He showed that the ionization increases with height. Later, it was thus deduced that this radiation consists of cosmic particles. This result earned him the Nobel prize in 1936.

In the following years, newly developed particle detectors led to several discoveries about cosmic rays. Among them, we name the discovery of the positron, the pion, and the muon, created by cosmic ray interactions in the atmosphere. Cosmic rays physics gave origin to particle physics, and they walked together until the advent of modern particle accelerators. Around 1938, Pierre Auger carried out a complete study of the behavior of the secondary particles created in the atmosphere by the interaction of cosmic rays, which form the so-called extensive air showers (EASs), which were the basis of many of the following developments.

Despite these discoveries, the origin of cosmic rays remained unknown. Different experiments and techniques were developed to search for their origin. Large arrays of particle detectors were deployed starting in the 1950s to measure EASs and infer the properties of the particles originating them. They showed that the range of energies of CRs is enormous, reaching up to 10^{20} eV, and their distribution is approximately isotropic in the sky, unable to find definite sources.

At the end of the 1960s, the Whipple observatory developed the Cherenkov technique, based on the effect first measured by Galbraith and Jelly in 1954, by which EASs are accompanied by a brief but intense pulse of Cherenkov light. It was not until 1989 that this effort bore its fruits with the undisputed discovery of the first cosmic source of Very High Energy photons, the Crab Nebula ([Weekes et al., 1989](#)). To achieve this milestone, the Cherenkov detectors had to become imaging cameras for which algorithms to identify gamma-ray-initiated EASs were developed. Nowadays, the technique is used by the Imaging Atmospheric Cherenkov Telescopes (IACTs) and is the central point of this thesis.

1.2 Sources in the high-energy sky

Currently, there are around 250 sources detected in the VHE gamma-ray band (see Fig. 1.1), mostly by the current generation of IACTs, the High Energy Stereoscopic System (H.E.S.S.), the Major Atmospheric Gamma Imaging Cherenkov telescopes (MAGIC), and the Very Energetic Radiation Imaging Telescope Array System (VERITAS). Within our Galaxy, many sources have been detected in VHE gamma rays, among them there are pulsars, pulsar wind nebulae (PWN), gamma-ray binaries, novae, and supernova remnants. On the other hand, among the extragalactic source, we mostly find Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN). See [Bose et al. \(2022\)](#) for a recent review of the TeV emitting sources. Since they are used throughout this thesis, a brief description of the paradigm of Supernova remnants, the Crab PWN, and the blazar subclass of AGNs, follows.

Figure 1.1: Sources in the VHE gamma-ray sky. Credit TeVCat (<http://tevcat2.uchicago.edu/>).

Crab Pulsar Wind Nebulae

The Crab Nebula, located at a distance of about 2 kpc ([Trimble, 1973](#)), is a PWN aftermath of a star explosion dated in 1054 AD. As a consequence, a neutron star remains spinning in the center of the nebula with a period of 33 ms. The broadband emission of both the pulsar and the nebula spans from radio to gamma rays (see review by [Bühler and Blandford, 2014](#), and references therein). Figure 1.2 depicts the multiwavelength spectral energy distribution (SED) from the Crab pulsar and nebula.

The detection of PeV emission was also recently reported by [LHAASO Collaboration et al. \(2021\)](#).

Figure 1.2: Crab nebula and pulsar broadband spectral energy distribution from the multiwavelength data compiled in [Bühler and Blandford \(2014\)](#). Credit of the plot: Gammapy developers.

It was the first astronomical source detected in the very-high-energy (VHE) gamma-ray band by [Weekes et al. \(1989\)](#). After several decades of VHE gamma-ray observations, various instruments have demonstrated that the Crab Nebula presents a steady emission in such energy range, taking into account the systematic uncertainties ([Konopelko et al., 1996](#); [Hillas et al., 1998](#); [Tanimori et al., 1998](#); [Aleksić et al., 2015c](#); [Adams, C. B. et al., 2022](#)). Therefore, being the brightest steady point-like source in the VHE gamma-ray band, the Crab Nebula is considered the standard candle in this energy range and is typically used as a source to calibrate IACTs and assess their performances. In this thesis, we use Crab Nebula observations to evaluate the capabilities of the Large-Sized Telescope prototype (LST-1) in Sect. 5.

Active Galactic Nuclei

AGNs are radio-loud galaxies powered by a central massive black hole, some of them

producing ultra-relativistic jetted emission. Those whose jetted emission is aligned with our line-of-sight are called *blazars* (see Fig. 1.3). Blazars are typically classified into two classes attending to their optical spectra: those which do not present noticeable features (either weak or unusual) are known as BL Lacertae objects¹ (BL Lacs for short), and those whose optical spectra are characterized by intense, broad emission lines, are so-called Flat Spectrum Radio Quasars (FSRQs). A thorough review of the AGN taxonomy can be found in [Urry and Padovani \(1995\)](#).

Figure 1.3: Overview of AGN unification model. From [Thorne et al. \(2022\)](#).

The emission from these objects is dominated by non-thermal processes giving rise to a broadband SED spanning across the entire electromagnetic spectrum from radio to VHE gamma rays and commonly presenting a high variability over different time scales. Their observed spectra feature two humps resulting from the acceleration mechanisms (either leptonic or hadronic) of the relativistic particles ejected by the jet ([Ghisellini et al., 2017](#)). The lower-energy bump, ranging from the optical band to X-rays, is traditionally explained by synchrotron radiation emitted by accelerated electrons and positrons in the presence of magnetic fields. The higher energy bump (spanning from X-rays to VHE gamma rays) is thought to be due to the inverse Compton scattering of lower energy photons by charged particles that transfer part of their energy to them. Such charged particles may be the same population of leptons that produce synchrotron radiation and the same synchrotron radiation stimulated by inverse Compton,

¹Because BL Lacertae is the paradigm of this kind of source.

a scenario known as self-synchrotron Compton (SSC) (Konigl, 1981; Maraschi et al., 1992). Alternatively, the boosted seed photons might not come from the jet but from an external radiation field instead, a model known as external Compton (EC) (Dermer and Schlickeiser, 1993). Also, hadronic scenarios have been proposed to explain the higher-energy hump emission of the broadband SED (e.g., Mannheim, 1993; Cerruti et al., 2015). None of these scenarios fully explain the variability observed in these objects.

Based on the frequency of the maximum synchrotron emission, located between the infrared and X-ray bands, BL Lacs are further classified into low- (LBL, $\nu_{\text{peak}} < 10^{14}$ Hz), intermediate- (IBL, 10^{14} Hz $< \nu_{\text{peak}} < 10^{15}$ Hz) and high-energy-peaked (HBL, $\nu_{\text{peak}} > 10^{15}$ Hz) BL Lacs (Padovani and Giommi, 1995). In addition, another sort of BL Lacs was introduced by Costamante et al. (2001), naming those whose synchrotron peak is above $\nu_{\text{peak}} > 10^{17}$ Hz extreme HBLs (EHBLs).

1.3 Extensive air showers

Energetic cosmic particles impinging the atmosphere produce cascades of secondary particles known as EASs. If the primary particle is a hadron, it will experience nuclear interactions with the molecules of the atmosphere, fragmenting into smaller nuclei and producing, in turn, other hadrons (mostly pions). These processes give rise to subsequent hadronic chained interactions, forming the hadronic component of the shower. After losing energy and undergoing interactions on their way, the charged hadrons may disintegrate into muons and corresponding neutrinos, giving rise to a muon component of the cascade. On the other hand, the neutral pions decay into two photons which, in the presence of other nuclei, give rise to electron-positron pairs, which in turn, by bremsstrahlung radiation, produce photons, thus initiating an electromagnetic cascade. Figure 1.4 shows the three particle components of a hadron-induced air shower. In contrast, showers initiated by gamma rays, electrons, and positrons have only the electromagnetic component driven by alternating bremsstrahlung interactions and e^{\pm} pair creation. For a thorough review of EAS physics, see Anchordoqui et al. (2004).

The primary particle's energy is completely absorbed by the atmosphere, which acts as a calorimeter. This energy is used to create new particles, which radiate and, eventually, ionize the medium, losing their energy. In the case of a hadronic shower, only a few secondary particles, such as neutrinos and muons, penetrate the atmosphere, reaching the surface carrying a small part of the primary particle's energy. However,

Figure 1.4: Schematic view of the components of a cosmic-ray-induced extensive air shower. Taken from [Schellart \(2015\)](#).

most of the energy is transferred to the electromagnetic component, where the cascading process continues until the electrons and positrons newly produced are more efficient at ionizing the air than at producing new photons through bremsstrahlung radiation (this occurs for e^\pm at about 86 MeV in the air). At this point, the number of produced charged particles in the shower (mostly electrons and positrons) is maximum, at around 10 km above sea level. Then it starts decreasing as new particles are no longer produced efficiently.

By detecting and analyzing the spatial, spectral, and temporal properties of the secondary particles, we can infer the properties of the primary incident particle², as the shower characteristics are quite different between those initiated by gamma-rays and protons (see an example of simulated showers in Fig. 1.5).

This idea is exploited in various ways in the different methods of measuring the energy deposited in the shower (see details in Section 1.4). The main approaches are: (1) to detect the shower particles that reach the ground with surface detector arrays, (2) to collect the air Cherenkov and fluorescence light emitted by the charged particles

²For this purpose, Monte Carlo simulations must be used to characterize the response of the different detectors and reconstruct the signal collected.

Figure 1.5: Comparison of simulated air showers initiated by 10 gamma rays of 300 GeV (top panel) and 10 protons of the same energy (bottom panel). Gamma-ray showers display a more similar structure than proton-induced showers, which present larger fluctuations because of the larger transfer of transverse momentum. Horizontal and vertical axes are indicated in kilometers, where the altitude starts at sea level. The color scheme of particle traces is as follows: gamma rays in green, electrons and positrons in blue, muons in red, protons in brown, charged pions in cyan, and neutral pions in magenta. From [de Naurois \(2000\)](#).

of the shower, and (3) to measure the radio synchrotron pulsed emission produced by

electron-positron pairs of the air shower deflected in the geomagnetic field (see, e.g., Huege, T. and Falcke, H., 2003).

1.3.1 Cherenkov radiation

Ultrarelativistic charged particles comprising the air showers (mostly electrons and positrons) travel faster than light in the air ($\beta > 1/n$, where n is the refractive index of the air³). The coherent depolarization of the air (see Fig. 1.6) induces the cone-shaped emission of Cherenkov light along the shower axis, with an opening angle given by

$$\cos \theta_c = \frac{1}{\beta n}.$$

In the case of the atmosphere, considering the variations of the refractive index with the altitude, this angle peaks at about 1° ⁴. The imprint of this light on the ground is a circular pool of light with a diameter of roughly 250 meters. In the GeV-TeV energy range and for vertical showers, the density of Cherenkov photons inside the pool is approximately constant, peaking at the pool edge and rapidly decreasing beyond it (see Fig. 1.7).

Figure 1.6: Depolarization of the medium caused by a particle passing through it. In the ultrarelativistic case, Cherenkov light is emitted in a wavefront characterized by the angle θ_c . From de Naurois and Mazin (2015).

The forward-beamed Cherenkov light travels practically at the same speed and direction as the particles down to the ground. This results in a beaming effect that condenses the light from the whole shower development in a pulse spanning a few

³Cherenkov radiation produced in other media like water can also be used for detecting shower particles that reach the ground with the so-called water Cherenkov detectors (see, e.g., Abraham et al., 2004; Abeyssekara et al., 2013). Considering the refractive index of water, Cherenkov radiation is produced by charged particles with $\beta > 0.77$.

⁴For water, since $n_{\text{water}} > n_{\text{air}}$, Cherenkov opening angle is instead around 40° .

Figure 1.7: Left: Shower development and Cherenkov emission (taken from [de Naurois and Mazin, 2015](#)). Right: Cherenkov light pool from a simulated vertical shower induced by a 1 TeV gamma ray. Simulation performed using CORSIKA v7.6300, see Chapter 2.

nanoseconds. The number of photons emitted per unit of path length dx of a charged particle and unit wavelength ([Tamm and Frank, 1937](#)) is given by:

$$\frac{d^2 N_{ph}}{dx d\lambda} = 2\pi\alpha Z^2 \frac{\sin^2 \theta_c}{\lambda^2} \quad (1.1)$$

which shows that the Cherenkov light spectrum (Fig. 1.8) is proportional to $1/\lambda^2$. Considering the variation of the refractive index of the air along the atmosphere (and assuming the atmosphere in the hydrostatic and isothermal approximation), the Cherenkov yield per unit of mass thickness ($dX = \rho dx$, where ρ is the density of the medium) does not depend on the altitude:

$$\frac{d^2 N_{ph}}{dX d\lambda} \propto \frac{Z^2}{\lambda^2 T} \quad (1.2)$$

and it can be seen that the total amount of Cherenkov light yielded from a shower is roughly proportional to the energy of the primary particle (see, e.g. [de Naurois and Mazin, 2015](#)). Therefore, a calorimetric measurement of the Cherenkov light emitted from the air shower is a good proxy of the primary.

Figure 1.8: Spectrum from Cherenkov light emitted by charged particles in EASs peaking around 300-400 nm. At lower wavelengths, the atmosphere completely absorbs this radiation ($\propto 1/\lambda^2$). Photodetectors must be designed accordingly to have a quantum efficiency peaking at these frequencies. Taken from [Doering et al. \(2001\)](#).

1.3.2 Fluorescence emission

Atmospheric fluorescence⁵ is produced isotropically by the radiative de-excitation of molecules previously excited or ionized by charged particles of an EAS ([Arqueros et al., 2009a](#)). In the near UV, molecular nitrogen is mainly responsible for this light emission, which is dominated by the so-called Second Positive system (2P) of N_2 ($C^3\Pi_u \rightarrow B^3\Pi_g$) and the First Negative system (1N) of N_2^+ ($B^2\Sigma_u^+ \rightarrow X^2\Sigma_g^+$), see Fig. 1.9. Each one consists of several molecular bands according to the vibrational quantum numbers v', v of the upper and lower electronic states of the transition, respectively. A small contribution from the Gaydon-Herman system of N_2 is also present ([Ave et al., 2007](#)). Figure 1.10 presents the spectrum from air-fluorescence emission measured by the AIRFLY Collaboration.

Although the radiative lifetimes of involved molecular states are of some tens of nanoseconds, the emission in the lower atmosphere is shortened down to a few nanoseconds due to collisional quenching, that is, excited molecules can also relax without

⁵This radiation should be named scintillation, although, for historical reasons, the cosmic-ray community refers to it as fluorescence.

Figure 1.9: Diagram of the main nitrogen molecular levels responsible for the air-fluorescence emission represented by the downward red and blue arrows. Taken from [Arqueros et al. \(2009b\)](#).

emitting light through collisions with other molecules, oxygen and water vapor being the dominant quenchers. The collisional cross-section depends on the kinetic energy of the encounters. As a consequence, the light intensity generated by an electron moving in the air depends on the atmospheric conditions (i.e., pressure, temperature and humidity).

Shower electrons and positrons are mostly responsible for the fluorescence emission, while other charged particles, if present (e.g., in hadronic showers), contribute to a minor extent. The deposited energy by these particles, used to excite the molecules responsible for fluorescence emission, is one of the key ingredients in estimating the intensity of the air fluorescence emission and can be computed via Monte Carlo (MC) simulations (see Chapter 2). The number of air fluorescence photons (N) emitted per unit of mass thickness ($dX = \rho dx$, where ρ is the density of the medium, and dx the differential path length) depends on the deposited energy by the charged particles per unit of mass thickness, $(dE/dX)_{\text{dep}}$ and the fluorescence yield parameter (Y) as

$$\frac{dN}{dX} = Y(P, T, h) \left(\frac{dE}{dX} \right)_{\text{dep}} \quad (1.3)$$

Figure 1.10: Air fluorescence spectrum measured by the AIRFLY Collaboration from 3 MeV electrons at 800 hPa. Taken from [Boháčová \(2009\)](#).

where the fluorescence yield, defined as the number of photons emitted per unit of deposited energy, is a key parameter to quantify the intensity of the fluorescence emission. It has been shown that this parameter is basically independent of the energy and type of ionizing particle ([Rosado et al., 2014](#)), that is, the fluorescence emission is proportional to the energy deposit at given atmospheric conditions. For a molecular band at a wavelength λ , the fluorescence yield at pressure P can be expressed as

$$Y_\lambda = \frac{Y_\lambda^0}{1 + P/P'_\lambda}, \quad (1.4)$$

where Y_λ^0 is the fluorescence yield in the absence of collisional quenching (i.e., when $P \rightarrow 0$). The parameter P'_λ is defined as the pressure for which the probability of radiative de-excitation equals that of collisional quenching and depends on temperature T and humidity h .

Alternatively, the fluorescence yield for any molecular band can be expressed relative to the absolute yield measured for a reference band in dry air at a given pressure P_0 and temperature T_0 as

$$Y_\lambda(P, T, h) = Y_{337}(P_0, T_0) I_\lambda(P_0, T_0) \frac{1 + P_0/P'_{337}(T_0)}{1 + P/P'_\lambda(T, h)}, \quad (1.5)$$

where the dependencies on the atmospheric parameters are now put explicitly. Here, we use the one centered at 337 nm wavelength as reference, which is the most intense band of the air fluorescence spectrum and corresponds to the 2P ($v' = 0 \rightarrow v = 0$) transition (see Fig. 1.10). Rosado et al. (2014) report a world-average fluorescence yield $Y_{337} = 7.04 \pm 0.24 \text{ MeV}^{-1}$ at 800 hPa and 293 K in dry air. The fluorescence yield from other bands can then be scaled based on their relative intensities $I_\lambda(P_0, T_0)$ to the reference band reported, for example, in Ave et al. (2007).

1.4 Detection principles

Several techniques are used for the detection and characterization of EAS. The most important rely on:

- Detecting the secondary particles of the shower that reach the ground: electrons, positrons, gamma rays, muons, or optical photons, to measure their density distribution on the ground and their arrival times.
- Imaging the distribution of air Cherenkov light, recording its shape and temporal characteristics.
- Recording the air fluorescence light received at the ground with limited imaging.
- Measuring the coherent radio emission produced by the shower front.

As this work is mainly concerned with Cherenkov and fluorescence detection, we will restrict ourselves to describing these techniques.

Imaging atmospheric Cherenkov telescopes

Since its inception in the 1970s, IACTs have been some of the most successful instruments to detect and characterize EASs originated by primaries in the range of tens of GeVs to tens of TeVs. They excel in gamma/hadron separation and angular and energy resolution, while they lack wide-angle coverage and operate with limited duty cycles.

Cherenkov Telescopes are composed of large mirrors that focus the fast Cherenkov pulses on cameras composed of high-speed photon detectors, in general photomultipliers or silicon photomultipliers. IACTs point towards or slightly offset from the source they are observing and have limited fields of view of diameters up to 10° , which given the scarcity of VHE sources for most regions of the sky, typically include less than ~ 5

sources⁶. Mirrors are usually composed of individual facets which can be oriented to compensate for the deformations induced when they change their pointing. To preserve the small-time dispersion of the Cherenkov front, the mirror geometry usually follows a Davies-Cotton or parabolic shape. At the same time, the individual facets are spherical surfaces for easier machining.

The cameras of IACTs are large, up to close to 2 meters in diameter for the LST-1 (see Sect. 1.6.1 and Cortina, 2019), the largest of its kind. Its size is due to optical limitations, the incompressibility of the so-called *etendue*, equivalent to the Liouville theorem for optics. Optics also limits the angular resolution achievable in the focal planes, a limitation which is somewhat relieved in Schwarzschild-Coude (SC) designs. Both factors lead to cameras that harbour a small number of pixels (around 1-2 thousand for single mirror models and not more than 10-20 thousand for SC ones) of large size. Some preamplification is invariantly attached to the pixels to transmit their signals from the camera to a central place; its sophistication depends on the telescope. In some cases, signals are fully processed in the camera, while in others, they are transmitted and processed elsewhere.

Cherenkov observatories are nowadays composed of several Cherenkov telescopes that observe EAS stereoscopically, providing a 3D reconstruction of the shower. The analysis of shower images with machine learning algorithms became standard in the field more than 10 years ago, notably increasing the technique’s sensitivity (see, e.g., Bock et al., 2004; Albert et al., 2008; Ohm et al., 2009). More details on the Cherenkov technique are given in the following sections concerning the MAGIC telescopes and Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) observatory.

Wide-angle air Cherenkov detectors

The atmospheric Cherenkov light can also be registered by wide-angle Cherenkov detectors (WACD) arrays. Each unit usually consists of one or more photomultipliers that collect the light through a Winston cone of ~ 1 sr acceptance. These facilities are used as non-imaging γ -ray telescopes with an energy threshold of a few tens of TeV and large sky coverage (Karle et al., 1995; Tluczykont et al., 2014; Gress et al., 2013; Aharonian et al., 2021). They are also employed for cosmic-ray studies over 0.1 PeV.

Fluorescence telescopes

Fluorescence telescopes (FT) use fluorescence light to observe the development of EAS as they develop in the Earth’s atmosphere. They share many features with IACT, such

⁶There are however regions in the galactic plane with many gamma-ray emitters piling up.

as large reflecting mirrors, cameras with PMTs and small duty cycles, due to their operation preferably during dark nights. On the other hand, FTs do not generally operate in a pointing mode but instead survey large volumes of atmosphere. Fluorescence observatories are composed of several stations separated by large distances. Their positions delineate a region on the ground whose atmospheric volume is surveyed. Each station hosts several telescopes pointing towards the center of the region of interest but in slightly different directions, jointly covering a large field of view. In this way, when an EAS develops in the covered volume, its longitudinal development is recorded ideally from all the stations. Combining the data using this stereoscopic information allows the reconstruction of the trajectory of the EAS in the sky.

Time scales in FTs are larger than the ones of IACT, as they correspond to the development of showers in the atmosphere seen from an angle, so there is no compression as in the Cherenkov case. Since the shower front moves basically at the speed of light and covers distances of tens of kilometers; typical integration times for the recorded images are of tens to hundreds of microseconds.

FTs have energy thresholds starting around 10^{17} eV, because the stations are further from the shower, and the fluorescence light is emitted isotropically, a lower density of light is thus recorded. In return, they survey very large volumes of atmosphere, making them competitive for these high-energy ranges where fluxes drop dramatically.

Presently a few fluorescence-based observatories operate around the world, the most relevant being the Pierre Auger Observatory ([The Pierre Auger Collaboration, 2015](#)) and the Telescope Array ([Abu-Zayyad et al., 2012](#)). Projects to build space-based fluorescence observatories, such as EUSO (Extreme Universe Space Observatory) are still in the early demonstration stages (see, e.g., [Casolino et al., 2015](#); [Bertaina, 2021](#)).

1.5 The MAGIC telescopes

The MAGIC telescopes comprise two 17 m diameter IACTs observing the sky in VHE gamma rays in stereoscopic mode. They are situated at the Roque de los Muchachos Observatory, on the Canary island of La Palma (Spain), at an altitude of 2200 m above sea level. MAGIC operates in the range of energies from about 50 GeV up to several tens of TeV. Its sensitivity for energies above 300 GeV is about 0.7% of the Crab nebula flux for 50 hours of mid-zenith angle observations assuming point-like sources with Crab-like spectra (see [Aleksić et al., 2016](#), Table A.6). To increase its duty cycle, MAGIC also observes under moonlight conditions as described in [Ahnen et al. \(2017\)](#) with the disadvantage of increasing its energy threshold.

Figure 1.11: MAGIC telescopes at ORM (La Palma, Spain). Credit: Robert Wagner/MAGIC Collaboration.

1.6 The Cherenkov Telescope Array

The CTA⁷ is the next generation of ground-based Cherenkov telescope observatory, detecting gamma-rays in the energy range from 20 GeV to beyond 300 TeV (Gueta, 2021). CTA was conceived as a joint effort grounded on the experience gained by the previous and current generations of Cherenkov telescopes. The array will be composed of IACTs of three different sizes distributed into two sites, one in the northern hemisphere (CTA-North) at *Roque de Los Muchachos* Observatory (ORM) on the Canary Island of La Palma (Spain) and another located in the southern hemisphere (CTA-South) close to the Paranal Observatory (Chile). CTA will be an open gamma-ray observatory. Any scientist will be able to propose observations and access the data.

The three types of telescopes are the Small Size Telescope (SST), the Medium Size Telescope (MST) –with two optical designs: Davies-Cotton and Schwarzschild-Couder (SCT)–, and the Large Size Telescope (LST). Table 1.1 summarizes their main specifications and a render of the telescopes all to scale is shown in Fig. 1.12.

Having one site in each hemisphere assures the coverage of the whole sky. The

⁷<https://www.cta-observatory.org/>

Characteristics	MST			SST
	LST	FlashCam	NectarCam	
Energy range	20 - 150 GeV		150 GeV - 5 TeV	5 TeV - 300 TeV
Optical design	Parabolic	Modified Davies-Cotton	Schwarzschild-Couder	Schwarzschild-Couder
Primary reflector diameter [m]	23	11.5	9.7	4.3
Secondary reflector diameter [m]	-	-	5.4	1.8
Effective mirror area [m ²]	370	88	41	8
Focal length [m]	28	16	5.6	2.15
Total weight [ton]	103	82	80	19
Camera FoV [deg]	4.5	7.5	7.7	10.5
Pixels in the camera	1855	1764	1855	11328
Pixel FoV [deg]	0.1	0.17	0.17	0.067
Photodetector type	PMT	PMT	PMT	SiPM
Readout rate [kHz]	> 7.0	> 6.0	> 7.0	> 3.5
Sampling speed [GSample/s]	1	0.25	≈ 1	1
Pointing accuracy [arcsec]	< 14	< 7	< 7	< 7
Positioning time [s]	30		90	60

Table 1.1: Specifications of each type of CTA telescopes. Notes: the energy ranges indicated here refer to the range in which each sort of telescope outperforms the rest. The effective mirror area values reported include the shadowing from the telescope structure. Positioning time refers to a movement of 180 deg in azimuth (and > 30 deg in elevation). Adapted from <https://www.cta-observatory.org/project/technology/>

Figure 1.12: Render of the different types of CTA telescopes all to scale. From left to right: SST, MST(Schwarzschild-Couder), MST (Davies-Cotton) and LST. Credit: Gabriel Pérez Díaz, IAC.

telescope array configuration of each site depends on the part of the sky that is visible from each site. Driven by the fact that the galactic plane is observed at large elevations from the southern hemisphere, CTA-South will focus on galactic sources whose emission typically reaches energies above a few TeV. On the other hand, CTA-North will concentrate on the extragalactic sources, trying to reach the lowest energies of the VHE band.

Each kind of telescope covers a range of gamma-ray energies due to their different sensitivities. Telescopes with larger mirrors are capable of detecting faint flashes from low-energy showers. On the other hand, the array's effective collection area needs to be large to be competitive at the highest energies. This will be achieved by adding a kilometer array of small-sized telescopes, which are less expensive than the bigger ones considering the large number of telescopes needed to fill such a large area. Halfway between these two classes of telescopes, MSTs will provide the best sensitivity in the middle energy.

Over the last years, several studies have been conducted to optimize the array layout in both sites based on its overall performance (see, e.g., [Acharyya et al., 2019](#)). The latest proposed layout for each array is depicted in Fig. 1.13. The CTA-North array will be composed of 5 LST and 9 MST, covering an area of $\sim 0.25 \text{ km}^2$. The CTA-South array will consist of 14 MST and 40 SST spanning over $\sim 3 \text{ km}^2$. The

Figure 1.13: CTA layout proposed for the North (so-called *Alpha* configuration, left) and South (so-called *M6C1* configuration, right) sites. Taken from [Gueta \(2021\)](#).

question of placing four LSTs in the southern array (see left panel of Fig. 1.13) is still under discussion.

The differential sensitivity used as a performance benchmark is defined as the minimum flux to get a 5σ detection of a point-like source as a function of the energy. The expected CTA sensitivity for both sites is displayed in Fig. 1.14. More details can be found in [Gueta \(2021\)](#). CTA sensitivity will surpass that of the current IACT experiments in both hemispheres by a factor of 5-10 across its entire energy range. By design, above ~ 100 GeV CTA-South array has better sensitivity, being the difference larger as the energy increases. On the contrary, CTA-North is more sensitive below ~ 100 GeV. CTA complements perfectly at lower energies with *Fermi*-LAT. *Fermi*-LAT 10-year sensitivity for extragalactic background meets that of 50-hours CTA-North at approximately 50 GeV. On the contrary, the Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory (LHAASO) 1-year sensitivity starts being comparable to that of CTA-North at roughly 20 TeV ([Ma et al., 2022](#)), whereas the High-Altitude Water Cherenkov Observatory (HAWC) will also outperform the northern array in five years of observations starting at a few tens of TeV ([Abeysekara et al., 2017](#)). In the case of the southern array, no existing instrument is that competitive at the highest energies for steady sources. However, there is an effort to design and build a next-generation gamma-ray facility in the southern hemisphere in the next decade, the Southern Wide-field Gamma-ray Observatory (SWGGO). Preliminary studies foresee that SWGGO will start competing with the CTA-South array at ~ 10 TeV after five years of observations, for steady sources

(Albert et al., 2019; Hinton, 2021). As also stated in Gueta (2021), another important improvement of CTA will be its superior angular and energy resolution compared to the current IACT experiments and other non-imaging detection techniques.

To probe the novel technologies developed for the future CTA Observatory, several prototypes of the different types of telescopes have already been built in different locations and are being commissioned. Among them, the LST prototype is the only one placed in the final observatory location.

1.6.1 Large-Sized Telescope prototype

The CTA Large-Sized Telescope prototype⁸ (LST-1, Mazin, 2021), is located at the Observatorio del Roque de los Muchachos (ORM) in La Palma (see Fig. 1.15) nearby MAGIC telescopes, which is an advantage for the operation, maintenance and cross-calibration of the prototype in its early stage.

After its construction phase from 2016 to 2018, it was inaugurated in October 2018. Shortly after, in December 2018, it recorded its first Cherenkov signal. Presently, LST-1 is going through its commissioning phase, taking data on astrophysical targets since the end of 2019. It detected its first gamma-ray signal from an astrophysical source, the Crab Nebula, on November 23rd, 2019. Observations recorded since then have been used to evaluate the performance of the telescope prototype (see section 5).

The data-taking process starts with recording the light pulses generated in EASs, initiated by the interaction of primary particles with the atmosphere, so-called *events*. These flashes are concentrated onto the PMT camera in the primary focal plane. The camera provides a fast sampling of the triggered light pulses. During observations, the telescope records $\sim 10^4$ events per second. The electronic behind each PMT digitizes the signal into 40 consecutive 1-ns samples of their *waveforms* with a resolution of 12 bits. Before the observations, and interleaved with them, a much lower rate of artificial *calibration events* is also acquired. Altogether around 3 TB of raw data are recorded per hour of observation time. In the following, the LST-1 subsystems involved in the operation of the prototype are described. All of them are subject to future modifications according to Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO) compliance. The general description of all the components of the telescope can be found in Cortina (2019) and references therein. When available, other references are also indicated below for some of the subsystems.

⁸<http://lst1.iac.es/>

Figure 1.14: Differential point-source sensitivity as a function of the reconstructed energy for both CTA arrays for 50-hour observation time and pointing at 20 degrees zenith angle. Sensitivity from other instruments is also shown for comparison. Adapted from Gueta (2021). Up-to-date information about CTA performance can be accessed at <https://www.cta-observatory.org/science/ctao-performance>.

Figure 1.15: LST-1 at ORM (La Palma island, Spain). Credit: Tomohiro Inada.

Camera: It is equipped with 1855 photo-multiplier tubes (PMTs) grouped in 7-PMT modules (Fig. 1.16 a) with a quantum efficiency of approximately 40% at 350 nm. It is placed in the focal plane of the telescope, sealed from the exterior, as shown in Fig. 1.16 b. The camera has a field of view (FoV) of around 4.5 degrees in diameter. The signal from the photosensors is sampled at 1 GHz by readout electronics (nicknamed *Dragon readout*) based on the Domino Ring Sampler 4th generation (DRS4) chips (Nozaki et al., 2020b) embedded in the front-end boards. The dead time at the rate of 7.5 kHz is around 5%. To detect dim and intense showers, two readout channels with different amplification provide a wide dynamic range from 1 to 3000 p.e. More information can be found in Saito et al. (2021).

Trigger and timing system: A selective multi-level signal trigger scheme is followed to avoid an overflowing data stream due to high-rate camera sampling and digitization mainly containing noise. When the summed signal from a few neighboring modules is above a certain threshold in a short interval, the trigger signal is propagated to the Trigger Interface Board (TIB) (Tejedor et al., 2022), which manages the different trigger levels from the camera and tags them according to their source (e.g., *cosmic*, *calibration*, and *pedestal*). The TIB will also handle the signal from surrounding telescopes operating in stereo mode. The triggering of showers by several telescopes enhances the rejection of the night sky background (NSB). A White Rabbit timing

(a) A module of the LST-1 camera with 7 PMTs and corresponding light concentrators. Connected to them, there is a readout board with the DRS4 chips. Taken from [Sakurai et al. \(2019\)](#).

(b) Front view of the LST-1 camera. Credit: Tomohiro Inada.

Figure 1.16: Module of 7 photo-multiplier tubes (left) that composes the LST-1 camera (right).

system, disciplined by a Global Positioning System (GPS), provides event-wise absolute timestamps with microsecond precision based on counters from pulse per second (PPS) and 10 MHz clocks. A node of the White Rabbit network, so-called Unified Clock and Trigger System (UCTS), installed in every telescope timestamps the TIB trigger signal, ensuring a stable and synchronized timing system among the telescope array. The prototype UCTS implementation integrated into the LST-1 is described in [Champion et al. \(2017\)](#). Timestamps and trigger-type information from both systems are further distributed and included by the Event Builder (EVB) in each camera event packet. Even though here it is described the case of the LST-1, some features of these technologies imply having more than one telescope.

Calibration box: To convert the Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) counts registered by the front-end boards to photo-electrons, a calibration device located in the center of the dish uniformly illuminates the camera with fast laser pulses of adjustable intensity, giving rise to the so-called flat-field events. A detailed description can be found in [Palatiello et al. \(2019\)](#).

Drive system: Electric servomotors on both the elevation and azimuth axes move the telescope. The post-calibration pointing accuracy, smaller than $14''$, is achieved through an accurate bending model with the help of several devices mounted in the center of the dish (star-guider camera and inclinometers) and a set of light-emitting

diodes (LEDs) attached to the camera (see [Foffano et al., 2021](#)). Thanks to the light material used in its structure, repositioning to any point in the sky takes less than 20 seconds.

Optical system: LST-1 23-m parabolic reflector is composed of 198 hexagonal mirrors. An active mirror control (AMC) focuses the mirrors based on the pointing zenith angle. To assess that the mirrors are focused, point spread function (PSF) measurements are done by measuring the reflection of stars on a mobile screen inside the camera frame. The PSF of the LST-1 depends on the distance to the axis and ranges from 0.05° to 0.11° .

Auxiliary systems: Several monitoring systems assist the operation of the LST-1 and, in the future, the whole CTA-N. For instance, a weather station, a Raman Light Detection and Ranging system (LIDAR) ([Gaug et al., 2019a](#)), and an all-sky camera evaluate the weather conditions.

Data acquisition system (DAQ): A set of subsystems and their associated software forms the low-level basis of the telescope data-taking operation. The main ones are the cluster and camera controllers, EVB, and ZFITS writer. The EVB ([Hoffmann and Houles, 2012](#)) receives the data from the modules, applies the low-level online corrections, and assembles the *events*, which are stored on disk by the ZFITS writer software in sequential files.

Telescope control unit (TCU): It is the high-level control software of the telescope. It orchestrates and communicates the rest of the LST-1 subsystems involved in the observations. LST-1 operators control the telescope, through a graphical TCU interface, during regular observations and maintenance tasks. The TCU also logs information from all the aforementioned subsystems in a centralized database.

Computing infrastructure: An IT data center housing a compact computing cluster placed by the telescope allows us to record and process the data it acquired. The data center provides 55 computing nodes, each with 32 cores, for a total of 1760 cores and 3.4 PB of disk space. This cluster uses the CentOS operating system, administers the workload through the Simple Linux Utility For Resource Management (SLURM) batch scheduling system⁹, and implements the Fujitsu Scalable Cluster File System

⁹<https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

(FEFS) based on Lustre parallel distributed file system¹⁰. The members of the LST Collaboration have access to this on-site IT center and use it for the commissioning of the telescopes and preliminary astrophysics analysis. Its vast computing power is vital to make possible the low-level stages of the processing of LST-1 data. This IT center is expected to provide sufficient computing power and bandwidth for the operation of the rest of the telescopes to be built on-site, i.e., a total of 4 LSTs and 9 MSTs.

Figure 1.17: Overview of the LST IT onsite data center and other subsystems networked to it. Taken from Mazin (2021).

After being recorded and processed, data are transferred via the network to the computing center Port d’Informació Científica (PIC)¹¹ located in Barcelona (Spain). Additionally, all the data is replicated in another data center, the National Center for Frame Analysis of the Italian Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN-CNAF)¹², based in Bologna (Italy). These off-site data centers supply enough storage to ensure the preservation of the data products in the long term.

Due to its fast sampling, the LST-1 is optimized for the energy range from 20 GeV to 1 TeV. This low energy threshold, together with the fast repositioning, makes LST-1 especially suited for detecting the early emission from transient phenomena such as gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) (Carosi et al., 2021). Other important physics goals in this energy range are pulsars, binaries, and high-redshift AGN (see CTA Consortium, 2019).

¹⁰<https://www.lustre.org/>

¹¹<https://www.pic.es/>

¹²<https://www.cnaf.infn.it/>

Chapter 2

Simulation of fluorescence emission in extensive air showers

This study was conducted with the guidance of Jaime Rosado, José Luis Contreras, and Fernando Arqueros. I implemented additional subroutines that handle fluorescence light emission in the CORSIKA program. Then, I conducted the simulations and analyzed the resulting Cherenkov and fluorescence light distribution on the ground, obtaining the results presented in this chapter. I was also involved in the modifications needed in the `sim_telarray` software to deal with fluorescence photons in the simulation of the response of the telescopes. Finally, I contributed to the shower modeling software (`ShowerModel`) developed by Jaime Rosado, focusing on implementing the documentation, versioning system, and automatic workflows for the unitary tests and publishing the code.

This chapter summarizes the work started during my Master’s thesis and later continued during this thesis: the implementation of the air-fluorescence light emission in CORSIKA, a MC program to simulate the development of EASs. To that end, we followed a similar procedure to that used in [de Souza et al. \(2004\)](#). The two main goals of implementing fluorescence emission in CORSIKA are:

- The study of the contamination of the fluorescence light over the Cherenkov signal in telescopes and detectors using the Cherenkov technique.
- Exploring the feasibility of detecting VHE gamma rays with Cherenkov telescopes using the fluorescence technique.

The preliminary results were presented at the International Cosmic Ray Conference in 2017 ([Morcuende et al., 2017](#)). We showed that the fluorescence contribution to the signals of Cherenkov telescopes might be non-negligible in some cases. This work is an updated implementation of the fluorescence emission and systematic MC results to quantify this fluorescence contamination in ground-based Cherenkov telescopes in detail, resulting in the publication [Morcuende et al. \(2019\)](#).

The Cherenkov and fluorescence light emissions (see Sects. [1.3.1](#) and [1.3.2](#)) from the charged particles of EASs are the basis of several observational techniques in VHE gamma-ray astronomy and ultra-high-energy (UHE, $> 10^{17}$ eV) cosmic-ray physics as summarized in Sect. [1.4](#).

Photons from both light components emitted from any point in an EAS are indistinguishable at the telescope level because they arrive simultaneously and in the same wavelength range. However, the angular distributions of both components are quite different. The Cherenkov radiation is peaked at a small angle of $\sim 1^\circ$ around the shower axis, while the fluorescence emission is isotropic. Consequently, the signal of a telescope pointing towards the shower axis is dominated by the Cherenkov component. On the contrary, the signal of a telescope recording the shower transversely is dominated by the fluorescence. Another difference between both processes is that fluorescence emission is less efficient than Cherenkov production. For instance, a 1 GeV electron in 1 m of atmosphere near the ground generates about 30 Cherenkov photons but only about 4 fluorescence photons.

Fast Cherenkov pulses are recorded to image the EASs with the IACT technique. Alternatively, this light can also be registered by wide-angle Cherenkov detectors (WACD) arrays, which characterize the timing of the showers. The contribution of

fluorescence light to the signals recorded by both imaging and non-imaging γ -ray telescopes is assumed to be negligible. Fluorescence telescopes, on the other hand, register the track of the shower transversely in the atmosphere detecting the signal dominated by the fluorescence component. However, a non-negligible amount of Cherenkov light gets into the telescope and has to be included as a relevant ingredient in the reconstruction algorithm (Unger et al., 2008). Interestingly, the LHAASO project has designed flexible and mobile telescopes that can be operated in both Cherenkov and fluorescence modes (Zhang et al., 2011).

A detailed Monte Carlo (MC) simulation of the development of EASs is a key tool in this field in order to characterize the response of the instruments and reconstruct the properties of the primary particles based on the signal detected. Notably, CORSIKA (Heck et al., 1998) has been extensively used since the late '90s for this purpose¹. Cherenkov telescopes need detailed simulations of the Cherenkov radiation generated by the shower and its detection by the telescope. The Cherenkov light production was initially implemented in CORSIKA to simulate the HEGRA AIROBICC detector (Martinez et al., 1995) and later upgraded by Bernlöhner (2008). The simulation of the fluorescence telescope signals is customarily based on the generation of both Cherenkov and fluorescence photons from a one-dimension shower profile obtained by either an analytical EAS model or a MC code like CORSIKA (see, e.g., Pra, 2005).

Generally, the production of MC simulations is tremendously computationally expensive, requiring many hours of cluster computing. On the other hand, they are becoming more and more necessary as the sophistication of new generations of instruments increases. New instruments are more sensitive to systematic errors due to a not entirely accurate characterization of the instrument by the simulations. Therefore, tools based on semi-analytical models are particularly helpful. Thanks to them, it is possible to carry out preliminary exploratory studies that would otherwise take much computational time if performed by simulations. Finally, they can be corroborated more precisely with detailed simulations. In this context, we also present a tool for modeling the development of air showers and the emission of Cherenkov and fluorescence light, ShowerModel.

The chapter is structured as follows: first, the MC simulation program of EASs, CORSIKA, is described in Sect. 2.1, highlighting the key aspects of the new implementation, such as the treatment of the deposited energy and the emission of Cherenkov light by the simulated particles. Then, Sect. 2.2 describes the implementation of the

¹A new modern simulation framework, CORSIKA 8, is currently being developed (Reininghaus and Ulrich, 2019).

fluorescence light emission within CORSIKA. Based on this implementation, Sect. 2.3 presents the results obtained on the relevance of fluorescence light in the detection techniques based on Cherenkov radiation. Section 2.4 introduces the `ShowerModel` package for modeling the development of air cascades and associated Cherenkov emission and fluorescence, a powerful complementary tool to the simulations. Finally, the possible implications of these results are discussed in Sect. 2.5.

2.1 CORSIKA

This section describes the CORSIKA simulation program written in FORTRAN from a general point of view, summarizing its workflow and main components. Then we focus on the existing implementation of Cherenkov emission, the starting point for our work of including fluorescence light emission.

2.1.1 Workflow

The general flow of CORSIKA is schematically represented in Fig. 2.1. The program starts by initializing the simulation based on an input data chart where the primary particle type and its characteristics, the hadronic and electromagnetic interaction models, and the atmosphere model to be used are defined. Considering this information, the shower simulation begins by determining the height of the first interaction suffered by the primary particle. The particle is transported to that point, and the interaction it will undergo is decided based on the effective sections of the interactions. During the transport of the particle, energy is deposited by ionization. After the interaction or decay, the possible resulting secondary particles, if they have an energy above the simulation threshold, are stored internally in a stack, waiting for their turn to continue the simulation. When the particle in action reaches the set observation level, it is written to the output file and passed to the next particle in the stack, if any. This process continues iteratively until all the particles accumulated in the stack are used. The information of each simulation run heads the output files. In addition, information on the longitudinal development of the cascade (i.e., number of particles, deposited energy as a function of the altitude) is written to output.

CORSIKA handles the transport of all particles generated from the very first interaction of the incoming particle down to the observation level. They are tracked while their energy is above a certain threshold, which the user sets for each particle

type. In addition, particles going upwards are discarded from being tracked². When a particle is propagated between two interaction points, its spatial and time coordinates are updated. The ionization energy loss, the multiple scattering, and the trajectory bending in the Earth's magnetic field are also evaluated for charged particles. Once the type of inelastic interaction or decay that the particle undergoes is determined, the outgoing particles are tracked, provided that they survive the above-mentioned energy and angular cuts.

Figure 2.1: Workflow diagram of CORSIKA. Taken from CORSIKA user's guide.

²The transportation of upward-going particles may be activated in CORSIKA, but this option is not included in the default settings, as it is irrelevant for the determination of the Cherenkov light at ground level.

CORSIKA code consists of many subroutines in charge of each task within the shower simulation. Some of them are in charge of essential parts of the simulation, for example: `SHOWER` (looks at what is on top of electromagnetic component particle stack and calls the appropriate routine to treat this particle), `BOX2` (determines the point of interaction or decay for any particle), `BOX3` (checks passage through observation level), `EGS4` (treats electromagnetic shower component), `MUTRAC` (muon tracking), `DATA` (reads input data card), `UPDATE` (tracks charged particles, except for electron and positrons, to observation level or the point of interaction or decay) and `ELECTR` (in charge of transporting electrons and positrons). Especially important for us is the `CERENK` subroutine (Sect. 2.1.2) in charge of emitting Cherenkov photons when a charged particle is transported by any of the other subroutines.

Energy deposited in CORSIKA

An important aspect of the simulation for both Cherenkov radiation and fluorescence emission is the energy deposited by the charged particles of the cascade in their development toward the ground. In both cases, the amount of light emitted will be proportional to the energy deposited. Therefore, it is especially important for implementing fluorescence emission to know the treatment of the deposited energy in CORSIKA.

There are two different cases by which particles deposit energy. First, being the main way, all charged particles transported in the simulation deposit energy by ionizing the medium in that path. Most of that energy comes from electron and positron particles which are the major component of particles in the cascade development. On the other hand, after interaction or decay, some particles end up below the simulation threshold, either because they are particles whose trajectory goes upwards (in the case of not considering the simulation of these particles) or those whose energy is lower than the cut-off energy to participate in the simulation. Additionally, the particles that reach the observation level deposit all their energy there, not contributing to the Cherenkov emission and fluorescence in the simulation.

Figure 2.2 represents the longitudinal development of deposited energy by a simulated gamma ray taking into account the different components of the shower. Most energy is deposited by the electromagnetic component's transport through the atmosphere. We see that the amount of energy deposited by the particles below the simulation threshold is not negligible. In the case of Cherenkov emission, this limit is chosen so that the particles no longer have enough energy to undergo this effect. On the other hand, the sub-simulation component can give rise to fluorescence emission. For this

Figure 2.2: Longitudinal distribution of deposited energy from all the shower components. The dashed vertical line represents the observation level at 2200 masl.

reason, the treatment of the energy deposited in the code in the case of fluorescence must be more exhaustive than in the case of Cherenkov, as we will see in the next sections.

2.1.2 Cherenkov subroutine

The Cherenkov radiation production within a predefined wavelength interval is evaluated each time a charged particle fulfilling the Cherenkov condition undergoes a transportation step (Fig. 2.3, left). The step is subdivided into smaller sub-steps of equal length and a bunch of photons, treated as a whole, is generated at the midpoint of each sub-step. The number of sub-steps of a given transportation step is chosen such that the number of photons in any bunch³ is always less than a certain *bunchsize* set by the user. For each bunch, the number of photons and their emission angle relative to the particle direction are determined by the refractive index at the corresponding height and the velocity of the particle, which is calculated taking into account the continuous

³In general, this is a fractional number.

energy loss along its trajectory. The azimuthal emission angle of the bunch around the particle direction is taken at random. Finally, the bunch is transported to ground level and its information (i.e., number of photons, spatial and time coordinates at observation level, arrival direction and emission height) is written to a file as long as it reaches the detector area defined by the user. This procedure significantly reduces the computation and storage needs while including statistical fluctuations in the spatial distribution of bunches on the ground.

Figure 2.3: Schematic view of particle transportation between interaction points (step) and generation of bunches of Cherenkov and fluorescence photons.

Optionally, CORSIKA can assign a specific wavelength to each bunch to evaluate both the refraction and the absorption of the atmosphere and the photon detection efficiency of the telescopes. However, this option needs substantial computational resources and is not activated in the default settings of CORSIKA.

By default, the Cherenkov emission in CORSIKA has the option to define a grid of rectangular Cherenkov detectors. Photons whose trajectory crosses these surfaces are stored. On the other hand, inspired by the IACT telescopes, Konrad Bernlöhr implemented the possibility of considering detectors with volume in the form of a sphere (Fig. 2.4) so that in this extension (known as IACT), only the photons intersecting this sphere and its shadow on the ground are propagated and stored in the output. This option defines a new auxiliary output format to the CORSIKA standard known as *eventio*, which is especially important for the next step, the realistic simulation of the telescope's response to the detection of these Cherenkov photons with the program `sim_telarray` (Bernlöhr, 2008).

- a: recorded photon bunch
- b: not recorded because not intersecting sphere
- c: recorded (not in 'shadow' but hitting a shadow grid cell)
- d: not recorded because not hitting a shadow grid cell

view from top:

Grid cells used for #1: A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2

Grid cells used for #2: B3, B4, C3, C4

Figure 2.4: Schematic view of a spherical detector mimicking an IACT in CORSIKA. Cherenkov photon bunches are considered to be registered by the telescope if they intersect the fiducial sphere enclosing the telescope and hit a grid cell containing the sphere *shadow* on the CORSIKA observation level. Taken from [Bernlöhr \(2008\)](#).

2.2 Implementation of fluorescence emission in CORSIKA

We implemented the fluorescence emission in the CORSIKA v7.6300 code. We followed the same scheme of photon bunches used in the simulation of the Cherenkov light production described above. Every time a charged particle deposits energy in the atmosphere, bunches of fluorescence photons are generated. The amount of fluorescence light is evaluated within a wavelength interval set by the user. In the workflow of CORSIKA, the energy deposition takes place under two different circumstances that are described next, together with the procedure to build up the bunches.

In the first place, when a particle is transported between two interaction points, it deposits an amount of energy equal to the continuous ionization energy loss. Most of the charged particles of an EAS are electrons and positrons having transportation steps shorter than 20 m, for which the atmospheric characteristics can be assumed to be constant. In this case, the number of fluorescence photons in the whole step is randomly calculated from a Poisson distribution with mean equal to the photon yield calculated as described in section 1.3.2, taking the atmospheric parameters at the step midpoint⁴. Then, photons are equally distributed in bunches, each one generated in a sub-step in the same way as for the Cherenkov light production. However, the maximum fluorescence bunchsize is defined independently to allow for a different granularity of these two processes. Each bunch is emitted in a random direction, but restricted to downward angles to save computing time. See Fig. 2.3 (right) for a schematic representation of the generation of photon bunches in the case of fluorescence emission.

For transportation steps larger than 20 m (mostly taken by muons), we first split the total path into steps of 20 m or less and then apply the above treatment for every newly defined step. The energy deposit of the original step is distributed proportionally to the thicknesses of the new ones.

The other circumstance when energy is deposited is that a particle does not survive the angular or energy cuts. Note that, as opposed to the Cherenkov light production, this has to be considered for the fluorescence production, because this process has no sizable energy threshold and is isotropic. The energy deposit is assumed to occur at the point where CORSIKA stops tracking the particle, and it depends on the type of particle. Photons, electrons and other stable particles deposit their kinetic energy. For

⁴The standard atmospheric parameterization in CORSIKA only has information on the air density and the mass overburden as a function of height. Therefore, pressure and temperature were calculated under the assumption of an ideal gas under a gravitational acceleration of 9.81 m/s^2 . Humidity effects were neglected.

positrons, the annotated energy deposit includes additionally the energy corresponding to two electron masses released as annihilation photons, which are not tracked. For muons and other unstable particles, the energy deposit is the total particle energy minus the mean energy fraction carried by neutrinos, which are supposed to deposit no energy in the atmosphere.

Each time CORSIKA applies the angular or energy cuts to a particle, bunches of fluorescence photons are emitted at random directions from the point where the energy is deposited. The distribution of photons in bunches is done taking into account the fluorescence bunchsize, as explained before.

Some remaining small contributions due to a variety of hadronic interactions producing subthreshold secondary particles are not included yet, but they were checked to be less than 1% of the total energy deposited by electromagnetic showers and less than 3% for EASs induced by TeV protons.

In the same way, as for the Cherenkov radiation, only bunches reaching the predefined detector area are stored. Fluorescence emission in CORSIKA is also compatible with the IACT option of CORSIKA, which provides an advanced output for Cherenkov telescopes (Bernlöhr, 2008). The information of both Cherenkov and fluorescence bunches is written in the same output file, either when using the standard CORSIKA output, or the IACT *eventio* output to further simulate the detection of the light by IACTs⁵ (see Fig. 2.9). We used the sign bit of the variable that stores the number of photons to differentiate between the two types of bunches. A summary of the output format for distinguishing both light components depending on the selected simulation options is shown in Fig. 2.5.

2.3 Fluorescence contamination in the Cherenkov technique

The implementation presented in the previous section has been applied to simulate the fluorescence light at conditions relevant to Cherenkov telescopes, to study the importance of the fluorescence contamination. Next, we describe the used CORSIKA setup and input parameters and the tools we developed to analyze the simulation data.

In this work, we used the high- and low-energy hadronic interaction models of QGSJET-01C and GHEISHA 2002d, respectively. The CERENKOV option, needed for the simulation of Cherenkov radiation, was used in combination with the EGS4 package

⁵We note that the wavelength-dependent atmospheric absorption and detector efficiency can be evaluated for fluorescence bunches in `sim_telarray`.

Figure 2.5: Output format according to the selected compiling options.

that allows the full Monte Carlo treatment of the electromagnetic component. The energy thresholds were set to 0.3 GeV for hadrons, 0.1 GeV for muons and 0.02 GeV for the electromagnetic component.

The detector was defined as a 5×5 km² square. As a representative case, we set the observation altitude at 2200 m a.s.l., which is the one of the Roque de Los Muchachos Observatory, on the island of La Palma. The geomagnetic field corresponding to this location was introduced. The US Standard atmospheric profile was selected. According to CORSIKA coordinate system, the x axis points to the magnetic North and the y axis towards the West direction.

The maximum bunchsize for Cherenkov and fluorescence light emission was set to 10 and 5, respectively. In this way, we compensated the more efficient production of Cherenkov photons with respect to that of fluorescence and the isotropic emission of the latter. The wavelength range of the simulated photons was 300 – 450 nm for both light components.

The MC production carried out for this work consists of γ -ray showers within a large energy range (100 GeV to 1 PeV) with zenith angles θ between 0° and 60° . To get good statistics of the photon density distributions on the ground, the number of events was scaled with the shower energy (e.g., 1000 showers of 10 TeV and 100 showers of 100 TeV for each θ value). Simulated showers were forced to impact at the center of the detector area so that arrival coordinates of bunches are given relative to the shower

core at the observation level. Inclined showers were assumed to always go from North to South, as depicted in Fig. 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Geometry and coordinate system adopted in the simulations. Inclined showers are assumed to go from North to South. Light density on ground is binned along the x axis. The FoVs of a wide-angle Cherenkov detector (WACD) and an imaging air-Cherenkov telescope (IACT) are also illustrated.

Figure 2.7: Averaged spatial distributions of Cherenkov (left) and fluorescence (right) light on ground from 10 TeV γ -ray vertical showers.

Dedicated Python-based scripts were developed to read the output files containing the bunch information and calculate the spatial distributions of Cherenkov and fluorescence photons on the ground. For this purpose, the detector area of $5 \times 5 \text{ km}^2$ was discretized into a dense grid and the number of photons in each grid element was counted, i.e., summing over all the bunches impinging on it. Cuts on the arrival angle

Figure 2.8: Radial distributions of Cherenkov (red) and fluorescence (blue) light obtained after averaging the 2D distributions of Fig. 2.7 over azimuth angle.

of the bunches were implemented so that the pointing direction and FoV of a Cherenkov telescope can be simulated (see Fig. 2.6). No cut in the arrival time of bunches was applied for this work, although it can be easily implemented for further studies of the time profile of the recorded signals.

In subsection 2.3.1, the spatial distribution of both Cherenkov and fluorescence light components on the ground are compared with the assistance of some illustrative examples. Afterward, we present the results of a systematic study on the fluorescence contamination in Cherenkov telescopes as a function of the primary γ -ray energy (subsection 2.3.2) and zenith angle (subsection 2.3.3). For the IACT technique, the impact of the observation offset angle is analyzed in subsection 2.3.4.

2.3.1 General features of the light distribution on ground

First, we show by simulations of an EAS (CORSIKA) and its detection by an IACT (`sim_telarray`) that the shower images seen from each light component (Cherenkov and fluorescence) have a similar shape (see Fig. 2.9). In this way, we can perform the whole analysis from the integrated signal, as presented below.

As an illustrative case, the spatial distribution of both Cherenkov and fluorescence photon densities averaged over 1000 vertical 10 TeV γ -ray showers is shown in Fig. 2.7.

Figure 2.9: Air shower as seen by an IACT separating the Cherenkov and fluorescence components, showing that both form similar images in the camera of the telescope. The image corresponds to a simulated LST looking at a shower with an impact parameter < 100 m. Fluorescence yield is amplified by a factor $\times 1000$ to appreciate better the imprint left by the fluorescence light in the camera.

For this example, no angular cuts have been applied. Both distributions have azimuthal symmetry around the shower core position, as the effect from the geomagnetic field is very small. Thus, we averaged the Cherenkov and fluorescence photon densities over azimuth angle to obtain the corresponding radial profiles (Fig. 2.8). Cherenkov light concentrates on the pool region, which extends up to a radial distance of ~ 120 m in this case⁶, while the photon density sharply drops outside this region. On the other hand, the fluorescence photon density decreases much less steeply with increasing core distance due to the isotropic nature of the fluorescence emission. In fact, the fluorescence photon density becomes even greater than the Cherenkov one at a very large core distance.

In the general case of inclined showers, the photon density distributions on the ground do not have azimuthal symmetry. For simplicity, we calculated the photon density profiles only along the x axis. Therefore, we restricted the detection area to a strip of 10 m width along this axis and defined bins of 10×10 m² within this strip (see Fig. 2.6).

Since we are interested in showers with large core impact distances (~ 1 km), only the highest energy range makes sense. Examples of these photon density profiles for 100 TeV showers with $\theta = 20^\circ$ averaged over 100 MC events are shown in the upper panels of figures 2.10 and 2.11. Two distinct observational techniques are contemplated.

⁶The extension of the Cherenkov light pool on the ground depends on the shower inclination, but it is almost independent of the primary γ -ray energy.

Figure 2.10: Upper panel: Averaged lateral profiles of Cherenkov and fluorescence photons with no angular cut (dashed lines) and with zenith angles lower than 60° (solid lines) from 100 TeV γ -ray showers with an inclination angle of 20° . Lower panel: Fluorescence contamination versus distance to the impact point.

Figure 2.10 illustrates the case of WACDs pointing to the zenith, like those of Karle et al. (1995); Tluczykont et al. (2014); Gress et al. (2013); Aharonian et al. (2021). Here, the dashed lines represent the light profiles without any angular cut, while the solid lines correspond to the profiles obtained by imposing the realistic condition that photons arrive with a zenith angle lower than 60° (i.e., within a FoV of 0.85 sr around the vertical direction). As a consequence of the directional emission of Cherenkov photons, almost all of them fulfill this condition as long as the detector is not too far away from the shower impact point. The fraction of fluorescence photons collected by the detector is around 70% for positive x values. On the other hand, this fraction is significantly lower along the negative x axis, because the lower portion of the shower is outside the FoV when observing from that side, as illustrated in Fig. 2.6. For a typical detector area of the order of 0.1 m^2 , the trigger level is around 10^3 photons per square

meter (Gress et al., 2013). This translates into a maximum acceptable x value of a few hundred meters for this shower energy, although core distances up to 1000 m can be of interest in the PeV energy range.

The scenario shown in Fig. 2.11 is that of IACTs with a FoV of 10° (solid lines) or 20° (dashed lines) assuming on-axis observation (see subsection 2.3.4 for a discussion about off-axis effects). Narrower FoVs, e.g., 5° , are only used in the low-energy range (< 1 TeV) and with small impact parameters for which the fluorescence contamination is negligible. The photon density was calculated for a horizontal surface element regardless of the inclination of the telescope. Core distances greater than 1000 m were not considered in the IACT case either, because the light intensity collected by a telescope positioned at such a distance would be extremely low and it would only image the uppermost portion of the shower. Notice that, although the lateral distributions exhibit a strong mirror symmetry, the light density decreases slightly more steeply along the negative x axis, since light travels a longer distance to reach the ground.

The narrow FoV of an IACT severely limits the fraction of both Cherenkov and fluorescence photons detected at a given core distance. The narrower the FoV, the smaller the portion of the shower development within it. On the other hand, since the missed portion of the shower is the lowest one (see Fig. 2.6), only photons with large emission angles relative to the shower axis are lost. Therefore, the reduction in the fraction of detected photons is more important for the fluorescence component due to its isotropic nature.

In this work, we define the fluorescence contamination R_{FC} as the ratio of the fluorescence over Cherenkov light densities. This quantity is represented as a function of x for the corresponding studied cases in the lower panels of figures 2.10 and 2.11. The parameter R_{FC} is very small ($< 1\%$) inside the Cherenkov light pool, while it grows roughly exponentially outside this region. At a core distance of around 1000 m, it will be very significant, i.e., $\sim 5\%$ for an IACT and even larger than 10% for a WACD. A detailed quantification of R_{FC} as a function of the observation conditions is given in the next subsections.

As mentioned above, no cut in the arrival photon times has been applied in this work. Nevertheless, we made some tests to check that the effect of using a finite time window has a negligible effect on the calculated R_{FC} values, since both light components have similar time distributions. For example, for 100 TeV showers with $\theta = 20^\circ$ and a telescope FoV of 10° , imposing a time window of 100 ns reduces R_{FC} from 6% to 5% at $x = 1000$ m.

Figure 2.11: The same as Fig. 2.10, but for IACTs with two hypothesis of FoV: 10° and 20°, and on-axis observation.

2.3.2 Energy dependence

The total number of charged particles in an EAS and the energy deposited by them scale approximately with the energy of the primary particle. Therefore, the total amount of Cherenkov and fluorescence light scales with energy too. However, the spatial distributions of both light components on the ground also depend on the longitudinal development of the shower. The higher the shower energy, the deeper into the atmosphere it develops and the more steeply these light distributions decrease with core distance. This effect is stronger in the fluorescence component than in the Cherenkov one, since the latter is concentrated within the pool. As a consequence, the fluorescence contamination should, in principle, increase with increasing energy. On the other hand, a finite FoV has the opposite effect because it reduces fluorescence contamination, as explained before. This reduction is more important as the energy increases, because the deeper into the atmosphere the shower develops, the larger the fraction of the shower development outside the telescope FoV.

The dependence of the fluorescence contamination on the primary γ -ray energy

for wide-angle detectors (60° FoV in the vertical direction) is shown in Fig. 2.12 for showers with $\theta = 20^\circ$ and at the characteristic core distances of 500, 750 and 1000 m. R_{FC} is found to grow approximately as $E^{0.22}$ for positive x values (solid lines), reaching up to $R_{\text{FC}} \approx 1$ at 1000 m for 1 PeV showers. The contamination is less significant and weaker dependent on energy for negative x values (dashed lines), because the impact of the FoV is more important in this region, as shown in Fig. 2.10, and compensates the above-mentioned effect of the deeper shower development. This asymmetry is similar to that found with particle detector arrays (e.g., the surface detector of the Pierre Auger Observatory) for inclined showers. As seen in Fig. 2.10, in the absence of fluorescence light, there would be almost no such asymmetry.

Figure 2.12: Fluorescence contamination R_{FC} , as a function of the shower energy and x distance for WACDs with FoV of 60° in the vertical direction. Results were obtained for γ -ray showers with a zenith angle of 20° . The statistical error bars are smaller than the symbol size.

Figure 2.13 shows the results for IACTs with a FoV of 10° , observing 20° inclined showers on axis. For this FoV, R_{FC} becomes non-negligible ($> 1\%$) at a distance larger than 500 m and is found to be nearly independent of energy at all core distances (the asymmetry between positive and negative x values is very small). Although we report results for a wide range of shower energies, it should be stressed that, outside the Cherenkov light pool, the photon density for showers with energy lower than 1 TeV is

comparable to typical night sky background values, thus the fluorescence contamination is only relevant for higher-energy showers when observed from a large core distance.

Figure 2.13: The same as Fig. 2.12, but for IACTs with a FoV of 10° centered at the arrival shower direction.

2.3.3 Dependence on shower zenith angle

The angular dependence of the fluorescence contamination for 100 TeV γ -ray showers is shown in figures 2.14 and 2.15 for the two techniques studied in this work. The behavior shown in these figures can be understood in terms of two effects of shower inclination on the spatial light distributions. In the first place, the size of the Cherenkov light pool on the ground is nearly proportional to $\sec^2 \theta$ along the x axis and to $\sec \theta$ along the y axis, that is, in the coordinate system $x' \equiv x \cos^2 \theta$, $y' \equiv y \cos \theta$, it is delimited by a circle of radius $r' \approx 120$ m at 2200 m a.s.l.⁷ Therefore, R_{FC} will be modulated by the modified coordinates (x', y') rather than by (x, y) . In the second place, an inclined shower develops higher in the atmosphere because, for a given atmospheric thickness transversed, the corresponding vertical depth is smaller by a factor $\cos \theta$. Because of both effects, R_{FC} generally decreases with θ for a given x value.

⁷This can be justified assuming that the Cherenkov light beam can be approximated by an inclined cone with the vertex at a fixed height regardless of the angle of inclination.

Figure 2.14: Fluorescence contamination as a function of zenith angle and x distance for WACDS with FoV of 60° in the vertical direction. Results were obtained for 100 TeV γ -ray showers.

Figure 2.15: The same as Fig. 2.14, but for IACTs with a FoV of 10° centered at the arrival shower direction.

For WACDs and positive x values, this decrease in R_{FC} is partly compensated by the fact that the detector observes the shower development at lower altitudes and with larger angle as θ increases.⁸ The opposite happens for negative x values, resulting in a steeper decrease of the fluorescence contamination with θ .

In the IACT case, the asymmetry between positive and negative x values is very small and the narrow FoV compensates the effects due to variations in the shower development, as explained in the previous subsection. In fact, for a fixed modified radial distance r' , R_{FC} is found to be nearly independent of both the shower energy and θ . For example, for an IACT with a FoV of 10° pointing to a certain γ -ray source, R_{FC} will be around 3% for any incoming shower that impacts at $r' = 750$ m. However, for a very large zenith angle of 60° , this would involve a core distance of 3000 m along the x axis or 1500 m along the y axis, which is unreachable for the IACT technique. As a simple recipe, a good estimation of R_{FC} at an arbitrary position (x, y) , γ -ray energy and zenith angle θ can be obtained from the result given in Fig. 2.11 for 20° inclined showers at an equivalent core distance

$$x_{\text{eq}} \equiv r' \sec^2 20^\circ = 1.13 \sqrt{(x \cos^2 \theta)^2 + (y \cos \theta)^2}. \quad (2.1)$$

2.3.4 Fluorescence contamination in off-axis observations

Quite often IACTs do not point exactly in the direction of the γ -ray source, but observe the incoming showers with an off-axis angle ϕ of up to a few degrees. This is the case of sky surveys (e.g., Abdalla et al., 2018), observation of extended sources, etc. We show here that the fluorescence contamination may be larger for off-axis observations.

As a representative case inspired by CTA Small-Sized Telescopes (White et al., 2021), the lateral light profiles for the sample of 100 TeV showers with 20° zenith angle and FoV of 10° (Fig. 2.11) have been recalculated for several off-axis angles ϕ . The results on the fluorescence contamination are presented in Fig. 2.16. For simplicity, we assumed that both the shower axis and the main optic axis of the telescope are on the XZ plane (ϕ is the angle between them). Positive ϕ values indicate the case in which the two axes intersect at a point above ground level, i.e., a *convergent observation*. This is equivalent to augmenting the telescope FoV in an on-axis observation, because it increases the observed fraction of the shower development.⁹ Therefore, the R_{FC} value increases with ϕ . On the other hand, the negative ϕ values in Fig. represent a

⁸Note that for $\theta > 30^\circ$ and positive x values, the detector would operate in *fluorescence mode*, as it would observe the shower transversely.

⁹We note, however, that further increasing ϕ makes the telescope miss the upper part of the shower development. An extreme value of $\phi = 90^\circ$ would correspond to observing the shower transversely.

divergent observation. For large core distances of interest for this work, this situation would correspond to a telescope that only catches the uppermost portion of the shower, collecting an amount of Cherenkov light insufficient to record a useful image.

Figure 2.16: Fluorescence contamination as a function of telescope off-axis angle and x distance for IACTs with a FoV of 10° . Results were obtained for 100 TeV showers with 20° zenith angle.

In the general case that the telescope axis is outside the XZ plane, the fluorescence contamination for small ϕ angles is expected to be moderately larger with respect to the on-axis observation. It should be noted, however, that IACTs with a FoV larger than 10° (e.g., LHAASO-WFCTA [Zhang et al., 2011](#)), may have very relevant fluorescence contamination in case they can observe with $\phi > 5^\circ$.

2.4 ShowerModel

Complementary to the MC tools, we developed a python package called `ShowerModel` to quickly compute the light emission in air showers and its detection by an array of telescopes ([Morcuende and Rosado, 2021](#)). This tool can speed up calculations that do not require a full simulation or that may serve to complement complex Monte Carlo studies and data analyses. A similar approach was presented previously in [Vuillaume et al. \(2017\)](#). In the following, main functionalities and examples of results obtained

with `ShowerModel` are shown. Also, several possible remarkable applications of this software are enumerated.

The package comprises several functions and classes to model air-shower development and detection. Both gamma and proton-like 1D air showers can be generated using analytical Greisen or Gaisser-Hillas formulas (Greisen, 1956; Gaisser and Hillas, 1977). Simulation-generated longitudinal profiles can also be input. Different flat atmospheric models are available. The code uses detailed parameterizations of both fluorescence and Cherenkov light emission and angular distribution (Morcuende et al., 2019; Nerling et al., 2006). The time-varying light intensity reaching a telescope is readily computed from geometry. Rayleigh scattering losses are also included. Telescope objects are highly configurable (e.g., quantum efficiency, pointing direction, field of view, detection area) to model fluorescence telescopes, imaging air Cherenkov telescopes, wide-angle Cherenkov detectors or hybrid designs. Camera images are produced using the Nishimura-Kamata-Greisen (NKG) function (Kamata and Nishimura, 1958; Greisen, 1956) to describe the lateral distribution of electrons in the air shower.

`ShowerModel` makes possible the calculation of:

- Projection of shower tracks in local coordinates `alt/az` as well as the telescope field of view coordinates `theta/phi` (Figure 2.17, left).

Figure 2.17: *Left*: Shower track projections of an air shower observed by a fluorescence telescope. *Right*: Signal produced from the two light components.

- Longitudinal shower profiles: energy deposit and light production.
- Cherenkov and fluorescence photon densities on the ground (Figure 2.18).
- Time evolution of signal in a telescope (Figure 2.17, right).
- Shower events detected by an array of telescopes (Figure 2.19).

Figure 2.18: Cherenkov and fluorescence photon densities at ground level.

Figure 2.19: Air shower observed by an observatory of 6 telescopes. Green dots mark the telescope positions and their relative signal sizes.

- Camera images in customized telescopes (Figure 2.20).

The proposed tool can serve as a complement to the analysis pipeline of cosmic-ray observatories. For instance, it might be used to fast evaluate if changes in the observation conditions (e.g., atmospheric parameters and night sky background) make

Figure 2.20: Camera images of an air shower observed by an array of six IACTs.

necessary new simulations or instrument response functions. In addition, it may be useful to explore new observatory configurations or detection techniques that exploit both Cherenkov and fluorescence signals (see [Contreras et al., 2016b](#); [Sailer, 2020](#)).

2.5 Operation with Cherenkov telescopes in fluorescence mode

The pioneering work [Contreras et al. \(2016b\)](#) suggested a new observing mode for Cherenkov telescopes inspired by the operation of fluorescence telescopes. This idea proposes to observe the atmospheric cascades in a transverse way (Fig. 2.21) with Cherenkov telescopes while, at the same time, the telescopes are operating in their usual on-axis mode.

One of the problems is the large difference between the time windows of Cherenkov pulse detection (on the order of several ns) with respect to the time it would typically take for the cascade to cross the telescope's field of view (on the order of several μ s). This could be solved by adapting the trigger and readout system of the telescope cameras to create a flexible system for detecting both events. On the other hand, the advantage of having large arrays of telescopes in the future is that together they could map most of the longitudinal development of the cascade, just as fluorescence telescopes with a large field of view do.

In this context, there are two ways to evaluate the necessary changes in the cascade light detection system. On the one hand, detailed MC simulations, including the detector part (`sim.telarray`). For example, following our implementation of fluorescence in CORSIKA, Sailer (2020) did the first studies in this sense, exploring what changes should be made in the FlashCam-type camera with which part of the CTA telescopes will be instrumented. Sailer (2020) shows that with the proper configuration of the readout time window of these cameras, showers initiated by primaries with energies of the order of 1 - 100 PeV could be detected. On the other hand, using modeling software such as `ShowerModel`, we can explore the best geometric arrangements that favor shower detection, complementing the simulation work.

This hybrid technique aims to improve the capabilities and sensitivity of the kilometer observatories to be built in the coming years. For example, larger effective gamma-ray collection areas would be achieved, opening a window to detect gamma rays of even higher energy than the sensitivity of current instruments. In addition, such a mode of operation could be interesting for cosmic ray detection, as transversal distribution of the showers could be studied with higher angular resolution (due to the finer pixelated camera of IACTs) than with fluorescence telescopes. Further studies are needed to explore this possibility.

Figure 2.21: Schematic representation of an imaging Cherenkov telescope operating in *fluorescence mode*. The preliminary estimation of the time window in which the air shower crosses the field of view of the telescope (a few μs) is much larger than the $\simeq 10$ ns duration in normal Cherenkov on-axis mode.

2.6 Conclusions

We implemented the atmospheric fluorescence emission in the CORSIKA code similarly to the Cherenkov light production. Based on this development, we quantified the fluorescence relevance in the signals recorded by ground-based air-Cherenkov telescopes, so far ignored in the reconstruction of EASs.

In the IACT scenario, the Cherenkov signal dominates within the light pool due to the different angular distributions of these two light components. Besides, the fluorescence contribution is strongly suppressed in these telescopes with a narrow FoV of several degrees. We find that the fluorescence contamination is, as expected, negligible at a few hundred meters from the impact point. Nonetheless, it starts being significant ($> 5\%$) at a core distance of 1000 m. Thus ignoring this effect would impact VHE gamma-ray observations carried out by kilometer-scale arrays, such as the future CTA, that will register signals at large core distances. Our systematic simulation study reveals that the fluorescence contamination in IACTs is nearly independent of the shower energy and somewhat dependent on the zenith angle for a given distance to the shower core. We also found that off-axis observations lead to an increase in fluorescence contamination.

In contrast, our simulations indicate that arrays of WACDs are strongly affected by fluorescence contamination, particularly for the highest energy showers. In the PeV region, the signals of detectors located 1000 m from the shower core can contain up to 45% fluorescence.

We plan to implement the fluorescence emission in the new CORSIKA8 code currently in development. Making it officially available would facilitate its usage in the community for detailed simulations of IACTs and arrays of WACDs working in conditions where fluorescence contamination is expected to be non-negligible. In these cases, fluorescence should be considered in end-to-end simulations, including the instrument, to avoid systematics of a few percent because of not completely neglecting the fluorescence component.

Finally, the implementation in CORSIKA and the complementary modeling tool, `ShowerModel`, will allow for further investigations of the feasibility of using arrays of IACTs in fluorescence mode.

Chapter 3

Analysis of Cherenkov telescope data

One of the main tasks of this thesis has been to contribute to developing and testing software for Cherenkov observatories. The analysis of Cherenkov telescope data follows a general scheme in all instruments. This chapter illustrates the analysis procedure with the software being developed for CTA and secondarily with MAGIC. Later, in Chapter 4, I will particularize some aspects of the analysis for the LST-1 and explain my contribution in this context.

3.1 CTA analysis framework

Since CTA will be an observatory open to the entire astrophysics community, an open-source analysis framework is needed to deliver already reduced data sets all prepared to obtain high-level science data products. Standard open-source tools are being developed to process CTA data from raw-level to high-level science products by performing the reduction and reconstruction analysis steps between subsequent data levels.

3.1.1 Data levels

The CTA data model is based on a hierarchy of data levels (Contreras et al., 2016a). Each of them is derived from the previous ones and has a smaller size, implementing a so-called *data reduction* chain. They span different categories: calibration, data, and system monitoring. We will mainly focus on the data stream coming from the telescope cameras and MC simulations, using the LST-1 as an example. The levels are as follows:

- **R0:** Raw level 0 is the data saved by the front-end boards, the electronic circuits that digitize the events selected by the trigger in all CTA telescopes. They consist of samples of the PMT signals recorded at high frequency (250-1000 Gsample/s), with a 12-bit resolution, and in windows that range from 40 ns for the LSTs to 200 ns for the SSTs. At this level, data are known as waveforms (see Fig. 3.1). They are not recorded but sent to the chain.

Figure 3.1: Uncalibrated waveforms from a given event for all the pixels of an LST camera (left) and two single pixels with and without shower signal (right).

- **R1:** Raw level 1 is R0 data minimally processed online by the DAQ. Events are built by collecting the information from all the front-end boards, they are numbered, and trigger and time information is associated with them. A fast calibration achievable in the short times available is performed. In the case of

the LST prototype, this is correcting the known distortions of the digitizing chips, the DRS4.

- **DL0:** Data level 0 is defined as the first level of data written to disk and, thus, preserved indefinitely. It is the R1 data grouped in different data streams to allow fast writing to disk and eventually compressed.
- **DL1:** this data level comprises two different sub-levels. DL1 files may contain one or both levels:

DL1a: In data level 1a, waveforms are analyzed and calibrated. Amplitudes are integrated over the samples and converted from ADC counts to physical units, this is, photoelectrons (p.e.) recorded in each pixel. The times of arrival of the signals to the pixel are estimated. An image example is depicted in Fig. 3.2. The calibration scripts use the DL0 calibration data, recorded together with the observation stream, both in calibration runs and as artificially triggered calibration events interleaved with the real ones. DL1a data can be understood as calibrated images in units of p.e. and information about the signal’s arrival time to each pixel.

Figure 3.2: DL1a and DL1b information: example of a calibrated image of an event in the LST camera. The number of photoelectrons is shown in the left panel and the time of the peak of the waveform pulse in nanoseconds is depicted in the middle. On the right-hand side, the corresponding cleaned image and some of the Hillas parameters are derived.

DL1b: Data level 1b consists of geometrical parameters obtained from cleaned camera images on an event-wise basis (information from individual pixels is suppressed at this stage). These are the so-called Hillas parameters (Hillas, 1985). They are based on the first and second moments of the light intensity distribution in the camera, assuming it can be modeled by a two-dimensional ellipse. A schematic view of some of these parameters is displayed in Fig. 3.3. The right

panel of Fig. 3.2 represents an example of a cleaned image with the derived moments overlaid.

Figure 3.3: Scheme of some of the Hillas parameters obtained from a cleaned camera image.

- **DL2:** In data level 2, the events are classified according to the probability that the primary particle inducing the EAS is a gamma ray. Besides, the energy and direction of the primary particle are also reconstructed. Classification and regression are performed using machine learning techniques. Classical methods typically used are based on the features extracted in the previous stage. Some examples of the implementation of these procedures can be found in [Ohm et al. \(2009\)](#) for the Boosted Decision Tree approach and in [Albert et al. \(2008\)](#) where it is explored the application of Random Forests to the IACT reconstruction analysis. Alternatively, new deep learning approaches are also being explored (e.g., [Shilon et al., 2019](#); [Nieto et al., 2017](#)). This new strategy does not depend on the features previously extracted.
- **DL3:** CTA will deliver this data product to the end-users. It is composed of two types of information wrapped together in datasets. On one side, a list of events from DL2 data to which a certain level of background rejection is applied, keeping only gamma-like events. The other component is the Instrument Response Functions (IRFs) derived from MC data similarly processed and with the same selection criteria as the sky data. IRFs comprise the effective collection area, the PSF and the energy migration matrix. DL3 files also include pointing and livetime information. In addition, metadata incorporates monitoring parameters from the observations as timing and pointing information. The list of events is indexed as different observations and serialized as FITS files. There is an ongoing

community initiative to define a common high-level data format among the existing gamma-ray instruments. This approach would make possible the analysis of their data using open-source science tools such as Gammapy (Deil et al., 2017) or `ctools` (Knödlseeder et al., 2021), as well as facilitate joint multi-instrument studies (see, e.g., Nigro et al., 2019). The format description is specified by the Data Formats for Gamma-Ray Astronomy¹ Deil et al. (2018). Gammapy has been recently chosen as the official CTAO science tool.

- **DL4:** In data level 4, the event lists are binned in a multidimensional data structure scheme according to their energy and assuming a given geometry and coordinate system.
- **DL5:** Data level 5 are the final science products, namely flux and Test-Statistic sky maps, light curves, and spectral energy distributions obtained by modeling and fitting the previously binned data sets. These products can be compiled to build source catalogs, and sky-maps surveys to assure CTA Observatory data legacy.

Data reduction is essential to cope with the immense volume of the files generated from the observations. LST-1 records approximately 2.4 TB/hour of data at a typical readout rate of 6 kHz. As summarized in Fig. 3.4, starting at the lowest level, the file sizes are reduced by 10 after obtaining the calibrated images. The event-wise list of Hillas parameters (DL1b), the subsequent data level, is 40 times smaller than the previous data level. DL2 files have approximately the same size as that of the DL1b. The following substantial volume reduction comes with DL3 data. Depending on the event selection cuts, the size reduction at this stage is typically a factor of 100.

3.1.2 `ctapipe`

An open-source low-level analysis python-based library, `ctapipe`² (Noethe et al., 2021), is being developed by the CTA Consortium. The aim of this library is twofold. On one side, it implements tools to handle the different stages of the CTA data processing up to DL3. On the other hand, it also contains methods and utilities for handling the input/output of the data, its visualization, the definition of the data models, and the provenance tracking of analysis products.

¹<https://gamma-astro-data-formats.readthedocs.io/>

²<https://github.com/cta-observatory/ctapipe>

Figure 3.4: Data reduction flow scheme for LST-1, starting from raw waveforms up to selected gamma-ray events (DL3). The size reduction factor and processing time on a single core are indicated. Due to the present organization of the LST-1 DAQ, DL0 data are grouped in sets of 5.3×10^4 consecutive events dubbed sub-runs. These files are the smallest unit that can be processed in parallel.

Several command-line *Tools* process the low-level data to DL1 or DL2 files in HDF5 format³, including image extraction, parameterization, and event reconstruction. These tools comprise several methods and algorithms carrying out the data reduction chain. Besides, an event source procures the information on an event-by-event basis being the interface that reads raw data, with a plugin for each type of telescope. Moreover, each level of data is defined according to the data model specifications of CTA. This package also contains the telescopes' characteristics and the description of the arrays.

The process starts with calibrating the camera images, which comprises image volume reduction and extraction of the pixel waveform signals. There are several methods for finding the peak of the pulse and integrating its charge. This stage yields the integrated charge and the time position of the peak for each pixel in the camera. Several algorithms are available to clean the images from noisy pixels keeping only those likely containing shower information. The resulting cleaned images are parameterized, for example, following the Hillas moment-based approach, and statistics of the images are extracted. These parameters serve as input for reconstructing shower direction, energy, and the inducing primary particle. At the time of writing, `ctapipe` supports two approaches. On the one hand, stereoscopic reconstruction can be carried out based on moments analysis (using machine learning methods in the case of single telescope data). On the other hand, using preexisting templates from simulations to perform likelihood fits to reconstruct event properties Parsons and Hinton (2014).

³<https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

Furthermore, visualization utilities help to display camera images and telescope array layouts. This library also manages the provenance tracking for each activity involved in the data processing.

3.2 Calibration

The signal recorded by the PMTs, digitized and written to disk by the DAQ is in ADC counts. The first part of the analysis chain consists of obtaining the conversion factors to transform the counts into physical-meaningful units as photo-electrons. The associated recorded times also need to be calibrated.

This procedure is specific for each instrument since hardware components are different. Usually, an artificial light source like a laser whose properties and intensity are known and can be controlled is used to illuminate the camera uniformly. Understanding the properties of this light allows knowing the expected response of the camera PMTs to that stimulus. Calibration coefficients are then used to transform the traces of the triggered and recorded events by the DAQ in ADC counts into photo-electrons. As an example, in section 4.1, the calibration procedure is outlined for the case of the LST-1.

3.3 Event reconstruction and selection

Pulses of the calibrated waveforms are integrated to obtain the total deposited charge per pixel and their signal arrival time. Camera images in charge and time (DL1a) are subsequently cleaned to eliminate the majority of pixels not containing signal from Cherenkov light. After cleaning, geometrical information of the distribution of the charge/time (DL1b) is extracted. Hence higher-level abstraction quantities from the shower-inducing particle can be inferred when compared to MC-simulated events. The extracted parameters fed machine learning algorithms to build regression and classification models for the primary particle properties (DL2).

The list of events contains both gamma photon candidates (likely coming from the source of interest) and any other cosmic particle comprising our background noise. We select the likely gamma-like events based on the particle-classification parameter and particle arrival direction (DL3). Additionally, the response functions of the instruments are calculated to be able to perform higher-level analyses.

3.4 High level analysis

This section summarizes the analysis steps starting at the DL3 level, calculating the significance of the signal, sky maps, light curve, and SED. This description focuses on the so-called 1D analysis for point-like sources based on the aperture photometry approach.

3.4.1 Detection significance and sky maps

Estimating the significance of gamma-ray excess coming from the direction of the source is done statistically through a likelihood ratio test approach comparing the null hypothesis of having no gamma-ray emitting source with the hypothesis of having a source producing a gamma-ray excess. To this end, we use the statistical tool developed by [Li and Ma \(1983\)](#). Their formula 17 computes the detection significance from the events counted respectively in the on-source and off-source control regions⁴.

Two main pointing strategies followed regarding the estimation of the signal and background subtraction, ON/OFF and wobble tracking modes. In the former, the telescope tracks the source location, so gamma rays emitted by the source end up being recorded mainly in the center of the FoV⁵. To know how many gamma-ray photons actually come from the source, we have to estimate the number of background events from a nearby control region where no gamma-ray emission from a source is expected. The drawback of this method is that a comparable amount of time has to be spent observing regions of the sky without gamma-ray emission. To optimize the observation time, the so-called wobble observation mode ([Fomin et al., 1994](#)) allows for using off-source regions within the same FoV of the observations on-source. In this case, telescopes point slightly off-axis, with an offset angle of typically $\simeq 0.4^\circ$ from the target location. Telescopes usually track several pointing locations alternating around the nominal source coordinates to reduce the systematic effect potentially affecting a given wobble position. This scheme is depicted in [Fig. 3.5](#).

For the computation of the event counts coming from the ON and OFF regions, we first histogram the squared distances between the reconstructed position of each event and a specific location in the sky (θ^2). These positions can be the source location (where the ON region is centered) or the midpoints of the off regions. Then we integrate the events within the signal region defined with a cut in θ^2 , obtaining the signal

⁴Valid when there are more than ~ 10 events in each region.

⁵The angular resolution of the instrument makes that a point-like source like the Crab Nebula is seen as a blurred image with an angular extension similar to the PSF.

Figure 3.5: Scheme of the wobble observation mode and definition of on-source and OFF regions. Credit: Abelardo Moralejo/MAGIC Collaboration.

and background counts. Apart from the events inside the ON and OFF regions, we have to consider the exposure ratio among them, for example, in the case of different observation times or usage of several OFF areas. Finally, with these components, the significance of the signal detection is calculated with Li&Ma prescription.

Sky maps are another of the scientific products obtained from high-level analysis related to the distribution of the reconstructed directions of gamma-ray-like events. They are a 2D representation of the reconstructed direction of gamma rays in camera coordinates or, more commonly, in a celestial reference system (equatorial or altazimuth coordinates). The error associated with the reconstructed direction of each event relative to the expected source location is characterized by the PSF. Sky maps are of particular interest in the case of extended sources, where their morphology can be seen beyond the size of the gamma-ray PSF of the telescope.

3.4.2 Spectrum and light curve

We aim to obtain the gamma-ray flux in physical units and calculate the spectrum of a source and its light curve. These two quantities are based on characterizing the gamma-ray flux as a function of its energy or time evolution. The gamma-ray flux is defined as the rate of gamma rays per unit area:

$$\Phi = \frac{d^2N}{dAdt} [\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}], \quad (3.1)$$

where the three ingredients are: counting gamma-ray event candidates, the effective collection area of the instrument, and the effective observation time.

The number of gamma rays from the source is calculated as those gamma-ray-like events recorded within a certain angular distance from the target location. A method

similar to the aperture photometry used at other wavelengths is used for this purpose. This technique compares the events recorded in the assumed source region (signal) to those recorded in a nearby area where there are no gamma-ray sources (background). This computation uses the θ^2 histograms, as discussed above, after splitting the data into reconstructed energy bins. The event selection of the gamma-ray excess in each energy bin is then performed by applying a θ^2 cut which defines the signal region and keeps a given percentage of gamma rays. These efficiency cuts are calculated based on an MC gamma-ray sample.

The effective time to estimate the gamma rate is calculated from the elapsed time of the observations assuming a Poisson process with a λ event arrival rate and dead time of the readout system, as:

$$t_{\text{eff}} = \frac{t_{\text{elapsed}}}{1 + \lambda d}. \quad (3.2)$$

The effective gamma-ray collection area is computed through an MC-simulated sample of gamma rays which is analyzed in the same way as the observations. A vast number of event simulations are performed in an area, A_{MC} , varying the impact point randomly within that region⁶. As the events are simulated homogeneously, we can therefore calculate the effective area by comparing the number of gamma-ray-like events surviving the analysis cuts to the total number of simulated events as:

$$A_{\text{eff}}(E) = \frac{N_{\text{surviving } \gamma}}{N_{\text{simulated } \gamma}} \times A_{MC}(E). \quad (3.3)$$

Effective area noticeably depends on the energy and the zenith angle; therefore, it is calculated in bins of such variables. The selection cuts applied for background rejection also influence the computation of the collection area.

We can now transform the observed gamma-ray excesses from a source into its differential energy spectrum, i.e., an estimate of its flux as a function of the true energy:

$$\frac{d\Phi}{dE} = \frac{d^3N}{dAdtdE} [\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{TeV}^{-1}]. \quad (3.4)$$

Alternatively, we can compute the SED, $E^2 d\Phi/dE$, corresponding to the quantity νF_ν typically used in other wavelengths.

An important remark here is that so far, we can estimate the spectra as a function of the estimated energy of the gamma rays. However, the final aim is to obtain

⁶Large enough so that we can assume that hypothetical external gamma-rays would not be able to trigger the telescopes.

this estimation based on their true energy. Taking this into account is not straightforward because the energy reconstruction of gamma-ray events has some spread around their true energy (typically current IACT instruments have $\simeq 15\%$ energy resolution, see, e.g., [Aleksić et al., 2016](#)), whose impact must be considered when building the spectrum. Due to this dispersion, some events could spill over from one energy bin to another, thus distorting the true spectral shape. This effect can be characterized by a migration matrix that associates gamma rays' estimated and true energy. This mapping table is created from an MC gamma-ray sample for which both quantities are known.

In order to obtain the true energy spectrum of the source, the spectra must be unfolded considering the instrument's finite energy resolution, a complex procedure numerically challenging (see, e.g., detailed description in the case of MAGIC [Albert et al., 2007a](#)). Another approach is the so-called *forward folding* procedure (see thorough description in [Piron, F. et al., 2001](#); [de Naurois, 2000](#)). This procedure assumes a spectral function whose parameters are obtained by a maximum likelihood fit to the observed gamma rays as a function of their energy. The hypothetical spectral shape of the source is folded with the effective area and energy dispersion matrix previously obtained.

Finally, the light curve represents the gamma-ray flux's temporal evolution. Observations are segmented into time bins. Then, assuming a given spectral shape fixed in all the bins, leaving only the flux normalization free, the spectrum obtained in every bin is integrated over a given energy range to obtain the flux values as a function of time.

3.4.3 Gammapy

In the context of CTA, the high-level analysis presented in Sect. 3.4 is performed using science tools such as Gammapy, taking as input the DL3 data files with the list of selected gamma rays together with the IRFs. This section particularizes the 1D spectral and temporal analysis of the gamma-ray emission from a point-like source done with Gammapy. The overview of the analysis flow is shown in Fig. 3.6.

The process starts by creating the `DataStore` object containing the list of observation blocks to be analyzed. These objects comprise the list of selected gamma rays characterized by their arrival time, energy, and reconstructed coordinates. From this list, Gammapy can make θ^2 plots and calculate the significance of the gamma-ray excess using its statistical utility functions.

Figure 3.6: Analysis workflow in Gammapy and the data levels as defined in the CTA framework. Credit: <https://docs.gammapy.org/dev/user-guide/package.html>.

The first data reduction step consists in binning the list of events in energy (DL3 to DL4). For this, we define the ON region centered on the source position from which we assume the gamma-ray signal to be used to extract the source spectrum. The aperture of this region enclosing the source can be the same for all energies or energy-dependent. This depends on how the angular cut θ has been applied to select the list of gamma rays both observed (DL3) and simulated (for calculating IRFs). Similarly, the specified reflected OFF regions for background estimation are defined on the opposite side of the ON signal region. At this point, a so-called `SpectrumDatasetOnOff` object is created, containing the predicted gamma-ray counts from the ON region and the background counts from the off-source control region (energy-binned) stacked for all the observations.

Then, we define the spectral shape to be assumed in the forward folding method to extract the source spectrum. For this purpose, we performed a maximum likelihood fit to the observed counts assuming the previously defined spectral model. Gammapy can also calculate the spectral flux points using the `FluxPointsEstimator` utility by fitting

the flux normalization of the global model in each energy bin. Finally, the light curve can also be computed from the reduced dataset through the `LightCurveEstimator`.

The extraction of the SED and light curve (among other science products) is considered the DL4 to DL5 step. The analysis steps described in this section are performed to obtain the spectrum and light curve from the LST-1 observations presented in Sect. 5.7.

3.5 MAGIC data analysis chain

In this section, the analysis described in previous sections in a general way within the context of CTA is particularized for the case of MAGIC telescopes. The reconstruction and analysis are carried out using proprietary C++-based software so-called MAGIC analysis and reconstruction software (MARS), developed by the members of the collaboration (Moralejo et al., 2009; Zanin et al., 2013). This software package was used to analyze the MAGIC data collected for the projects described in Chapter 6 and Appendix A. The general scheme of the steps that comprise the analysis is summarized in Fig. 3.7, and a brief description of each stage follows.

3.5.1 Low-level analysis and reconstruction

The first part of the analysis is performed by the onsite analysis (OSA) pipeline (Fidalgo et al., 2016), which runs on the machines hosted in the MAGIC control building next to the telescopes. Starting from the raw data taken by both telescopes, the first step is to merge the information from each of the subsystems involved in the data acquisition to the raw files written to disk, a task performed by the `merpp` program. This auxiliary information centralized by the central control software is essential to perform the subsequent analysis steps. Then, another program dubbed `sorcere`r extracts the digitized waveform signal in each camera pixel, calibrating it in time and charge. The details of the signal extraction are outlined in Sect. 3.2 and 4.1.1. This analysis level corresponds to the DL1a from CTA.

The images are then cleaned by discarding the pixels containing NSB fluctuations, electronic noise, and light from stars in the FoV using the so-called *Sum Cleaning* algorithm. Signals are clipped in amplitude, and the camera sum of signals is computed for combinations of compact neighboring pixels. We consider that pixels belong to the shower if this sum is beyond a specific threshold within a short time interval. Next, a two-level threshold cleaning (Lessard et al., 2001) with *core* and *boundary*

Figure 3.7: Overview of the MAGIC standard stereo analysis pipeline. The upper dashed line box indicates the low-level analysis stages usually performed by the on-site analysis chain. The bottom dashed line box gathers the analysis steps that analyzers have to do offline. Green rectangles depict the input data, blue rectangles are the programs, and final science products are highlighted in yellow. Credit: Julian Sitarek/MAGIC Collaboration.

charge thresholds, in the standard procedure⁷ set to 6 and 3.5 p.e., respectively) is applied to the pixels that survived the sum cleaning. The selected pixels, containing mostly Cherenkov light from the EASs, are then parameterized based on the method introduced by Hillas (1985), performing a principal component analysis up to the third order of the charge and time distributions in the cleaned camera images (see Fig. 3.3). An example of the cleaning procedure and Hillas parameterization of the cleaned image is depicted in Fig. 3.2. The image cleaning and parameterization are performed for each telescope calibrated data by the MARS program named `star`, and data at this point is equivalent to the DL1b from CTA.

The sets of images from both telescopes are then merged in a unique stream, matching the events seen by both telescopes. Then, through stereoscopic reconstruction, the geometry of the cascade is calculated, obtaining the direction of incidence, the point

⁷These cleaning thresholds are optimal for data taken under low NSB conditions. In general, these thresholds must be increased accordingly to the NSB level of the observations looking at the interleaved pedestal events containing only NSB fluctuations.

of impact on the ground, and the height of the shower maximum. This analysis step is performed by the `superstar` program.

It is generally at this point when analyzers start their work. First, data selection is carried out with the MARS tool called `quate`. The selection can be made, among others, based on the NSB level, the atmospheric transmission measured by the LIDAR, the occurrence of problems derived from the data acquisition, and the zenith angle at which the data have been taken. The objective is twofold: on one side, filtering out poor-quality data that may increase the systematic uncertainty of the results, and on the other side, splitting the data sets into subsamples that require different IRFs because of various conditions such as the zenith angle or the NSB level. This program outputs the selected time slices of the observations for further analysis.

The next step is to estimate the properties of the particles that induce them from the event-wise parameters of the shower images. These properties are their energy, and incident direction, besides the discrimination between gamma rays and other hadronic particles. The gamma/hadron separation is performed using a multivariate classification analysis based on the random forest (RF) method (Albert et al., 2008). To train the classifier RF model, MC simulated gamma-ray data (Carmona et al., 2008) and samples of observations containing mostly hadronic events (from dark patches observations or data with no signal detection) are used. The classification is quantified by a parameter called `hadroness`, which indicates the probability for each event of having a hadronic origin. For the estimation of the energy, a look-up table method is used. These tables, which contain the expected energy values as a function of the image parameters, are built based on simulated events. Alternatively, it can be estimated using regressors based on RF models (as currently done for the LST-1). Finally, the estimation of the direction of incidence of the primary particle is performed by the `disp` method (distance between the image centroid and the source position, see Fig. 3.3) described in Domingo-Santamaría et al. (2005), which improves the geometrical reconstruction previously performed by the `superstar` program. The `disp` parameter reconstruction is based on RF regression techniques trained on MC-simulated gamma-ray data. The outcome of the direction reconstruction is the relevant parameter θ , which represents the angular distance between the reconstructed incoming direction of the primary and the assumed source location. The gamma/hadron classifier, energy look-up table matrices, and `disp` RF regressor model are applied by a program dubbed `melibea` to the observations to obtain the reconstructed attributes of the primaries. The analysis products at this point would be equivalent to the DL2 from CTA.

Figure 3.8: Example of a θ^2 distribution from ON (red crosses) and background events (grey-shaded histogram) from off-source regions. Li&Ma significance from the estimated ON and OFF event counts is also shown. The dotted line at $\theta^2 = 0.02 \text{ deg}^2$ indicates the signal region from where ON and OFF events are extracted.

3.5.2 High-level analysis

The following steps are part of the high-level analysis that produces scientific results.

Source detection: First, we estimate whether a significant excess of gamma rays comes from the direction of the source using the statistical tool developed by [Li and Ma \(1983\)](#) and described in Sect. 3.4.1. MARS implements this calculation in a tool named `odie`, which first produces the θ^2 histograms for the ON and OFF regions (typically assuming wobble observations). Signal events and background counts are estimated by integrating the events within the region defined with a cut in θ^2 (see example in Fig. 3.8).

Sky maps: MARS includes a program called `caspar` for producing sky maps (see Sect. 3.4.1), illustrating the reconstructed direction of the incoming gamma rays in two dimensions. An example is shown in Fig. 3.9, which depicts a sky map representing the significance of the gamma-ray excess described by [Li and Ma \(1983\)](#) as the test statistic (TS). The smearing is done using a Gaussian kernel whose size matches the telescope’s gamma-ray PSF.

Spectra: To obtain the gamma-ray flux in physical units and calculate the spectrum of a source and its light curve (see a general description of the procedure in Sect.

Figure 3.9: Example of TS sky map from MAGIC gamma-ray observations smeared with the telescope PSF, whose size is represented in the bottom left corner.

3.4.2), we use the MARS program called `flute`. This program calculates the effective gamma-ray collection area, the effective observation time⁸, and the excess gamma-ray events needed to compute the SED. Figure 3.10 shows an example of the effective area (left panel) and migration matrix (right panel) calculation by `flute`.

The calculated SED by `flute` (see Fig. 3.11, left) is not unfolded considering the migration matrix. In contrast, the spillover of events due to the spread of the energy reconstruction is treated preliminarily by estimating its effect when calculating the ef-

⁸In the case of MAGIC telescopes, the dead time is about 26 μs for the current readout based on DRS4 chips.

Figure 3.10: Example of effective area calculation (on the left) and migration matrix between true and estimated gamma-ray energies (on the right) from `flute`.

Figure 3.11: Example of SED and light curve from MAGIC observations obtained with `flute`.

fective area in terms of the estimated energy, assuming a tentative source spectrum. However, a proper and complicated unfolding method needs to be done by another program implemented in MARS, `CombUnfold`, to obtain the true energy spectrum of the source. This deconvolution transforms the estimated energy distribution into true energy, considering the instrument’s finite energy resolution. Alternatively, the `fold` program performs the *forward folding* of the spectrum, convoluted with the effective area and migration matrix, based on a maximum likelihood fit of the observations to a hypothetical spectral parameterization. This technique is used in Sect. 6.6 for the redshift estimation of the blazar 1ES 0647+250.

Light curves: In addition, `flute` also provides the light curve by splitting the observations into time bins. First, the spectrum is calculated in each bin, assuming the spectral shape is fixed but leaving free the flux normalization. Then spectra are integrated above a specific energy to obtain the time evolution of the flux value. Figure 3.11 (right) shows an example of a light curve obtained with `flute` from MAGIC observations.

As a last note, there is an ongoing effort in the MAGIC Collaboration to produce DL3 files to be analyzed with standard open-source science tools within the CTA era, such as Gammapy (see, e.g., Nigro et al., 2019). From this initiative, MAGIC would benefit from easier software maintainability, reproducibility, and sharing of scientific results.

Chapter 4

Analysis of LST-1 data

This chapter describes the analysis library for the LST-1 data, `cta-lstchain`, and my contributions to this software package. Moreover, I present the on-site analysis pipeline used to orchestrate and automate the processing of the LST-1 data, `lstosa`, of which I am the lead developer. Finally, a substantial part of my time was devoted to supervising the data reduction for the LST Collaboration using these tools.

4.1 Analysis library for the LST-1 data

Inheriting from `ctapipe` (Sect. 3.1.2), the LST Collaboration is developing an open-source prototype analysis library for the low-level analysis of the LST-1 data, `cta-lstchain`¹. It aims to reconstruct the data taken with the prototype telescope delivering products to be ingested by higher-analysis science tools like `Gammapy` (see Sect. 3.4.3). Several command-line scripts and tools carry out the data flow. Aside from the analysis stages, there are ancillary utilities, for instance, merging files and generating daily run summaries. At least 27 people have contributed to some extent to the development of `cta-lstchain`. The first publications describing this analysis package available by the time of the writing of this thesis are [López-Coto et al. \(2021\)](#); [López-Coto et al. \(2022\)](#).

4.1.1 Calibration

The first set of tools, comprising calibration chain ([Kobayashi et al., 2021](#)), aims to correct the DRS4 systematic features, convert from ADC counts to photoelectrons, and do corrections to make the charge and peak-pulse time uniform across all the camera pixels.

We first align the baseline of each DRS4 capacitor, setting them to an average offset of 400 ADC counts. The baseline values depend on the time elapsed since the last capacitor readout. The calibration code also subtracts predictable systematic spikes in some capacitors. After these calibration steps, HG and LG channels reduce their pedestal noise to a few ADC counts. These corrections are done using dedicated DRS4 calibration runs taken nightly, containing only pedestal events triggered without signal.

Afterward, we calibrate the arrival time of the pulses recorded by the DRS4 chips as the sampling frequency is not perfectly homogeneous among each capacitor. For this purpose, we make use of laser-calibration events. The method, described in [Sitarek et al. \(2013\)](#), corrects from the varying peak time as a function of the capacitor readout. The time resolution for each pixel found after these corrections are below 1 ns at 5 p.e. ([Kobayashi et al., 2021](#)).

Finally, we obtain the ADC-to-photoelectron conversion factors, later applied to the uncalibrated waveforms in ADC units. The procedure relies on the so-called excess-noise factor method, which relates the variance of the charge distribution from flat-field events to its average value. Flat-field events are taken by illuminating the camera

¹<https://github.com/cta-observatory/cta-lstchain>

uniformly with laser pulses from a calibration box. Interleaved pedestal events are also recorded and used to subtract the charge baseline. The gain factor transforming from ADC to p.e. is calculated pixel-wise. The pipeline also identifies faulty pixels. The sky-data runs also contain interleaved calibration events recorded at 100 Hz, which can be used to fine-tune the calibration coefficients. After the calibration, the charge resolution in both HG and LG channels is within 5% for calibration pulses (Nozaki et al., 2020a).

We currently perform these calibration steps offline. Nonetheless, in the future, they are planned to be conducted online by the EVB, producing directly pixel-wise calibrated data in charge and time (so-called DL0 in the CTA data model), from which subsequent analysis will start.

4.1.2 Event reconstruction and selection

After creating the calibration products, we process the raw-level sky data up to DL3 following the scheme described in 3.1.1. A first script converts raw data (R0) to calibrated images (DL1a) with information on the estimated number of photons and their arrival time in each pixel. EVB writes R0 data files based on a custom data file format named `zfits` making use of `protozfits`² (low-level R0 FITS files writer/reader). The data are accessed employing the `LSTEventSource` from `ctapipe_io_lst`³, which dumps the information to data structures defined in `ctapipe`. The event source applies the DRS4 baseline corrections, plus the pixel charge and time calibration mentioned before. Moreover, the gain selection is also carried out, selecting the most relevant range.

Additionally, LST-specific procedures are performed to include the time and pointing information into the data stream. The main source of timestamps and trigger tags is the UCTS. However, during the LST-1 commissioning phase, the reliability of the UCTS is not complete. Therefore, the event-wise timestamp and trigger information are sometimes needed to be corrected from possible event jumps at this point of the analysis. Besides, the pointing information is fetched from the external drive report and interpolated on an event-by-event basis. Both the timestamp correction and the pointing information are described later in Section 4.1.3. The sourced data at this point would correspond to the R1 level in the CTA scheme. Then, calibrated waveforms are integrated within an 8-ns window around the peak and the signal's arrival time is estimated by averaging the charged-weighted time samples. The script performing these

²<https://pypi.org/project/protozfits/>

³https://github.com/cta-observatory/ctapipe_io_lst

steps also identifies and analyzes muon images to assess the telescope throughput and tune the efficiency of the MC simulations accordingly (the method is detailed in [Gaug et al., 2019b](#)).

At this stage, images still keep the information of all camera pixels for every event (DL1a), most of them containing fluctuating noise from the NSB light. Therefore, the images are cleaned to extract meaningful information from the Cherenkov light, filtering out the noisy pixels. Based on the so-called two-level *tailcut* cleaning procedure ([Lessard et al., 2001](#)), we select pixels above the *picture* and *boundary* charge thresholds of 8 and 4 p.e., respectively, besides having at least two neighbor pixels fulfilling these conditions. This selection is then fine-tuned by considering the charge distribution from interleaved pedestal events, checking the proximity of the arrival times between selected pixels and requiring a minimum pixel charge of 3% of the average charge of the three brightest pixels. The cleaned images are then parameterized following the approach by [Hillas \(1985\)](#), as depicted in Sect. 3.1.1. At this point, we use diagnostic tools to check and evaluate the correctness of the products of the analysis steps carried out so far, from the calibration to the parameterization stage. These data checks help us debug potential data issues and select quality data for higher-level analysis.

In the next stage, we use the extracted parameters from cleaned images (DL1b) from processed MC data to train Random Forest models for the regression of the energy and direction of the primary particle, as well as the classification of gamma rays differentiating them from hadronic particles. DL2 data incorporates these reconstructed parameters. Models are built using the `scikit-learn` machine learning library ([Pedregosa et al., 2011](#)). For the estimation of the direction, two models are trained based on the `disp` parameter (see Fig. 3.3). Another model is employed for the reconstruction of particle energy. Finally, another classifier model is trained using previously reconstructed quantities to infer the probability of the primary particle being a gamma (i.e., the gammaness). As the geomagnetic effects distort the images depending on the pointing coordinates of the telescope, we use point-source-like gamma MC simulations performed along pointing nodes close to the source path in the sky for training and testing the random forest models to take into account this effect.

The last analysis step carried out by `cta-lstchain` is the selection of gamma-like events and production of IRFs forming DL3 data. Different event filters can be applied. We usually apply energy-dependent gammaness and theta cuts based on the desired gamma efficiency in each energy bin. The IRFs calculation is done using the package `pyirf` ([Nöthe et al., 2022](#)). The higher-level analysis is performed using the standard science tool `Gammapy` described in Sect. 3.4.3.

4.1.3 Contributions to the development of `cta-lstchain`

I have contributed to the development of `cta-lstchain` in several aspects for several years. On one side, include and correct the timestamp and point information to the data stream. On the other hand, to create a script to produce summaries of the daily observations. Aside from that, I have also been helping to increase the stability, maintainability, and usability of the code. In this regard, I worked on implementing testing units, their automation using continuous integration (CI), and the deployment of the software documentation.

Timestamp information

As described in section 1.6.1, event-wise timestamps are provided by the UCTS based on White Rabbit technology and a GPS for the absolute time reference. Consequently, timestamp values in nanoseconds can be directly accessed when reading a raw data file as part of the event information, as seen in the code snippet below:

```
1 from ctapipe_io_lst import LSTEventSource
2 from astropy.time import Time
3 import astropy.units as u
4
5 source = LSTEventSource(
6     input_url="LST-1.1.Run02967.0000.fits.fz",
7     apply_drs4_corrections=False,
8     pointing_information=False,
9     trigger_information=False,
10 )
11
12 first_event = next(iter(source))
13 timestamp = first_event.lst.tel[1].evt.ucts_timestamp
14 Time(timestamp * u.ns, format="unix_tai").iso
15 >> '2020-11-21 00:28:18.954'
```

The timestamps are in UNIX format and International Atomic Time (TAI) scale, which means seconds elapsed since 1970-01-01 00:00:00, 37 leap seconds ahead of the Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) scale⁴ at the time of the writing of this thesis.

However, during the early phases of the LST-1 commissioning, we faced problems with the availability and stability of the UCTS-based timestamps. Sometimes, time and trigger type information was not reaching the camera event structure. The origin of the problem was understood to have different causes, for example, the malfunction of one of the involved subsystems, the communication between them, wrong data-taking setting during observations, or external problems giving rise to spoiled fragments of data. Consequently, the trigger type and time information were sometimes unavailable.

⁴The archive of leap seconds in last decades is available at <http://hpiers.obspm.fr/eop-pc>.

Occasionally, UCTS timestamps were available at the beginning of the run, but this information stopped being recorded at some point. Some other times, this information was entirely lost.

To overcome this issue, we alternatively constructed the event-by-event timestamps using the low-level counters from the PPS and 10 MHz clock signals from the UCTS from the TIB. Additionally, the *Dragon* modules of the camera readout have their own counters. The timestamp of the event n -th in TAI scale is built by summing the counters from both clock signals transformed to nanoseconds Δt_i and adding them to an absolute reference timestamp:

$$t_n = t_{\text{ref}} + \Delta t_n \text{ [ns]}$$

where, for a given event, $\Delta t_n = \text{PPS}_i + 10\text{MHz}_i - \text{PPS}_{\text{ref}} - 10\text{MHz}_{\text{ref}}$ is the combination of its counters (PPS and 10 MHz) after subtracting the counters corresponding to the reference timestamp t_{ref} . As reference timestamp, we used, when available, the UCTS-based timestamp and corresponding counters from the first event of a given observation run. Otherwise, the timestamp denoting the start of the run can be used instead. This reference timestamp has a few seconds offset, which cannot be accurately determined with respect to the recording of the first event. Also, this offset varies randomly from run to run. Thus, the timestamps built in this fashion cannot be used for analyses where timing accuracy and precision are needed (e.g., pulsar analyses). However, despite the few-second imprecision, they still can be used to interpolate the pointing coordinates on an event basis (see details later within this section) as the systematic error in the coordinates is within the pointing precision that can be achieved. Timestamps and counters of the first events are obtained and stored before starting the data processing.

Initially, we kept the three timestamps for redundancy and checking purposes. An event-wise flag in the camera event structure indicates the validity of a particular time source and trigger information. After monitoring the first year of data taking, analyzing the different issues regarding the availability and reliability of the provided timestamp, and that calculated afterward, it turned out that timestamps based on *Dragon* counters were the most flawless among the three of them. They have proven to be the source of time with higher availability and stability while keeping microsecond precision even if TIB and UCTS-based timing and trigger information streams were not correctly propagated to the camera event structure.

In addition, we check the consistency between UCTS and *Dragon*-based timestamps and log any event jump causing a shift of trigger and time information. To check the validity of the timestamp, we considered 375 observation runs recorded between August

Figure 4.1: Left panel: Distribution of time difference between Dragon and UCTS-based timestamps to check the consistency between both sources of time in LST-1 data. Right panel: Distribution of time intervals between consecutive triggered events. Assuming a Poissonian process with a deadtime $\simeq 7 \mu\text{s}$, the slope of the dashed line indicates the rate of the registered events $\simeq 5 \text{ kHz}$.

2020 and March 2021. Around 30% of them presented missing UCTS-based timestamps at some point. Most of the time, the loss of time information was momentary. In contrast, on only a few occasions, UCTS-based timestamps were not propagated to the camera event structures for most of the events of specific runs. Among those looking healthy, the offset between UCTS and Dragon-based timestamps was less than $1 \mu\text{s}$, therefore within the expected precision, as displayed in Fig. 4.1 left. The right panel of Fig. 4.1 shows the distribution of time differences between successive recorded events, assumed to follow a Poisson process with an event rate of about 5 kHz, considering a deadtime (minimum inter-arrival time) of roughly $7 \mu\text{s}$. The agreement of the data to the distribution indicates the sanity of the timestamps. An independent cross-check of the validity, accuracy, and precision of the LST-1 timing system is the detection of the 33-ms pulsation of the Crab pulsar with high statistical significance, as can be seen in Fig. 5.18.

Pointing information

The events recorded by the camera do not contain pointing information therein since the cadence at which this information can be logged is not fast enough to follow the high rate at which events are recorded. Instead, the drive system records the altitude and azimuth coordinates every few seconds in auxiliary files. The objective was to have telescope-pointing information for each event so that the coordinates of each event are reconstructed in later stages of the analysis.

In order to have the pointing information for every event, coordinates have to be

interpolated based on the logged drive information taking into account the timestamps of the events. This interpolation is done using `interp1d` function from [SciPy](#). Bending model corrections over the azimuth and altitude values are additionally applied if needed.

These timestamps and pointing calculations are implemented in `ctapipe_io_lst` and done when sourcing the events. Hence the information is directly available event-wise when opening a raw file. Both software developments and checks performed have helped to debug various issues in the involved subsystems (DAQ, drive, trigger, and clock) during the commissioning phase. Finally, it is important to stress that time and pointing event-by-event information is essential and utterly propagated to DL3 files. Hence, every gamma-ray photon in the list encloses its arrival time, reconstructed coordinates, and energy for higher-level analysis.

Summary of daily observations

When writing this thesis, we did not have a database containing the list of observations made by LST-1 during its first years of operation. Instead, each day we created a list of the observations made during the previous night. With that aim, we developed a script that produces enhanced character separated values (ECSV) files ([Astropy Developers](#)) listing the observation runs performed on a given date serving as grounds for a future proper database. Each run comprises a number of sequential files, dubbed *sub-runs*, which is the number of files in which a run is written to disk as each has the same maximum of events (the last sub-run can contain fewer events depending on when data acquisition stops). The number of sub-runs is also contained in the files as we use them later to parallelize the data processing. In addition, it includes the type of run (i.e., sky-data, DRS or pedestal calibration run) as guessed from the percentage of events with a given trigger tag (cosmic, pedestal, or flat-field trigger). The LST-1 data processing framework, described in the Sect. 4.2, uses these files to know what data to process and which calibration products to employ for each observation run.

Moreover, it stores the reference timestamps, and associated PPS and 10 MHz clock counters to build the event-wise timestamps described in the previous paragraphs. It also indicates whether the reference time is the UCTS (timestamps refer to a precise absolute timestamp) or not (hence the timestamps are inaccurate by a few seconds).

Tests and documentation

Apart from several bug fixes, part of my work has contributed to developments related to the maintainability and usability of `cta-lstchain`. On one side, I have helped

improve this library’s automatic unit tests, which are meant for checking that the developed code behaves as expected. They are functions that check if the output obtained corresponds to the expected result from given input arguments. These checks are beneficial when developing software since they allow the quick identification of possible errors in new code and undesired effects of new changes in existing code. In `cta-lstchain`, we use the testing framework [pytest](#).

In particular, I implemented several tests for the previously unimplemented observed data processing scripts, remarkably increasing the percentage of code covered by unit tests. We use trimmed sample test files (due to the large size of the original files) as input arguments, along with the necessary auxiliary files to check the processing of those test files. Since the data taken by the LST-1 are not public, we host them on a password-protected server, from which the continuous integration and continuous delivery (CI/CD) pipeline downloads them every time tests are run.

`Pytest` offers a handy tool, the so-called *fixtures*, to arrange the test input data set and temporal directory structure to store the testing products. Fixture functions define test objects and create, at the same time, files or directories that can be used as input by any other unit test across the library, provided they are defined in a script named `conftest.py`. In this analysis library, meant to build a pipeline, it is crucial to establish some dependencies among the tests, so that other tests use the products generated in previous tests as input. This orchestration of scripts is the same idea we employ in the data processing pipeline described in section 4.2. The following snippet shows an example of how two connected fixtures are defined. The first fixture creates a temporal directory, while the second uses the previously created directory to store the run summary file that subsequent tests will use.

```

1 @pytest.mark.private_data
2 @pytest.fixture(scope="session")
3 def dir_observed_files(tmp_path_factory):
4     """Temporal common directory for processing observed data."""
5     return tmp_path_factory.mktemp("observed_files")
6
7
8 @pytest.fixture(scope='session')
9 def run_summary_path(dir_observed_files):
10    date = "20200218"
11    r0_path = test_data / "real/R0"
12    run_summary_path = dir_observed_files / f"RunSummary_{date}.ecsv"
13    run_program(
14        "lstchain_create_run_summary",
15        "--date", date,
16        "--r0-path", r0_path,
17        "--output-dir", dir_observed_files
18    )

```

```
return run_summary_path
```

These tests are part of the CI/CD library’s pipeline, which can be run either locally or remotely as part of an automatic workflow based on [GitHub Actions](#), triggered every time code changes are proposed. Apart from running the unit tests, the pipeline automatically checks the code’s syntax, style, and quality, making the development less error-prone and preserving a consistent style. As a result, the code is easier to read and maintain. Another aspect that eases the development process is the automatic publishing of the library to the software repository [PyPI](#).

In addition, I also helped in automating the deployment of `cta-lstchain` documentation. Documentation is a paramount aspect of a software library for its users. Typically, the documentation describes the installation process and the analysis’s theoretical background, including examples, tutorials, and guides for best development practices. It also contains the application programming interface (API) documentation, based on the docstrings comments defined at the beginning of a function, describing its use, purpose, and input and output parameters, if any. Docstrings written in the appropriate format are interpreted by libraries dedicated to generating documentation in HTML format publishable as a web page.

In `cta-lstchain`, we use the [Sphinx](#) static-site generator library. Documentation source code, kept in the `docs/` sub-directory, comprises configuration file `conf.py` defining basics settings, a `Makefile` with the compilation instructions, and the files with the documentation content itself written in reStructuredText (reST) markup language. The documentation compilation and deployment are automated as part of the CI/CD pipeline mentioned above each time the code repository is modified. Publishing can be done directly through [GitHub Pages](#) or other external applications such as [ReadTheDocs](#).

4.2 On-site analysis pipeline for the LST-1

The following section presents the rationale for developing an on-site analysis pipeline for processing the LST-1 data, describes the pipeline prototype, and explains how we have handled the processing of all the data taken by the telescope prototype. The development of this software and processing of the entire LST-1 dataset constitutes a substantial part of this thesis.

Figure 4.2: Web site home page of the `cta-lstchain` documentation (<https://cta-observatory.github.io/cta-lstchain/>).

4.2.1 Motivation

The three categories of data products contemplated within the CTA data model are the following⁵:

- **Category-A** data will be produced by an on-site real-time analysis (RTA) pipeline, using simplified analysis techniques offering less precision and higher systematic uncertainties as the priority is promptness. As final data products, preliminary high-level results will be obtained and distributed for rapid science alert generation (SAG). Moreover, they will provide immediate data-quality monitoring.
- **Category B** comprises data products processed offline by an OSA pipeline next day after they are collected. Having the next-day data products available, we can confirm the preliminary results from the previous category, organize follow-up campaigns, and rapidly help spot issues in the telescope’s operation. Since the time to obtain these products is not as critical as in the previous case, they will be based on a not-so-simplified calibration and analysis, improving data quality.
- **Category-C** data have the highest possible quality based on more elaborated calibrations and analysis techniques whose precision meets the CTA requirements.

⁵Although the reference document is internal to the CTA Consortium, the idea was already outlined in Contreras et al. (2016a) and Lamanna (2016).

These products will be produced in off-site data centers in a more extended time frame and are supposed to be the final ones ready for publication.

Both on-site RTA and OSA pipelines are planned to be developed within CTA as a result of a more general effort (see, e.g., [Bulgarelli et al., 2016](#); [Fioretti et al., 2016](#)). However, the development of the OSA pipeline presented here, dubbed `lstosa`, responded to the necessity of having a data processing framework working by the time LST-1 started regular data-taking in November 2019, when there was no working RTA pipeline. It has played an essential role in supporting the commissioning of the telescope and the development of the analysis software for observed data.

The OSA pipeline aims to automatically orchestrate the offline data reduction process using the LST-1 analysis library, `cta-lstchain`, in an on-site data center placed at the telescope site (see section [1.6.1](#)). This pipeline allows any member of the collaboration to perform fast and preliminary higher-level analyses, which are relevant for managing the observing schedule when prompt time of opportunity (ToO) follow-up observations of flaring sources need to be planned. In addition, checks help to detect problems quickly during the commissioning phase, so rapid actions can be taken to solve potential problems as swiftly as possible without disrupting the regular data collection rate. Due to the enormous amount of daily recorded data, transferring them throughout the network connection from La Palma to off-site data centers before their analysis off-site would delay the generation of analysis outcomes. Therefore, having this pipeline working on-site is quite convenient as processing the data before they are transferred is faster.

In addition, this pipeline is currently used to reprocess the entire LST-1 dataset with new and more performant software versions or fine-tuned settings, resembling the category C of data products foreseen in CTA⁶. Aside from these points, OSA provides bookkeeping for the observations, tracking the provenance of the data products to ensure reproducibility.

4.2.2 Description

`lstosa`⁷ is a Python-based pipeline connecting the stages of the LST-1 data analysis using `cta-lstchain` (section [4.1](#)) to reduce the uncalibrated raw data to science-ready products. It integrates with a job scheduler to efficiently make full use of the capacities of the on-site computing cluster to speed up the data reduction. The architecture design

⁶In the future, in CTA, these reprocessings are planned to be done in off-site data centers.

⁷<https://github.com/cta-observatory/lstosa>

Figure 4.3: Flowchart of `lstosa` with its three main blocks: pre-processing preparation of the analysis workflow, batch processing of the data, and finally, some post-processing tasks close the workflow by checking for job completion and storing the products in their final directories.

and core code are based on the experience gained in the OSA pipeline developed for the MAGIC experiment (Fidalgo et al., 2016). The workflow scheme is outlined in Fig. 4.3. Each of its components that prepares and manages the data reduction is detailed in the following:

Pre-processing

The so-called `sequencer` script handles the pre-processing workflow that prepares the data reduction. It is executed daily by a cron job scheduled in the morning, right after data taken has finished, because it has to wait until some auxiliary data are available. Thanks to the cron jobs, we can fully automatize the orchestration of the pipeline, so there is no need for manual intervention unless a problem occurs during processing. Running the following command triggers the preparation and actual data processing:

```
1 $ sequencer --config configuration_file.cfg --date YYYY-MM-DD LST1
```

This workflow starts by producing the summary of the night’s observations. For a given date, the data recorded typically contains observations of astrophysical targets (hereafter referred to as sky data) and additional calibrations. Each observation block is also known as a *run*. Sky-data *runs* typically last about 15-20 minutes and are composed of $\mathcal{O}(10^2)$ sequential files (nicknamed sub-runs), each comprising less than 10 seconds of data taking (5.3×10^4 events recorded at a typical rate of 6 kHz), which approximately corresponds to a file of 6 GB. Attending to their type, `lstosa` identifies which observations will be processed each day and which calibration *runs* will be used to calibrate the sky data. Based on this information, the pipeline decomposes into

sequences of sky-data observations and calibrations, establishing dependencies between them, so they are processed sequentially. Each sequence object corresponds to a *run*, the essential data processing piece.

Sequences have attributes like the type of run, the number of sub-runs that comprise them, the date, the telescope⁸, and the name of the primary target source in the FoV⁹. Part of this metadata information is fetched from the TCU database, where data-taking information is logged and centralized. In addition, another set of attributes of the sequence objects is employed to indicate the processing status of each sequence. This first procedure is implemented in the `nightsummary` and `extract` sub-modules.

Once the runs to be processed are identified, we generate the analysis workflow by connecting the stages for both the calibration and the sky-data reconstruction sequences. For each run, `lstosa` creates a pilot job batch script wrapping the calls to the actual `cta-lstchain` commands, with the corresponding input arguments. A configuration file contains the parameters controlling the workflow and defines the I/O paths.

The on-site analysis pipeline integrates the usage of the job scheduler available in the on-site computing infrastructure, SLURM¹⁰, taking advantage of the computing capacities of the on-site computing cluster for faster data reduction. The job-pilot scripts are submitted via SLURM's command `sbatch`. We specify the job requirements (the wall time and memory size requested for the job execution, their priority in the job queue, and the definition of the standard output/error logs) using the SLURM environment variables defined at the top of the job file preceded by `#SBATCH`. For testing, the job pilot script can also be run interactively and locally without needing a batch scheduling system. The workload manager creates dependencies between the jobs. Hence those corresponding to sky-data processing run only after the calibration sequence has finished successfully since the former needs the calibration files generated by the latter as input arguments.

Using the SLURM job array capability, each of the jobs scheduled for a run is split in turn into similar-size jobs, one for each sub-run, achieving a highly parallelized data reduction. SLURM takes care of allocating the resources and running the jobs whenever resources are available. Performing the data reduction in a reasonable time is possible

⁸Even though we are considering here the analysis of the LST-1, `lstosa` is also designed to process the data from more telescopes and eventually conduct stereoscopic analyses whenever the corresponding tools become available in `cta-lstchain`.

⁹We specify the target source name for a given run for bookkeeping purposes. However, each observation block in CTA will not have any associated target in the future because there could be several sources in the FoV –especially for those telescopes with a larger one.

¹⁰However, it could be adapted to any other batch system manager.

OSA processing status

Processing data from: 2022-09-21. Last updated: 2022-09-22 08:45:24 UTC

Tel	Seq	Parent	Type	Run	Subruns	Source	Action	Tries	JobID	State	CPU_time	Exit	DL1%	MUONS%	DL1AB%	DATACHECK%	DL2%
LST1	1	None	PEDCALIB	9258	5	None	Check	1	19334009	COMPLETED	00:22:52	0:0	None	None	None	None	None
LST1	2	1	DATA	9259	10	1ES1959+650	Check	1	19334010	COMPLETED	00:26:57	0:0	100	100	100	100	0
LST1	3	1	DATA	9260	137	1ES1959+650	Check	1	19334011	COMPLETED	00:28:20	0:0	100	100	100	100	0
LST1	4	1	DATA	9261	161	1ES1959+650	Check	1	19334012	COMPLETED	00:29:04	0:0	100	100	100	100	0
LST1	5	1	DATA	9262	27	BLLac	Check	1	19334013	COMPLETED	00:28:47	0:0	100	100	100	100	0
LST1	6	1	DATA	9263	154	BLLac	Check	1	19334014	RUNNING	00:03:59	None	100	11	11	11	0
LST1	7	1	DATA	9264	151	BLLac	Check	1	19334015	RUNNING	00:03:12	None	100	0	0	0	0
LST1	8	1	DATA	9265	149	BLLac	Check	1	19334016	RUNNING	00:02:38	None	44	0	0	0	0
LST1	9	1	DATA	9266	141	BLLac	Check	1	19334017	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	10	1	DATA	9267	132	BLLac	Check	1	19334018	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	11	1	DATA	9268	47	BLLac	Check	1	19334019	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	12	1	DATA	9269	113	LSI+61	Check	1	19334020	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	13	1	DATA	9270	132	LSI+61	Check	1	19334021	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	14	1	DATA	9271	142	LSI+61	Check	1	19334022	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	15	1	DATA	9272	152	LSI+61	Check	1	19334023	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	16	1	DATA	9273	360	Crab	Check	1	19334024	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	17	1	DATA	9274	61	Crab	Check	1	19334025	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	18	1	DATA	9275	113	Crab	Check	1	19334026	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	19	1	DATA	9276	131	Crab	Check	1	19334027	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	20	1	DATA	9277	182	Crab	Check	1	19334028	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	21	1	DATA	9278	187	Crab	Check	1	19334029	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	22	1	DATA	9279	190	Crab	Check	1	19334030	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	23	1	DATA	9280	193	Crab	Check	1	19334031	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0
LST1	24	1	DATA	9281	88	Crab	Check	1	19334032	PENDING	00:00:00	None	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 4.4: Snapshot of the data-processing status monitoring web page. This static HTML file containing the output table from the `sequencer` script is regenerated regularly. Any member of the LST Collaboration can access it.

due to the parallelization of the processes. Assuming that ten runs consisting of 100 sequential files each are taken in one night, the 1000 sub-runs could all be processed simultaneously in about an hour. If we were to process each of the ten observations simultaneously without sub-run parallelization, the processing time would increase to several days.

We also use the `sequencer` script to monitor the state of the jobs. For that purpose, we implemented a dry-run mode that does not submit any job nor produce any output file but only simulates the subsequent steps of the workflow. Fig. 4.4 shows an example of the `sequencer` output table we use to monitor the daily data reduction. The job status (elapsed time, return code, job state) is retrieved from the SLURM jobs database by wrapping calls to the `squeue` and `sacct` commands.

Batch data processing

The data processing comprises two analysis flows: the first generates the files used to calibrate the sky observation data, and the subsequent workflow calibrates and reduces these sky data. The commands that form the analysis sequence are specified in the job-pilot scripts created in the pre-processing stage and are executed parallelly

in batch for each sequential file using SLURM. The analysis directives are outlined in the yellow-highlighted boxes of Fig. 4.5 and described in the following.

An initial batch process connects the two calibration steps that daily produce the files used later to calibrate the observations collected on the same day. This way, we try to minimize potential systematic effects. The first command produces a file containing the offset corrections for the baseline in the DRS4 chips. The second step generates another file with the coefficients for converting the ADC counts recorded by each camera pixel to photoelectrons. For this stage, we employ two dedicated calibration data taken every night. First, a so-called DRS4 pedestal run is taken with the camera shutter closed and triggering events randomly to record just the baseline signal. The second dubbed pedestal-calibration run contains events where the camera was uniformly illuminated with an intensity light interleaved with events containing only randomly triggered noise. Camera calibration experts produce additional calibration files on a less regular basis. The purpose of these other files is twofold. On the one hand, the temporal alignment of the signal of the pulses recorded by the DRS4 chips. There is no need to regenerate this file daily, just when a camera module is replaced. On the other hand, to calculate the second-order noise term for the F-Factor method used to derive the charge calibration coefficients. Every few months, this is done by fitting the signal from several calibration runs with different light intensities produced using different filters for the light pulses emitted by the calibration box. The details of the calibration procedure for the LST-1 are described in section 4.1.1.

Sky-data processing jobs are executed afterward as they use the calibration files previously produced to calibrate and perform the subsequent steps of the analysis. The workflow aims to reduce the non-calibrated raw data up to DL3. However, it currently produces calibrated data and image parameters (DL1) and reconstructs the primary particle physical parameters (DL2). A more thorough description of each analysis step for the LST-1 data is presented in section 4.1.2. The reconstruction of the direction and energy of the primary particle, along with particle classification for DL2 production, requires RF regressor and classifier models trained with MC-simulated data sets. Besides, IRFs for the high-level analysis is based on the gamma-ray MC DL2 test sample. These simulated-based products are created with `lstMCpipe` (Vuillaume et al., 2022), a pipeline analogous to `lstosa` devoted to orchestrate the analysis of the MC simulated data in the on-site computing center managed by the LST Collaboration.

The automation of the production of standard DL2 products and next-day preliminary science products is still under development in `lstosa` as `cta-lstchain`'s tools needed for this purpose are still not ready. The first approach was to use MC data

Figure 4.5: Data flow of LST-1 analysis from raw data to high-level products. It corresponds to the batch data processing block of Fig. 4.3. Blocks in dashed lines group the data levels or types according to their role in the LST-1 data processing. Raw non-calibrated data are first calibrated using dedicated calibration runs, then reconstructed using the RF models trained by another pipeline devoted to MC data reduction, `1stMCpipe`. The higher-level products are obtained in the final block using Science Tools like `Gammapy`. Processing steps within the framework of the `1stosa` correspond to the yellow-shaded boxes (calibration, sky-data reconstruction, and high-level analysis). However, although it is included in the diagram, the production data levels higher than DL2 are still under development.

simulated at just two zenith angles (20 and 40 degrees) and fixed azimuth, which did not consider the effect of the geomagnetic field on the shape of the shower images. Similarly, just considering three zenith angles also introduced systematic effects on the reconstruction of the properties of the primary particle. It was recently decided to follow a new strategy based on MC data simulated in a dense grid of pointing coordinates such that the MC data mimic the path of observed targets more realistically along the sky. The aim with this “all-sky simulations” is to interpolate the IRFs based on the pointing coordinates, not simply use the closest MC node. To standardize the production of DL3 and higher-level analysis, we first plan to apply different sets of reasonable gamma-ray event selection cuts for performing automatic preliminary fast analyses for most of the targets observed.

Aside from performing the data reduction, the pipeline also provides data-quality check products that help us promptly debug problems during data taking and quality-select data for higher-level analyses.

Each analysis stage has a level associated with it, which controls the analysis flow. These subsequent levels cache checkpoints each time an analysis stage is completed. Provided a given step fails, the return code is caught and the command is retried a maximum of three times or until it succeeds. Before the retry, the pipeline cleans up the corresponding created non-valid files, so they are produced again. This approach is convenient when run-time errors occur due to intensive I/O usage in the computing cluster.

Provenance

The data analysis steps executed are captured for each *run*, together with the configuration parameters and input arguments needed, as well as intermediate files produced. This information is serialized in JSON files, following the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) Provenance Model Recommendation (Servillat, M. et al., 2020), whose three key elements and connection between them are sketched in Fig. 4.6. The model relates the data products (*entity*) with the user (*agent*) who generated them and the pipeline tasks used for that (*activity*). Provenance graphs are also provided in PDF files, rendering an overview of the data analysis process, which eases traceability inspection. A more detailed provenance query tool integrating the storage of provenance information in a database is also foreseen. Provenance tracking was introduced in `1stosa` by José Enrique Ruiz (IAA-CSIC) following the ecosystem described in Servillat et al. (2021).

Figure 4.6: World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) provenance model concept used to trace the data products produced by the LST-1 on-site analysis pipeline, the way they are generated, and the responsible of the analysis. Adapted from <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-primer/>.

Post-processing

Finally, another closing script named `autocloser` is in charge of running the last steps of the on-site workflow after the batch data processing is finished. It is executed similarly to the pre-processing `sequencer` script:

```
1 $ autocloser --config configuration_file.cfg --date YYYY-MM-DD LST1
```

This script first checks that all jobs have finished successfully. For this purpose, check that the expected analysis products were produced for every sub-run, the state of all jobs is completed, and none of them present a non-zero return code indicating problems during the analysis. After the first check is successful, data products are transferred to their final storage locations and merged run-wise for easy handling in further analysis stages. Apart from the files containing the actual data, some checks products are generated and merged daily for inspection and diagnosing potential problems. Several files are produced for this purpose: (i) first a text file where spotted issues like quantities outside certain limits are noted, (ii) an HTML based on the

`bokeh`¹¹ plotting library to visualize and evaluate the quality of the data interactively, (iii) HDF5 formatted files containing the bulk of the data-check information that can indeed be used for data-quality selection. The possibility of merging these daily data check files is handy for long-term monitoring. Data-check plots are swiftly provided to the entire collaboration through a web interface. Finally, the provenance captured during the batch data processing is parsed from the previously stored logs, and files that allow easier inspection are created as described above. To avoid repeatedly processing the data for a given particular date, `autocloser` sets a flag indicating that the on-site analysis for that particular night has finished successfully and no further action is expected.

Software development

`lstosa` is Python-based open software hosted in a public GitHub repository, facilitating collaborative work in its development. As a software project, its development additionally involves coping with maintenance and usability issues in the same way described for the `cta-lstchain` program in the previous section. As already discussed, implementing test units covering most of the developed code is very useful, especially during the development process, as they allow us to anticipate potential bugs while implementing new code. We have also tried to keep the style as appropriate as possible according to the quality standards, which helps in the development process of collaborative projects. On the other hand, we have created the library's documentation (see Fig. 4.7), including the description of the code and its different components. It also provides installation instructions and usage examples.

For the packaging and distribution of `lstosa`, we have followed the guidelines recommended in the Python community. The packaging includes the versions of the dependencies required to ensure the program's correct functioning and reproducibility in isolated environments. For ease of distribution and installation, it has also been published in PyPI (<https://pypi.org/project/lstosa/>).

4.2.3 LST-1 on-site data processing

The on-site analysis pipeline, `lstosa`, has been running in the on-site installed computing cluster (see section 1.6.1) since the start of telescope data acquisition in November 2019. Ever since, we have been employing it to perform the next-day processing of all data recorded, being a crucial support element during the commissioning phase of the

¹¹<https://docs.bokeh.org/>

Figure 4.7: Snapshot of the home page of the `lstosa` documentation website <https://lstosa.readthedocs.io/>.

telescope prototype. At the time of the writing, after almost three years of operation, LST-1 has taken more than 800 hours of data over almost 300 nights, as shown in the cumulative observed time distribution depicted in the right panel of Fig 4.8. There are two 3-month periods of no data-taking due to external reasons to the telescope, the COVID-19 lockdown in 2020 and the eruption of the *Cumbre Vieja* volcano in La Palma island where the telescope is located in late 2021. Other periods with no data-taking were due to problems in different subsystems of the telescope prototype. The computational requirements and performance of the on-site analysis running in the LST-1 data center at La Palma are described below.

Each observing night, roughly 3 hours of sky data are typically taken on average, with a maximum of about 7 hours on just a few nights (see the left panel of Fig. 4.8). The rest of the time was usually devoted to performing tests, calibrations, or dealing with various problems.

The time used to process the data collected on a particular night can be understood

Figure 4.8: Left: nightly elapsed observing time for the LST-1. Right: cumulative observation time of the LST-1 from November 2019 to October 2022. More than 800 hours of sky data have been taken.

as follows. The first calibration sequence is executed once a night. It takes about 20 minutes (8 minutes for the production of the DRS4 pedestal corrections file and the rest for the production of the file with the load calibration coefficients). Then, for each sequential sky-data file, the data reduction is executed in parallel in each available node of the SLURM farm. Each batch job lasts about 40-45 minutes in a single core, distributed as follows in each analysis step: R0 to DL1a takes about 30-35 minutes, both DL1a to DL1b and the DL1 data-quality check take a few minutes. Adding the DL1b to DL2 would take another few additional minutes for the analysis. We note that the time taken for the analysis sequence for the sky data is just illustrative, especially when there is intensive use of reading and writing to disk. In these saturation situations, the processes may be frozen for some time, so the computation time may occasionally increase unpredictably. Fig. 4.9 shows the statistics for the memory size usage and time elapsed for a sample of jobs. Regarding the memory consumption of the jobs, it is interesting to note that there is no correlation between longer elapsed times and higher memory usage. Indeed, as can be seen in Fig. 4.9, a small number of jobs with short duration have a memory usage significantly higher than expected. The solid lines indicate the upper limits of the time and memory consumption job requirements, a maximum of 2 hours and 4 GB of memory per single core. In this sample of $\sim 10^7$ jobs, more than 99% of them fulfill those requirements. Those outside those limits are canceled and retried. Optimization of memory capacity and computational time requirements has been done by trial and error.

Because of SLURM's usage configuration, the number of concurrent jobs we can

Figure 4.9: Elapsed time and memory usage per single-core for $\sim 10^7$ jobs corresponding to the last version of data processing from raw level to parameterized cleaned images. Solid lines indicate the maximum computation time and memory consumption requested for the jobs. More than 99% of the jobs lie within those limits.

run is limited to approximately 1300, each using a single core. In addition, it is worth noting that the computing cluster is not exclusively used for the on-site processing of data observed by the LST-1. It is also used to perform Monte Carlo simulations for the reconstruction of the data and any high-level analysis carried out by any member of the collaboration. For this reason, we do not always have the maximum number of free cores available, which can delay the processing of the data taken by the telescope, even though on-site data reduction processes have higher priority in the job queue.

On average, the number of sequential sky data files taken each night is about 1000 sub-runs (on rare occasions, it has been as high as 3000 files). Provided the maximum number of cores (about 1300) were available to perform the data reduction, all jobs could run simultaneously and typically finish in under an hour. To that time should be added about 20 minutes for the initial calibration sequence and the time required for post-processing. Over time, automation has increased to a point where the pipeline does not need human interaction unless problems occur during processing due to poor data quality. The script checking that the data processing is finished runs automatically through a cron job every half hour throughout the day. If problems occur during data reduction that requires human intervention, the time in which the

Figure 4.10: Percentage of the nights whose processing was finished at a given hour after `1stosa` started running every morning at 8:00 UTC. The statistics collected correspond to observing nights from May 2021 onwards.

night can be considered processed is generally longer. Figure 4.10 shows the percentage of nights processed after 8:00 UTC when data reduction begins. On more than 80% of the days, the reduced data and corresponding checks are available around noon the day after they are collected.

In addition to the next-day reduction of the daily data, we have conducted several reprocessing of the complete data set collected by the telescope. Each reprocessing is performed when there is a major release of a new version of the LST-1 data analysis library, `cta-lstchain`. Each new version brings improvements in the analysis chain, i.e., bug fixes, more effective cleaning algorithms, better background suppression, and new features that, in turn, improve event reconstruction, eventually enhancing the performance of the analysis. In these first three years of data acquisition, five on-site reprocessings of all the data recorded by the telescope have been carried out using `cta-lstchain` versions v0.4 to v0.9 (the latest version available when writing this thesis). As new data have been taken, the reprocessings have become more demanding in terms of computational time, requiring a couple of weeks of work between coordination, computation, and post-verification time. As an estimate, the more than 800 hours of sky observations taken to date correspond to approximately 3×10^5 sequential files. Considering that each one takes about 45 minutes to process on a single core, a total

of about 10^5 days of computation per single core would be needed. Having access to 1000 simultaneous cores, reprocessing all data would take about ten days of processing time. This estimation does not count the generation of the daily calibration files, adding another 20 minutes of processing per day of observation.

4.2.4 Discussion

Based on the MAGIC on-site analysis pipeline, `lstosa` has been a helpful tool during the commissioning phase of the LST-1. Thanks to it, we have automated on-site processing of the massive amount of data collected daily with the telescope. Members of the collaboration have had access to the reduced data promptly, typically a few hours from the completion of data collection. Otherwise, transferring first the raw data to an off-site computing center and performing there the reduction would further delay the delivery of reduced data products. On the one hand, it has made it possible to perform high-level analyses, which are essential to determine the emission state of potential flaring sources quickly and thus to organize multiwavelength monitoring campaigns as soon as possible. `lstosa` has been especially important during these years since no real-time analysis pipeline is working for LST-1 yet.

On the other hand, on-site analysis has helped quickly identify data-taking problems so that experts can fix them as soon as possible. It has also helped debug the analysis library `cta-lstchain` since a massive amount of data taken under various conditions has been scrutinized. Due to the large number of analyses performed, `lstosa` is susceptible to potential data problems due to data-taking anomalies that may require adaptations in `cta-lstchain` and would otherwise have gone unnoticed. In this regard, we note that having a common framework like `lstosa` helps to significantly avoid potential human errors related to the misconfiguration of the analysis. Also, we would end up with a wide variety of low-level data products with hard-to-follow traceability.

An essential part of the on-site analysis system has been the integration with the job scheduler to make efficient use of the computational capacity of the on-site data center. It has also been a crucial tool for processing large-scale data, facilitating job monitoring, and error handling during analysis. Otherwise, data processing would not have been possible in such tight time frames. Besides that, the pipeline has also been helpful for observations and analysis bookkeeping.

Future developments

There are some missing features in `lstosa` planned for future development that could

ease the handling of the data analysis or extend it with new capabilities. Some of them are discussed in the following:

- At the moment, `lstosa` does only perform the source-independent analysis. We could also include another stream conducting the source-dependent analysis approach, for which we would need additionally to know which source is being observed.
- Currently, we standardly produce DL1b analysis products and associated data-quality checks. Further developments include processing the observed data to DL2 and DL3. Recently the collaboration has started to use an “all-sky” MC production for fine-tuning the association of simulated and observed data. MC data is produced in a grid of pointing positions. We would then interpolate the different pointing positions of the data recorded by the telescope to the nearest MC node, such that every observation block has associated IRFs with stable and non-changing conditions. At this moment, these interpolation tools are still under development in `cta-lstchain` and `pyirf` libraries and, therefore, not yet implemented in `lstosa` as part of the standard data analysis.
- The next natural step is to produce science-ready data products (DL3) and next-day fast high-level results. Machinery to add these two subsequent analysis stages is ready within `lstosa` as it has been designed modularly. We intend to apply several sets of gamma-ray selection cuts well suited for most observations. Based on these DL3 data sets, we would eventually produce preliminary science products for fast-checking the activity state of potential flaring sources.
- We do not yet integrate a centralized database to collect information derived from data processing. This problem has been discussed within the LST collaboration without leading to a definitive solution. For example, possible use cases practical at different levels are: (i) indicate which auxiliary files have been used in the analysis, which runs have been used for the calibration of the cosmic data, (ii) know the completion status of data processing, hence checking the readiness of the data to be transferred to off-site data centers and (iii) perform data quality selection. Each aspect might require a separate database at face value, although maintaining several databases would be more demanding. Given the data structure, we suggest implementing several relational tables within a single database as an intermediate solution.

- Another extension of the work done in the on-site analysis of LST-1 would be the inclusion of the joint analysis of the observations made simultaneously to the nearby MAGIC telescopes. A common on-site analysis would analyze the MAGIC and LST-1 data using a ctape-based analysis library¹², matching events detected by the three telescopes using timestamps, and finally, jointly reconstruct the data. The combined analysis aims to achieve higher sensitivity than the MAGIC telescopes (better than the individual sensitivity of LST-1, as described in the next section), as well as a cross-calibration since LST-1 would benefit from having a solvent system observing at the same time with the same conditions. As maintainers of the on-site analysis chains of both telescopes, we have collaborated in designing the joint analysis strategy and managing the joint observations by both instruments.

Lessons learned for the future CTAO

During the commissioning phase of the LST-1, we prototyped a data processing management system as no official architecture was available within the CTA Consortium ready to be used for the LST-1 data handling. Nonetheless, the Data Processing and Preservation System (DPPS) computing division of the CTA Consortium intends to develop a data processing framework to be used in the science phase of the future CTAO, consisting of calibration, simulations, data-quality monitoring, and data-processing pipelines. It will aim to perform the same low-level analysis presented here since providing directly to the end users DL3 data products. With this regard, there are some aspects of the data processing we have dealt with during these first years of operation of LST-1 that could serve as lessons learned with regard to the operation of CTAO:

- The orchestration of data processing must be **extensible** to any telescope and flexible enough to process data from any combination of telescopes. This way, it can be used as new telescopes become operative until the final telescope layout is complete. One potential problem in processing data collected by dozens of telescopes is the highly demanding next-day data reduction. We suggest reserving nodes in the batch farm dedicated exclusively to this task. In addition, we recommend limiting the use of local machines for other types of analysis that may require very intensive reading and writing files. Any tasks not essential in the data collection and processing workflow and not essential to be performed on-site should be outsourced and carried out in off-site data centers.

¹²<https://github.com/cta-observatory/magic-cta-pipe>

- During the commissioning phase, the instrument has constantly been evolving. This fact makes it necessary to change the analysis settings accordingly depending on the period in which the data were collected and, therefore, adapt the on-site pipeline accordingly. Hopefully, this problem of non-stability will not be that important in the future as it is expected that the operation will be smoother after the commissioning phase. However, there will still be varying weather conditions, aging of the telescope, and hazardous situations that would, in turn, result in data needing different analysis treatments. Unstable data-taking conditions can be addressed using, for example, tailored MC simulations on a run-wise base for which **observed and simulated data pipelines need to be closely connected**.
- It would be convenient to start the development from scratch using existing libraries for **workflow management** (e.g., [Luigi](#), [Snakemake](#), [Airflow](#), or [Common Workflow Language](#)). They already incorporate features needed in an analysis pipeline and would reduce the need to add them ad hoc, as we have done for the LST-1 on-site analysis pipeline, not taking advantage of already developed tools. The tool should be flexible enough for where data only needs to be reprocessed beyond a certain level without running the entire analysis chain end-to-end and **configurable** via a setup file that would compile the requested analysis steps.
- These years, we have lacked the essential **metadata** to know which data were to be analyzed and how to do it. This information must be gathered and centralized. Moreover, related to the previous point, the data processing workflow can be more easily designed and adapted to the various data-taking conditions.
- **Automating** the different tasks that make up the data processing pipeline is one of the keys to achieving an autonomous system. In our on-site analysis pipeline prototype, we have followed an approach based on a cron job scheduler that depends on assuming a priori a specific duration for each analysis step. However, this approach can fail when unforeseen problems arise during processing, which we overcome through the repeated use of cron jobs. A data-driven approach might be more convenient, i.e., a database would indicate the existence of new observations that the pipeline would identify and begin to process based on a preset configuration established by a production manager. The different steps would follow sequentially with dependencies between them. For further self-sufficiency, we suggest that it should define an **error-handling** schema to allow

certain decisions to be made in case of known errors in the analysis that can be overcome with a different configuration. Nevertheless, even with a high degree of automation, overall human supervision is recommended.

- Finally, we stress the importance of the **provenance** of the data produced, registering how the analysis was performed, and which settings were used, which steps were followed. The provenance would ensure that the analysis is traceable and reproducible in other environments with the appropriate analysis libraries and dependencies.

Chapter 5

Performance of the Large Size Telescope prototype

This work has been done in collaboration with Abelardo Moralejo, Rubén López-Coto, Thomas Vuillaume, and Seiya Nozaki as part of the first performance study of the LST-1 using MC simulations and observations from the Crab Nebula conducted during its commissioning phase. My contribution has been the low-level processing of the entire observed Crab dataset (calibration, cleaning and geometrical parameterization, which corresponds to DL1b) following the source-independent analysis approach using the LST-1 onsite analysis pipeline (`1stosa`). Then, starting from reconstructed parameters (DL2), I also did the source-independent high-level analysis of the Crab Nebula, obtaining its spectrum and light curve.

5.1 Context

This chapter evaluates the LST-1 performance using MC simulated data and Crab Nebula observations taken during its commissioning phase. The LST-1 is the first of the four LSTs telescopes planned for the future CTA-North observatory. These telescopes will be sensitive to the lowest energies of the range in which CTA is expected to operate. In particular, the LSTs are expected to be capable of detecting gamma rays starting at about 20 GeV. Section 1.6.1 describes the instrument and its subsystems.

We evaluate its performance based on the data analysis from the Crab PWN (hereafter Crab Nebula), considered the brightest VHE gamma-ray source with a steady flux extensively studied for decades. Thus, the Crab Nebula is an excellent standard candle and calibration source for IACTs. This astrophysical object is reviewed in Section 1.2. The other central pillar of the work is the use of Monte Carlo simulations, essential for analyzing the data, which have been fine-tuned from the observations of the Crab Nebula.

The following sections describe the dataset and the MC simulations used for this study, as well as the analysis pipeline employed to reduce, reconstruct and analyze the data. We compared both simulated and observed data finding a good agreement between them. Next, we obtained several figures of merits as the angular and energy resolution, energy threshold, and flux sensitivity, to assess the telescope's performance. This characterization will constitute the benchmark for the analyses of the rest of the sources observed by LST-1. Hence this work ensures their reliability. Finally, the high-level spectral and temporal analysis of a quality-selected Crab Nebula dataset is carried out, proving that the prototype performs as expected. This study also discusses the possible systematic errors in the data analysis, which will be detailed in a forthcoming paper.

5.2 LST-1 observations and data-quality selection

In this work, we have used data from Crab Nebula observations conducted between November 2020 and March 2022, approximately spanning 1.5 years, during the commissioning phase of the LST-1. These observations were performed in the so-called wobble mode (Fomin et al., 1994), in which the telescope points with an offset of 0.4° to the Crab Nebula position, alternating between two opposite pointing positions on either side of the target location. In this way, we simultaneously measure the signal and background events by selecting different regions in the sky during the analysis.

Out of all the observations gathered with a total duration of 57.2 hours, we selected good-quality data. First, to have the lowest possible energy threshold for gamma rays (aiming at 20 GeV), we select data taken with low zenith angles (below 35°) and under dark sky conditions, assuming that the moon was below the horizon. These two constraints left us with 48.0 hours of data. Second, we keep observations taken with good atmospheric conditions. Non-optimal weather, like variable atmospheric transmission, affects the trigger rate of sky events collected. Currently, there is no monitoring of atmospheric conditions that could be used for excluding runs not taken in good weather conditions. Hence we have to look for another proxy. The more straightforward candidate would be the rate of shower events. However, during the commissioning phase, there were frequent modifications in the trigger settings of the camera. Several trigger configurations and algorithms to dynamically modify the trigger’s settings in the presence of stars in the field of view were tested, causing the LST-1 not to have a stable trigger threshold. After these tests, the current trigger settings were fixed in August 2021. Therefore the trigger rate cannot be used as a gauge of acceptable atmospheric conditions for the entire data set. Instead, we have considered other parameters that do not depend on the trigger threshold, which is variable due to the changing trigger settings, to eliminate outliers that correspond to poor-quality data. For this purpose, we define two additional conditions computed from showers well above the threshold, in order to ensure the stability of the sample taking into account the charge distribution in the camera. One is the rate of pixels with a charge greater than 30 p.e. (averaged over the whole camera), and the other is the rate of sky events with intensity between 80 and 120 p.e. (R_{80-120}). We filter out the runs for which these two quantities (averaged over each run) do not fulfill the conditions¹ $pixel_rate_{q>30} > 4.5$ Hz and $R_{80-120} > 800$ Hz. After this rate-based quality selection, we ended up with 117 runs, typically 20 minutes each, taken over 34 nights. The total elapsed time after data quality selection is 35.9 hours, which remains 34.2 hours of livetime if we take into account that the dead time² is about 4.7% of the total elapsed observation time.

The distribution of the intensity (sum of the charge of the pixels surviving the image cleaning) of shower events from the Crab data sample is displayed in Fig. 5.1. If we select images with an intensity above 80 p.e., their rates in the selected runs are stable within 20%. The remaining spread is likely related to the differences in zenith angles (spanning from 6° to 35°). On the contrary, below 80 p.e., the low-intensity

¹We note that these values are somewhat arbitrary, aiming to remove clear outliers.

²Estimated based on the distribution of time differences of consecutive events as the minimum inter-arrival between two triggered events, which for the LST-1 is about $7\mu\text{s}$. See, for example, Fig. 4.1.

Figure 5.1: Run-by-run distribution of shower image intensity (sum of charge of pixels surviving the cleaning) distribution of the Crab Nebula data sample. The effect of fixing the trigger setting in August 2021 is noticeable near the threshold. Below 80 p.e., there is a spread in the intensity spectra of the shower events, mainly due to the variable trigger settings. Above around 80 p.e., the intensity spectra are however stable within a 20% difference, the differences being due to the spread in zenith angles of the observations. We also show the discarded observation runs due to the rate-based cuts described in the text, clearly not following the tendency of the selected runs. Credit: Abelardo Moralejo.

threshold has a more significant scatter due to the changing configuration of trigger settings in observations recorded before August 2021. These differences disappear once the trigger settings are frozen in August 2021, after which the collected data show a more stable and lower threshold. To achieve a good agreement between the simulations and the observed data, a trigger threshold equal to the lowest estimation for observed data, which corresponds to the data taken after August 2021, has been used as a MC configuration parameter. However, if we want to consider the whole data sample, we have to apply an intensity cut of 80 p.e. to make the analysis trigger equal. For data taken after August 2021 a lower cut-off of 50 p.e. is sufficient.

5.3 Monte Carlo simulations

The reconstruction of the energy, arrival direction, and type of the particle inducing the EASs depends on very detailed MC simulations of the shower development, Cherenkov light emission and its detection by the telescope. Knowing the properties of the primary

particle in the simulations allows us to train machine learning reconstruction models to be applied to reconstruct the observed data. An independent MC “test” sample reconstructed with the same trained algorithm is employed to derive the IRFs used to conduct the high-level analysis.

We used `CORSIKA v7.7100` (Heck et al., 1998) for shower development and `sim_telarray v2020-06-28` (Bernlöhr, 2008) for telescope response simulations, respectively³. They incorporate all the optical and electronic elements of the telescope involved in detecting the Cherenkov signal, including the trigger system and signal digitization, aiming to simulate data as similar as possible to the observations. Some simulation settings come from laboratory measurements, such as the reflectivity of the mirrors and the quantum efficiency of the photomultipliers. Nonetheless, various circumstances (e.g., non-optimal atmospheric conditions, different background light levels at night, dirt on the optical elements, and mirror degradation) can degrade the performance of the telescope. Therefore, to reflect the actual situation once the telescope is installed and operational, the initial configuration of the simulations must be finely tuned afterward. We present below the adjustments of the MC to the Crab Nebula observations carried out for this work, namely adjusting the PSF, the NSB, and overall light collection efficiency to the same conditions as in the observations used for this study.

First, actual measurements estimate that 80% of the PSF⁴ lie within a diameter of approximately 0.06° , smaller than a pixel size (0.1° diameter). During the period considered for this study, no significant change in the PSF was detected. Therefore, no further adjustments to the parameters of the simulations were necessary. Another adjustment consists in assimilating the background noise simulated in the MC data to the average background noise presented by the observations. The initial NSB level considered in the simulations corresponds to dark sky conditions, which yields a pixel-wise rate of 193 MHz of photoelectrons (p.e.) on average. Even selecting only dark data in this work, the Crab is nearby the Galactic plane. Therefore it is necessary to increase the noise with respect to that initially considered in the simulations, which is assumed for extragalactic surroundings. We estimate our observations’ background level through the interleaved pedestal events, which contain just noise. Since we only consider the Crab Nebula field and filter out data with higher noise levels, we add a single NSB tuning to the simulations describing our whole dataset, which is approximately an increase of about 70% over the value initially used. The additional Poissonian noise

³Low-level MC simulations are provided by the LST Collaboration and processed afterward by Thomas Vuillaume to train the Random Forest models and also calculate the IRFs.

⁴Daily monitored by a CCD that captures the reflected image of the stars on a screen placed in the focal plane.

is added pixel-wise to the MC data just before the image-cleaning step. The last modification deals with the actual optical efficiency of the telescope with respect to the one first assumed in the simulations. This tuning is described later when muons simulations are introduced for this purpose.

From this point onwards, MC data is processed analogously to the observed data (see Sect. 5.4 below) and used to train machine learning models for event reconstruction based on the Random Forest algorithm (Breiman, 2001). The “training” sample, which we used to train the Random Forest models, comprises showers initiated by gamma rays and protons. Besides, the “test” sample for the characterization of the instrument response is composed of only gamma-ray-induced EASs. Table 5.1 indicates the characteristics of each simulated data subset. We remark that to be capable of reconstructing sources inside the FoV, the training samples are simulated isotropically within a maximum angular radius of 2.5° for gamma-rays and 8° for protons. In contrast, gamma rays from the test sample are produced with an offset of 0.4° from the telescope pointing. This approach mimics how the standard observations are carried out in wobble mode for point-like sources.

Table 5.1: Settings of the LST-1 MC simulations.

	Gamma rays		Protons
	Train	Test	Train
Energy range ^a	5 GeV - 50 TeV		10 GeV - 100 TeV
Differential energy spectrum	$\propto E^{-2}$		$\propto E^{-2}$
Maximum impact parameter ^b	900 m	700 m	1500 m
Viewing cone ^c	2.5°	0.4°	8°

^aEnergy range for vertical incidence. These limits scale with the zenith distance (ZD) as $E_{\min, \max} \propto \cos^{-2.5}(\text{ZD})$ with a maximum energy of 200 TeV, regardless of the zenith angle. ^bThe maximum value corresponds to vertical showers. These distances scale as $\cos^{-0.5}(\text{ZD})$ for any other zenith distance. Every shower simulation is re-used ten times, randomly changing the telescopes’ location within a circle of radius equal to the impact parameter. ^cParticles are simulated isotropically within this angular distance centered at the telescope pointing. For the protons, this maximum angular offset varies as $\cos^{0.5}(\text{ZD})$ with the zenith angle.

In order to make the simulations as close as possible to the observed data, they have been performed in a grid of telescope-pointing directions covering the whole visible sky from the LST-1 site as much as possible. This approach aims to train the Random Forest models with proton and gamma-ray MC data produced at different sky positions. Hence, the pointing coordinates of the telescope are also a parameter used in reconstructing the primary particle properties, as the image parameters vary with the incoming direction of the showers. In this way, we decrease the systematic

error due to the difference between the telescope pointing in the observations and the directions in which the MC data are simulated. A different grid of sky directions has been designed for each MC sample (test and training).

On one side, the training sample was simulated along lines with fixed declination, drawing a path in alt-azimuth coordinates based on the telescope’s position. Following the length of these lines, we simulated the training MC in equidistant pointing directions. For the Crab Nebula analysis, we select the closest declination line ($\delta = 22.76^\circ$), with 19 pointing nodes along it as depicted in Fig. 5.2. Ideally, simulations covering the whole sky could be generated. However, besides the fact that only those directions close to the source trajectory would be used, simulating a more or less dense grid of directions in the sky is a trade-off between the computational expense of producing a large number of simulations and the performance gain to be achieved in the reconstruction. On the other hand, the MC gamma-ray test sample was simulated on a grid of positions in alt-azimuth coordinates. Particularly significant is the effect on the shape of the images of the air mass ($\propto \cos^{-1}(ZD)$) and the geomagnetic field. Therefore, the pointing directions for the simulation were conveniently chosen in a triangular lattice layout in the variables $\cos(ZD)$ and B_\perp/B . These test samples are used to produce IRFs. For each observation block of the Crab Nebula, filtered below $ZD = 35^\circ$, the node closest to the pointing direction of the telescope is used (two at each of the zenith angles, $ZD = 10^\circ, 23.6^\circ, 32^\circ$, with azimuth coordinate symmetrical to the direction of the magnetic North). Fig. 5.2 also illustrates these test MC sky directions. The greater the difference between the observations and the pointing nodes, the greater the systematic error in the IRFs, in turn, used for the sensitivity estimation, spectral, and timing analysis of the Crab Nebula. Some of the data runs were particularly affected by a more considerable discrepancy with respect to the MC test pointing direction, potentially causing instabilities in the results that will be discussed in the following sections.

In addition, we also simulated single muon events in vertical incidence to calibrate the telescope’s overall optical throughput (Gaug et al., 2019b). We produced them with a differential energy spectrum following a power law with a spectral index of -2.0 in the energy range between 8.4 GeV and 1 TeV. We limited the maximum impact distance to 9.8 m (80% of the dish radius) and the off-axis angle to 0.9° . These settings ensure the muon rings are well contained in the camera. The amount of Cherenkov light emitted by the muons is closely related to their initial energy and can be estimated by fitting the ringed shape of the muon footprint. Assessment of the total light efficiency of the telescope, which can be affected by mirror degradation or dirt covering their surface,

Figure 5.2: Pointing directions for simulating the training nodes (dots) and testing nodes (stars). Only those testing nodes $ZD < 35^\circ$ are used for this study. Credit: Thomas Vuillaume.

is performed by comparing simulated muons assuming different optical efficiencies of the telescope with the muons identified in the actual observations. For the analysis, we extract the total light intensity of good quality muon rings integrating over a range of $\pm 25\%$ of the estimated radius. By comparing the correlation between light intensity and ring radius between simulations and observations, we found that, on average, for the sample used in this work, we had to reduce by about 20% the telescope's light collection efficiency with respect to that initially assumed. Long-term run-to-run variations are $\pm 5\%$ (see Fig. 5.3, where the estimated optical efficiency for each data run is presented). For this reason, we do not use run-wise MC data tuning the optical efficiency accordingly for each observation, but just a single optical efficiency value averaged for the whole MC sample, which is another source of systematic errors.

Figure 5.3: Overall optical throughput run-by-run from muon analysis for the good-quality selected Crab Nebula data. Here, 100% level represents the optical efficiency set for the entire MC simulation dataset. Deviations are mainly due to the varying number of aligned mirrors and dust deposition on their surface. Especially remarkable is the efficiency drop after the *Cumbre Vieja* volcano eruption (dashed vertical line) in the last quarter of 2021, which recovered somewhat after a rainy period. Credit: Rubén López-Coto.

5.4 Analysis

The observed and simulated data have been analyzed using the LST-1 data-analysis library `cta-lstchain` described in Section 4.1. Heavily based on it, we use both `lstosa` (whose development is a substantial part of this thesis, described in Section 4.2) and `lstMCpipe` (Vuillaume et al., 2022; Garcia et al., 2022) to handle the processing of the observed data and MC simulation in the on-site computing facility at ORM (see section 1.6.1). To perform the high-level analysis and obtain light curve and spectra we employ the Gammapy library (Deil et al., 2017; Donath et al., 2022, see also Sect. 3.4.3). The IRFs used for the high-level analysis and to assess the performance of the telescope make use in turn of the `pyirf` library (Nöthe et al., 2022). In what follows, the analysis procedure (already outlined in Section 4.1) and specific settings used are

detailed focusing on the source-independent approach.

The signals recorded by each of the LST-1 pixels consist of 40 1-ns samples, dubbed waveforms. We apply the needed corrections and calibrate the raw waveforms following the procedure presented in Section 4.1.1. Next, the **signal extraction** is performed by integrating the charge of the calibrated waveforms in an 8 ns time window centered around the waveform peak, using the so-called *LocalPeakWindowSum* method. The number of photo-electrons corresponding to the integrated charge is then obtained using conversion factors calculated from dedicated calibration runs, as described in Section 4.1.1. The event arrival time is also derived by averaging the time of each sample weighted with their charges.

After the signal extraction is performed, we clean the image to keep mainly the information coming from the Cherenkov signal of the shower and filter out the rest of the background noise. This **image cleaning** is performed using the so-called *tail-cut* method (Lessard et al., 2001), which assumes two-level “picture” and “boundary” thresholds of 8 and 4 p.e., respectively. On top of that, there are additional considerations to fine-tune the pixel selection. In order to deal with stars in the field of view, for those pixels already above 8 p.e., the picture threshold is raised as $\langle Q_{\text{ped}} \rangle + 2.5 \cdot \sigma_{Q_{\text{ped}}}$, to account for noisy pixels, based on the charge distribution of the interleaved pedestal events. $\langle Q_{\text{ped}} \rangle$ and $\sigma_{Q_{\text{ped}}}$ are the average and standard deviation of the charge values from interleaved pedestal events, and they are calculated every few seconds⁵. Pixels with more than two neighbors above the picture threshold comprise the “core” of the image. Those contiguous to the core ones and whose charge is above the boundary threshold are also kept as part of the cleaned image. Since pixels with signal from showers are expected to arrive close in time, an additional requirement assures that we keep only islands of pixels whose signal arrival time lies within a 2-ns window with respect to their closest neighbors. A final condition deals with a problem suffered during the commissioning phase of the telescope by some observations used in this work. On some occasions, several dish mirrors were out of focus, originating duplicated spurious images of less intensity accompanying the original image. Only those pixels with a charge greater than 3% of the charge peak in the image are selected to discard such fake islands. The effectiveness of the cleaning procedure has been proven with interleaved pedestals containing only noise. The probability of survival after image cleaning for pixels in an interleaved event, is the same as the one for an island consisting of pixels

⁵This treatment of the stars in the FoV makes it possible to use simplified MC data with just added Poissonian noise uniformly across the camera that corresponds to the NSB level estimated from the Crab Nebula observations as indicated above, but not simulating the effect of stars.

containing only noise in a Cherenkov event. This probability is only a few percent after applying the cleaning method described above to our dataset taken in dark conditions.

Next, images with only surviving pixels are **parameterized** following the approach by Hillas (1985) described in Section 3.1.1 (see Fig. 3.3). Calculated parameters are used to **train Random Forest models** to reconstruct the attributes of the primary particle inducing the shower: its direction, energy, and the probability (nicknamed *gammaness*) of being a gamma ray rather than a hadron. The different models employed for inferring each of the three characteristics are described in Section 4.1.2. For the direction reconstruction, we rely on the *disp* method described in Lessard et al. (2001). A Random Forest regressor is trained to reconstruct the norm of *disp* (*disp_norm*), i.e., the distance between the image centroid and the point along the semi-major axis closest to the actual source position in the camera. The reconstruction of the *disp_norm* is degenerate because there are two possible reconstructed positions on each side of the ellipse. Therefore a second classifier model is used to choose between one of the two sides (*disp_sign*). A third Random Forest regressor is trained for the reconstruction of the logarithm of the true energy, giving rise to a new parameter *log_reco_energy*. Finally, we train another classifier model fed with proton- and gamma-ray-based simulated data for the particle classification. Table 5.2 summarizes the image parameters used for each model. Fig. 5.4 depicts the relative importance of the training parameters for each model. Particularly remarkable is the importance of temporal information in the direction and energy reconstruction, which is expected in cases with a single telescope, as reported in Aliu et al. (2009). Besides, we note the significant implication of the altitude pointing of the telescope in the energy reconstruction.

In addition, we have estimated the threshold energy achieved in the analysis, which is especially significant for LST-type telescopes since, within CTA, they are targeted for the lowest energies. The energy threshold is commonly estimated from the peak of the true energy distribution of events, which are weighted in each bin of energy by the Crab Nebula spectrum from Aleksić et al. (2015c). Such a distribution can be obtained after each analysis step and, in turn, gamma-ray-like event selection. Fig. 5.5 compiles these distributions, showing a threshold of about 20 GeV for triggered events, which raises somewhat to roughly 30 GeV post-analysis and selection of well-reconstructed gamma rays. The lower the energy, the larger the rate of events lost in each analysis step. This loss is due to poor reconstruction of the direction of events at the lowest energies. Likewise, the discriminating power of background events in single telescope analysis is also worse at low energies. We remark that the reconstruction of events is greatly improved in the stereoscopic case when more telescopes come into play. For this

Parameter	Direction reconstruction	Energy reconstruction	Particle classification
<i>log_intensity</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>width</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>length</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>x</i>	☐	☑	☑
<i>y</i>	☐	☑	☑
<i>wl</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>skewness</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>kurtosis</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>time_gradient</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>leakage_intensity_width_2</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>az_tel</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>alt_tel</i>	☑	☑	☑
<i>log_reco_energy</i>	☐	☐	☑
<i>reco_disp_norm</i>	☐	☐	☑
<i>reco_disp_sign</i>	☐	☐	☑

Table 5.2: Image parameters used (ticked boxes) as input for training the Random Forest models. The particle classifier model uses the output from the other two reconstructions.

Figure 5.4: Importance in relative terms of the features used to train each Random Forest model for the source-independent analysis. Credit: Thomas Vuillaume.

reason, even with a lower energy threshold and a larger mirror dish, the performance of a single LST in its energy range of operation is not better than the current generation of IACTs.

Figure 5.5: True energy distribution for simulated gamma rays with $ZD = 10^\circ$ after each subsequent analysis step and selection cuts (source-independent approach). The peak of the distributions indicates the energy threshold $\simeq 20$ GeV for the triggered events and $\simeq 30$ GeV after analysis and gamma-ray event filtering. The rate of surviving events after each stage is also noted. Credit: Abelardo Moralejo.

The trained models are then applied to the gamma-ray MC test samples in each simulated sky direction described above (see Fig. 5.2) to produce the IRFs of the LST-1. They serve two purposes: evaluating the telescope performance (reported in Section 5.6) and being further used for higher-level analyses to obtain SED and light curve (see Sect. 5.7).

One final remark regarding the source-independent analysis approach followed here. Single-telescope analysis suffers from poor direction reconstruction if compared with the gain of the stereoscopic analysis when more telescopes are in place. This fact is especially critical at low energies where angular reconstruction worsens significantly in the monoscopic case. This problem can be partly overcome by adopting the source-dependent analysis approach, in which it is assumed a priori that all gamma rays come from the target position for point source cases. In this analysis, we use the key parameter *dist*, defined as the distance between the shower image's centroid and

the source’s position in the camera. The usage of this parameter can improve the energy reconstruction and identification of gamma rays over the isotropic cosmic-ray background.

Although this method is employed in this work analogously to the source-independent analysis approach, it is out of this thesis’s scope. We only mentioned it for comparison purposes between the two procedures in the following sections. Alternatively to the *theta* angle employed in the source-independent analysis for calculating the excess counts, the source-dependent method uses instead the *alpha* angle, which is the angle between the major axis of the cascade and the direction formed between the centroid of the cascade and the expected position of the target. IRFs for the source-dependent analysis are comparable to those of the source-independent method. The main disparity appears below 50 GeV, where in the case of the source-dependent one, the effective area is 40% larger, and the energy resolution is significantly better.

5.5 Comparison between simulations and observations

In this section, we compare the distributions of image parameters from both MC simulated and observed data for the source-independent analysis. Firstly, the comparison of the θ^2 distribution from the gamma-ray excess computed from both samples is shown in Fig. 5.6, splitting the data into four *intensity* bins. MC distributions were weighted following the log-parabola function fitted for the Crab Nebula SED in [Aleksić et al. \(2015c\)](#) so that the distribution of gamma-ray energies in simulations is similar to the one from observations.

The excess of gamma rays coming from the direction around the Crab Nebula was estimated by subtracting the number of gamma rays coming from the on-source region (with a specific angular size) and the gamma-ray count performed in a control off-source region diametrically opposed simultaneously from the same observation runs. Subtraction can be done straightforwardly as both regions have the same acceptance for background events. This technique is possible since the observations were carried out in wobble pointing mode with 0.4° offset between the center of the field of view and the position of the Crab Nebula (see Sect. 5.2). Therefore the on- and off-source regions are separated by 0.8° . To reduce the background from hadronic events, we apply a cut in gammaness (noted in each panel of Fig. 5.6) that keeps roughly 80% of gamma-ray events in each intensity bin. We also note that due to the poorer angular reconstruction at the lowest energies (range of lower intensities, whose events are centered at a *true*

energy of $\simeq 30$ GeV), the tail of the angular distribution of gamma rays goes beyond the center of the FoV. Therefore, background events from the off-source region contaminate it (hence the need for the correction represented in the upper-left panel of Fig. 5.6). On the contrary, angular distributions exhibit a better direction reconstruction (narrower distribution) as we consider events with larger intensity.

A good agreement between simulated and observed distributions was found. We note, however, that the angular distribution of on-source gamma-ray excess for the MC data is slightly pickier than that of the observed Crab Nebula excess. This discrepancy increases with the intensity values. It might be due to an underestimation of the LST-1 PSF in the simulations or a possible mispointing not adequately corrected in the observations. In any case, the disparity is way below the angular resolution achieved with the LST-1.

Figure 5.6: Comparison of θ^2 distribution from gamma-ray excess found in simulations and Crab Nebula observations. MC distributions are normalized to match the distributions from observed data. Credit: Abelardo Moralejo.

The same comparison exercise is done for the *gammaness* parameter. The distributions in the same four ranges of intensities are plotted in Fig. 5.7. In this case, we apply an angular cut in θ in each range to keep those gamma rays likely coming from

the source. Cuts were chosen to contain 90% of the excess events, which are indicated in each panel of Fig. 5.7. The distributions of the gamma-ray excess were calculated the same way as for the θ^2 distributions (i.e., the difference between the on-source and anti-source regions with the same angular cut). The *gammaness* distributions of the background events are also represented in Fig. 5.7, showing the improvement in the discrimination capability between gamma rays and hadrons of the *gammaness* parameter as the images get brighter. Again, the agreement between the *gammaness* distributions derived from MC simulations and observed data is excellent, making IRFs calculated from MC data reliable even when tight gamma-ray cuts (low cut efficiency) are not applied. We note that at the lowest energies, the particle classification is a complex issue, and the angular resolution is poor (see Sect. 5.6) as expected from a single telescope near the threshold. Both facts make the uncertainty in the background normalization a necessary aspect to consider at low energies. Stereo reconstruction will improve the background rejection.

The same applies for the rest of the image parameters as can be seen in Fig. 5.8 for two of the most meaningful image parameters used for Random Forest models training, *length* and *width*. In order not to bias the comparison towards the selection of gamma-ray-like events, we do not apply any cut in the *gammaness* parameter in these last comparisons.

5.6 Performance metrics

We gather here the figures of merit that assess the performance of the telescope. The metrics typically considered to evaluate the detection capability of an IACT and how well it reconstructs the angular direction and the energy of the primary gamma rays are effective collection area, angular and energy resolution, all derived from the gamma-ray MC test sample as a function of *true* energy for several configurations. For the event selection, we first applied a global *intensity* cut to keep only those above 50 p.e. as explained in Section 5.2. Next, we apply an energy-dependent cut in *gammaness* to keep a given percentage of gamma rays in a given bin of reconstructed energy (that we refer to as gamma-ray efficiency). Then, for the collection area and energy resolution computation, to this selected gamma-ray event candidates, another energy-dependent θ cut is applied such a given percentage of the events with the best direction reconstruction survive in each reconstructed energy bin. In this work, we consider the nominal selection cut with a 70% gamma-ray efficiency for both parameters *gammaness* and θ , which will be used for calculating the Crab Nebula spectrum and light curve in

Figure 5.7: Comparison of *gammaness* distribution from gamma-ray excess found in simulations and Crab Nebula observations. MC distributions are normalized to match the distributions from observed data. For better visualization, the background rates from the off-source position in the lower intensity bins are down-scaled by 50. Credit: Abelardo Moralejo.

Figure 5.8: *Length* and *width* distributions for events with *intensities* between 800 and 3200 p.e., obtained from MC simulations and Crab Nebula gamma-ray excess events. For comparison, we also depict the distribution of the off-source events scaled down for easier comparison. No *gammaness* cut was applied. Credit: Abelardo Moralejo.

Section 5.7. Fig. 5.9 shows the three instrument responses for simulated gamma rays at a zenith angle of 10° and several gamma-ray efficiencies, from soft to hard ones. On the contrary, in Fig. 5.10, IRFs are shown for several zenith angles⁶ with the 70% gamma-ray selection efficiency.

The **effective collection area** is computed as the relation between observed gamma rays after analysis selection cuts and the number of gamma rays simulated multiplied by the area orthogonal to the direction of incidence on which we uniformly generated the MC gamma rays⁷. This quantity depends on the gamma-ray energy, the zenith angle of their incoming direction and the selection cuts applied to reject background events, as shown in Figs. 5.9 and 5.10 (mid panel). Below ~ 100 GeV down to the threshold, the effective area decreases rapidly. In contrast, its value saturates at the highest energies. Regarding the dependence on the selection cut efficiency, the overall trend of the effective area is to increase as high-efficiency looser cuts are applied as more gamma rays end up in the final sample. The effect of the zenith angle is that, while at the lowest range of energies, the collection area is greater for low zenith angle observations, at the high energies, the fact of having large-zenith angle observations increases the collection area.

The **angular resolution** θ_{68} is expressed as the angle containing 68% of the reconstructed gamma rays relative to their actual direction, θ . The top panels of Figs. 5.9 and 5.10 show that angular resolution is worst near the energy threshold ($\gtrsim 0.4^\circ$) as expected from a monoscopic analysis and improves as energy increases ($\simeq 0.2^\circ$ at several hundreds of GeV depending on the selection cut efficiency). It also improves for tighter cuts for a given zenith distance. A related key parameter used to evaluate the ability of the telescope to disentangle two close point-like sources is the gamma-ray PSF. Its core mainly comprises events whose direction is adequately determined, while the tail of the distribution, especially at low energies, is composed of events whose head-tail direction reconstruction is reversed.

The **energy resolution** represents the value of the relative difference between the reconstructed (E_R) and the true energy (E_T),

$$|\Delta E|/E_T = |E_R - E_T|/E_T,$$

for which 68% of the reconstructed gamma rays are contained. Besides, it is also commonly used the energy bias, which is calculated as the median of the previous

⁶From the simulated samples at each of the MC pointing nodes, close to the zenith angles from those of the Crab data sample as described in Section 5.3.

⁷Approximation only valid when this area is large enough so the number of observed events outside it is negligible.

Figure 5.9: Angular resolution (top), effective area (middle), and energy resolution and bias (bottom) as a function of the *true* energy for $ZD = 10^\circ$ and three efficiencies of gamma-ray event selection. Credit: Thomas Vuillaume.

Figure 5.10: Angular resolution (top), effective area (middle) and energy resolution and bias (bottom) as a function of the true energy for a gamma-ray efficiency of 70% and assuming several zenith angles corresponding to the pointing nodes of the gamma-ray MC test sample. Credit: Thomas Vuillaume.

expression in each bin of true energy. Bottom panels of Figs. 5.9 and 5.10 plot these quantities for observing conditions and analysis cuts. Again, the best energy resolution ($\lesssim 20\%$) is achieved at the highest energies starting from a few hundred GeV. In contrast, it worsens at the lowest energies, where an artifact in the monotonic trend shows up, presumably originated by the fluctuations in the energy-dependent gammaness selection cuts near the threshold. Furthermore, the harder the selection cuts applied (less efficiency of the cuts), the better the resolution. The improvement in the resolution, both angular and energy, with tighter cuts, rejects better the background events, but on the other hand, fewer gamma-ray events are selected, and in turn, the collection efficiency shrinks, as depicted in Fig. 5.9. Although not shown here, the source-dependent analysis presents better energy resolution near the energy threshold than the source-independent approach.

The last figure of merit we obtained is **differential flux sensitivity**, defined as the minimum flux that an instrument can detect from a point-like source with $5\text{-}\sigma$ significance in 50 hours of observation⁸. We also require the detection of at least ten gamma rays per energy bin and a signal-to-noise ratio greater than 5%. The sensitivity was evaluated entirely from Crab observations. For calculating the differential flux, we use five off-source regions to estimate the background. We performed a cut optimization for gamma-ray selection to obtain the best sensitivity in each bin of reconstructed energy by scanning pairs of angular and gammaness cuts. The resulting curves are displayed in Fig. 5.11, where the bands represent the total uncertainty assuming a 1% systematic uncertainty in the background normalization. At low energies, requiring the background to be less than 5% of the signal significantly penalizes sensitivity. This energy range, limited by the systematic uncertainty in the background normalization, is significant for less intense sources whose spectrum lies near the LST-1 energy threshold. Fig. 5.11 shows the sensitivity curve without imposing such a condition. We emphasize, however, that a higher systematic uncertainty affects the sensitivity at these energies, as we will see in Section 5.7.

The sensitivity achieved by both analyses (source-dependent and source-independent) is comparable over the whole energy range. However, the former has better resolution at energies close to the threshold. The best differential sensitivity ($\simeq 2.5\%$ C.U.) is reached at about 500 GeV. For comparison, the sensitivity of the two MAGIC telescopes is 1.5 times better than that of LST-1 on average over the whole energy range in which they overlap due to, as anticipated, the advantage of the stereo reconstruction. A

⁸See also Sect. 1.6 for a description of the sensitivity foreseen for the two arrays of the future CTAO.

Figure 5.11: LST-1 differential flux sensitivity in units of Crab Nebula flux (C.U.) as a function of the reconstructed energy in 50 h of observing. Hatched bands are calculated without assuming the condition $S/N > 5\%$ relevant only at the lowest energies. We plot the MAGIC sensitivity curve (Aleksić et al., 2016) for reference. Credit: Rubén López-Coto.

single telescope with a bigger dish is usually not enough to outperform a two-telescope system. Note, however, that LST-1 has a lower energy threshold than MAGIC operating in stereo with standard digital trigger⁹ (Aleksić et al., 2016). The difference in sensitivities between the two instruments decreases with energy until their sensitivity becomes comparable in the range of a few TeV. As a side note, we remark that using five off-source regions for calculating the differential flux, even if it reduces the systematic uncertainty of the background estimation, is not feasible in the low-energy regime where direction reconstruction is inferior. For this reason, we use one off-source region for the Crab Nebula calculation in Section 5.7.

⁹We note that the new MAGIC analog trigger, *Sum-Trigger-II*, can lower the trigger threshold (Dazzi et al., 2021).

5.7 Crab Nebula spectrum and light curve

The bright and persistent gamma-ray emission of the Crab Nebula is assumed to be stable in the VHE regime, which makes it a standard candle and calibration source for instruments operating in such an energy band. Therefore, another way to probe the performance of the telescope is by comparing the SED of the gamma-ray emission from the Crab Nebula and its light curve with values reported in the literature. We have obtained both high-level science products using Gammapy v0.20.1 (Donath et al., 2022) from observations of the Crab Nebula conducted during the commissioning phase of LST-1 (see description in Section 5.2). Although we produced the SED and light curve for the two analysis approaches, this thesis focuses only on the source-independent-based results.

Starting from the curated quality-selected dataset described in Section 5.2, the events selected for this purpose are those with an intensity greater than 80 p.e. to build the spectrum of the entire dataset and 50 p.e. to produce it, separately, only from August 2021 onwards. These intensity cuts aim to decrease discrepancies between the MC and observed data at the lowest energies near the threshold, as explained in Section 5.2. Next, we select candidate gamma-ray events by applying energy-dependent gammaness and theta cuts. As a reference, the cuts we employ have a 70% efficiency in selecting gamma-ray-type events in each bin of reconstructed energy using the MC sample (see Fig. 5.12). To avoid selecting evident non-gamma-ray events at the lowest energies, where reconstruction is significantly worst, we set limits to the efficiency selection, a maximum gamma-ray selection efficiency of 0.95 for the gammaness and a maximum θ value of 0.32° , which corresponds to $\theta^2 < 0.1(^{\circ})^2$. How loose or tight we set the selection cuts entails a trade-off between the statistical and systematic uncertainties. Soft cuts rely less on a perfect control of systematic uncertainties and keep more gamma-rays at the cost of also accepting more background. On the other hand, harder cuts produce purer signals but need good control of the systematic effects.

Thanks to the use of observations in wobble mode, we are capable of simultaneously estimating the signal (on-source events) and background (off-source events) within the same field of view using a single control off-position mirrored to the expected source location (“antisource”). We keep respectively those events within a certain angular distance (dependent on the gamma-ray energy) from the assumed positions of the source and the reflected “antisource”. The usage of a single reflected background region for the analysis of the Crab Nebula is due to the poor angular reconstruction at the lowest energies in the monoscopic case. Having more off-regions would provoke

Figure 5.12: Energy-dependent *gammaness* and θ cuts based on 70% gamma-ray selection efficiency. Blue lines correspond to the cuts in each data run, while orange lines are the median values in each reconstructed energy bin. The dotted line indicates the maximum values for the cuts.

they would be closer to the on-source region. Therefore, since the Crab Nebula is such a bright source, gamma-ray events that certainly come from it although with misidentified angular reconstruction would contaminate the off regions more easily. The eventual outcome would be increased systematic uncertainty due to background estimation.

With the knowledge of the response functions of the LST-1 discussed above, we then performed a forward-folding Poissonian likelihood fit (see description in [Piron, F. et al., 2001](#); [de Naurois, 2000](#)) in the energy range 50 GeV - 30 TeV¹⁰ assuming a differential energy spectrum of gamma rays with log-parabolic shape:

$$d\phi/dE = f_0 \cdot (E/E_0)^{-\alpha-\beta \cdot \ln(E/E_0)} [\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{TeV}^{-1}],$$

where $E_0 = 400$ GeV was chosen near to the *pivot* energy for which spectral parameters are less correlated between them. The *pivot* energy can be estimated analytically when assuming a power-law function, as described by Eq. (1) in [Abdo et al. \(2009b\)](#). In our case, that is not applicable, but we can instead derive the *pivot* energy numerically by checking for which normalization energy the relative error in flux amplitude is smallest or, analogously, the correlation values between model parameters are minimum. The result of this check can be seen in Fig. 5.13. With this method, the value is 312 GeV, hence a better choice for the model fit would be a rounded decorrelation energy of 300 GeV.

¹⁰For direct comparison to the Crab Nebula spectrum reported by MAGIC ([Aleksić et al., 2015c](#)).

Figure 5.13: Relative error in flux normalization as a function of the normalization energy (E_0) assuming a log-parabola model. *Pivot* energy is the value for which the relative error in flux normalization is minimum, in this case, $E \simeq 312$ GeV (dotted line).

The resulting parameters of the best fit are indicated in Table 5.3 and the correlation between them (covariance matrix) is shown in Table 5.4. Fig. 5.14 shows the SED for the entire dataset. For reference, we show the Crab Nebula SED from MAGIC (Aleksić et al., 2015c) in the same energy range as LST-1 and *Fermi*-LAT (Arakawa et al., 2020) overlapping at the lowest energies, near the LST-1 threshold. Spectral points are also determined for the LST-1 SED using the `FluxPointEstimator` functionality from Gammapy, which fits the amplitude of the spectral model in each energy bin starting from the best-fit model previously computed. We have used 8 bins per decade logarithmically spaced along the energy range used previously in the forward-folding fit. This binning intends to be consistent with the average energy resolution of the LST-1. Additionally, we perform a joint fit for the *Fermi*-LAT and LST-1 datasets assuming again a log-parabolic parameterization from 2 GeV to 2 TeV. The result is presented in Fig. 5.14. The observed bump in the SED is typically described as inverse Compton emission, peaking at around 60 GeV as estimated from the resulting joint best fit model. Resulting spectral parameters from this fit are shown in Table 5.3.

Fit	f_0 [$\text{TeV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$]	E_0 [GeV]	α	β	$-2\log\mathcal{L}$
LST-1	$(3.05 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-10}$	400	2.25 ± 0.01	0.114 ± 0.006	48.5
<i>Fermi</i> -LAT & LST-1	$(5.95 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-9}$	100	2.06 ± 0.01	0.069 ± 0.002	61.4

Table 5.3: Spectral parameters for the source-independent analysis of the Crab Nebula in the energy range 50 GeV-30 TeV (LST-1 solo fit) and 2 GeV-2 TeV (*Fermi*-LAT and LST-1 joint fit). The last column indicates the test statistic value from the forward-folding log-likelihood fit.

	f_0	E_0	α	β
f_0	1.00	-	-0.18	0.54
E_0	-	-	-	-
α	-0.18	-	1.00	-0.51
β	0.54	-	-0.51	1.00

Table 5.4: Covariance matrix for the best-fit parameters indicated in Table 5.3 for the LST-1 solo fit.

As only statistical uncertainties are being considered and systematic uncertainties, very relevant especially near the threshold, are not taken into account, the resulting statistics from this fit are not really meaningful.

To check how the best-fit model SED changes when applying different gamma-ray selection efficiencies, we obtained the SED for different combinations of efficiencies for *gammaness* (40%, 70%, 90%) and θ (70%, 90%) cuts. We do not recommend harder angular cuts than 70% in θ due to the mismatch in the angular distribution of reconstructed events between MC simulated and observed data sets (see discussion in Section 5.5). This estimation is represented as the hatched band, comprising all the variations in the SED of the different cut efficiencies, in Fig. 5.14.

At the lowest energies, the first spectral points significantly differ from the best-fit model, as shown in Fig. 5.14. This discrepancy cannot be solely accounted for with statistical uncertainty near the threshold. To explain this difference, we checked how significant is the effect of a wrong evaluation of background normalization, showing that, at the lowest energies, systematic uncertainty in background normalization is dominant over the statistical error. On the ground that both on-source and off-region have the same acceptance due to wobble mode observations, we show the effect of a small change in the background estimation, increasing it by 1%, over the SED calculation at the lowest energies (see open markers in Fig. 5.14). Even such a slight variation in the background normalization can substantially change the SED determination. We remark that the likelihood analysis method implemented in Gammapy currently only

Figure 5.14: LST-1 spectral energy distribution for the entire Crab Nebula dataset (34.2 h livetime) obtained with the source-independent analysis approach. Flux points and best-fit model correspond to the dataset with energy-dependent with 70% gamma-ray efficiency in *gammaness* and θ cuts. Gray open markers represent the SED calculated by increasing the background normalization by 1% as a test to show the large impact that such a small systematic error has, overshooting the statistical uncertainty at the lowest energies. The hatched band encompasses the effect of using different efficiency cuts (40% to 90% for the *gammaness* cut, and 70% to 90% for the θ cut). We also show the Crab Nebula SED from MAGIC (Aleksić et al., 2015c) and *Fermi*-LAT (Arakawa et al., 2020) for reference. To show the smooth connection of the LST-1 spectrum with that of *Fermi*-LAT, we show the joint fit assuming a log-parabola model as a dotted line with the corresponding statistical uncertainty band. The bottom panel shows the residuals with respect to the joint fit to *Fermi*-LAT and LST-1 spectra.

relies on statistical uncertainties but does not consider any systematic uncertainty as the one just described. Considering both effects, systematics in the background estimation and a wide range of cut efficiencies, LST-1 SED is compatible with that of *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC telescopes. We note that the contribution of gamma rays from the pulsar emission is about 10% at 30 GeV (Bühler and Blandford, 2014) going down very quickly at higher energies. Thus, its effect is expected to be minor in the

overall emission, dominated by the nebula, even near the LST-1 energy threshold. In addition, Fig. 5.15 shows the smooth link of the LST-1 spectrum to that measured by LHAASO (LHAASO Collaboration et al., 2021).

Figure 5.15: Crab Nebula spectrum as measured by *Fermi*-LAT (Arakawa et al., 2020), LST-1 and LHAASO (LHAASO Collaboration et al., 2021) showing the smooth connection among the three instruments in the overlapping LST-1 energy range.

To investigate the behavior after establishing the current trigger settings in August 2021, therefore having a more stable threshold, we extracted the SED separately for the pre- and post-August 2021 data sets (25.4 h and 8.8 h livetime, respectively). The comparison of both SEDs is shown in Fig. 5.16. Most of the post-August sample was collected after the interruption of data-taking due to the Cumbre Vieja volcano eruption in La Palma between September 19th and December 13th 2021. The post-August 2021 sample yields a slightly lower flux, likely due to the lower optical throughput (see details on muon analysis in section 5.5). With softer gamma-ray selection cuts, the SED obtained from both subsets is compatible, though (see the hatched blue band on Fig. 5.16).

We also obtained the light curve with 1-day binning above 100 GeV, assuming a log-parabola function (see Fig. 5.17). Flux points from the light curve are fitted to a constant value of

$$F_{>100 \text{ GeV}} = (4.95 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

Figure 5.16: Comparison of Crab Nebula SED before and after trigger setting updates (August 2021). The livetime of the data sample until and after August 2021 is 25.4 h and 8.8 h, respectively. We use a coarser binning due to the poorer statistics. We applied energy-dependent *gammaness* and angular cuts with a 70% gamma efficiency. Additionally, for the different observing periods, we filter out low-intensity events (below 80 p.e. before August 2021 and below 50 p.e. after August 2021). The best fit to a log-parabola model for both data samples and corresponding statistical error bands are shown. The hatched region represents the effect of varying the selection cut efficiencies for the data sample taken after August 2021.

with $\chi^2/N_{dof} = 119.2/33 \approx 3.6$ (P-value= 1×10^{-11}). Considering only the statistical uncertainties, this value is incompatible with the steady-flux hypothesis. We have calculated that additional 6% systematic uncertainty in the flux values summed quadratically to the statistical uncertainty would make the light curve compatible with the constant flux (P-value $\simeq 0.5$). This estimate seems reasonable as we have employed a unique set of IRFs depending only on the zenith angles, but not tailored to each data run nor observing night to take into account the different observation conditions more accurately. Averaged LST-1 integral flux above 100 GeV is about 4% greater than the value calculated from MAGIC observations (Aleksić et al., 2015c) integrating the same energy range.

Another side result from the LST-1 performance study is the detection of the pulsation of the Crab pulsar. Although beyond the scope of this thesis, for completion, the phaseogram of the Crab pulsar obtained from this study is also included (see Fig. 5.18). This result is significant because it validates the accuracy and precision (below

Figure 5.17: Crab Nebula 1-day binned light curve above 100 GeV for the source-independent analysis. Weighted-averaged flux is depicted as a dash-dotted line representing the fit to constant flux. For reference, we also indicate the integral flux in the same energy range calculated from the log parabola model reported in [Aleksić et al. \(2015c\)](#) (dashed line). The black error bars of the flux points correspond only to statistical uncertainties. In gray, error bars are incremented quadratically, assuming a 5.8% systematic uncertainty in each light-curve individual point.

0.1 ms) of the event timestamps needed for pulsar analyses, calculated as explained in Section [4.1.3](#).

5.8 Conclusions

We have presented the first study of the single-telescope performance of the LST-1 based on MC simulations and data from Crab Nebula observations carried out during the commissioning phase of the instrument (Section [5.2](#)). For that purpose, we adjusted the simulations according to the observed data achieving an excellent agreement between them (Section [5.5](#)), which is essential to obtain a satisfactory comprehension of

Figure 5.18: Phaseogram of the Crab pulsar from LST-1 observations, proof that the LST-1 timestamps are accurate and precise enough for pulsar analyses. The significance of the detection of both pulses is also reported. Credit: Rubén López-Coto.

its performance.

First, we have found that the optical throughput of the telescope was stable within $\pm 5\%$, as unveiled by the muon analysis during the observing period of one and a half years covered by this study (from November 2020 to March 2022). Noteworthy to mention that the eruption of a nearby volcano, which halted the telescope operation for three months, did not cause a considerable decline in the optical light efficiency (Section 5.3). The trigger threshold was not definitively established until August 2021, when the current trigger settings were frozen, being about 20 GeV after that. The energy analysis threshold of the LST-1 is about 30 GeV. Hence it is sensitive down to the energies for which it was designed.

We have employed source-dependent and source-independent analyses, the latter being the standard method to be used in the analysis of the CTA data. The angular resolution achieved with the source-independent analysis is approximately 0.17° above 1 TeV for a gamma-ray selection efficiency of 70%, which we used for the spectrum and light curve calculation. Near the threshold, the angular resolution worsens to about 0.4° . The energy resolution is around 20% above 300 GeV and worsens to 50% near the energy threshold. The source-dependent analysis technique makes the difference in this energy range, achieving a better energy resolution of 30%.

The estimated differential sensitivity for 50 hours of observation is about 1.5 times worse on average than the sensitivity of the MAGIC telescopes. Although the LST-1 has a lower energy threshold (larger collecting area and more performing camera), it is not competitive with telescopes operating in stereo mode. Both source-dependent and source-independent analyses provide comparable sensitivity over the entire energy range of the LST-1, with the source-dependent method being marginally better in the case of the source-dependent method near the instrument’s energy threshold.

Finally, the spectra of the Crab Nebula we computed with the two analysis types are comparable. LST-1 SED is also consistent within statistical and systematic uncertainties with that reported by MAGIC (Aleksić et al., 2015c) and agrees well at low energies with that obtained by *Fermi*-LAT (Arakawa et al., 2020). At the lowest energies (below 100 GeV), the systematic uncertainty from the background normalization is especially noticeable. The light curve above 100 GeV also agrees with the value reported in the literature when systematic uncertainty is considered. The light curve is consistent with the steady flux hypothesis for the Crab Nebula when taking into account a relative systematic uncertainty of 5%. Moreover, these high-level results do not reveal any significant change in the telescope behavior before and after the volcano eruption. In addition, we have also obtained the phaseogram resolving the two pulses of the Crab Pulsar, proving again the low energy threshold that LST-1 can reach and, as a side note, that the timing system of the LST-1 works well within 0.1-ms precision.

This work will serve as a benchmark and reference for any analysis performed on other sources observed by the LST-1 in the same standard conditions as the ones from the Crab sample used in this work. Other observation under different conditions, like higher zenith angles or higher NSB, needs further and dedicated studies. In this sense, a more detailed investigation of the systematic uncertainties of the LST-1 data analysis, which has only been mentioned in this work, is needed.

All the above considered, the LST-1 has stably performed as it was designed during its first years of operation within the systematics expected from an instrument of these characteristics due to non-optimal observation situations and typical aging. We conclude that the telescope is ready to produce scientific results.

Chapter 6

Multiwavelength study of the emission from the blazar 1ES 0647+250

This chapter presents the work done in the MAGIC collaboration within the extragalactic physics group along with Jorge Otero Santos, Daniela Dorner, David Paneque, and Vanda Fallah Ramazani, which resulted in a publication on the study of the emission from the blazar 1ES 0647+250 after 10-year multiwavelength monitoring ([MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2023](#)). My contribution focused on the analysis of the VHE gamma-ray data taken with the MAGIC telescopes obtaining the high-level results (significance of detection, spectra of different observing epochs, and overall light curve), and estimating the redshift through the spectrum of the gamma-ray emission measured by MAGIC telescopes and *Fermi*-LAT.

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the study and temporal and spectral characterization of the MWL emission from the blazar 1ES 0647+250. A work I have contributed to as one of the main authors, focusing on analyzing the VHE gamma-ray data, estimating the redshift of the source through the *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC spectra absorbed by the extragalactic background light (EBL), and finally contributing to the temporal analyses of the collected multi-instrument data.

The project started within the ToO MAGIC program, which triggers observations of sources potentially flaring alerted from other instruments. A flare at VHE was detected by MAGIC telescopes in 2019 [Mirzoyan \(2019b\)](#) following an alert from *Fermi*-LAT reporting an enhanced activity from 1ES 0647+250. This source had been monitored in the past by MAGIC soon after it started stereo operation. Afterward, some additional ToO observations were also carried out following alerts from different monitoring instruments. However, the MAGIC data were never published. Taking advantage of the interest from the recent flares, a workforce within MAGIC collaboration decided to compile all the data MAGIC took from 1ES 0647+250 over the last decade, analyzing them in a multiwavelength (MWL) context resulting in a publication ([MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2023](#)).

I have also contributed to analyzing MAGIC data from two other blazars: BL Lacertae and 1ES 1959+650. The projects that study these other sources plan to involve MWL data analysis and theoretical model of the broadband emission. The work in this regard is less advanced, sometimes because the analyses of the extensive data sets are rather intricate and more effort should be put into it, and sometimes because the projects are not scientifically interesting enough for publication. The work carried out in these two other projects is reported in [Appendix A](#).

With this MWL study on 1ES 0647+250 based on extensive long-term monitoring, we intend to characterize the variability at different timescales, looking for correlations between the multi-band emissions. In this context, as VHE is a young field, studies that monitor sources over long periods are few, and variability from blazar emission is not well understood yet. We also aim to model the broadband emission from several observing campaigns in which we found its emission in different states.

The BL Lac object 1ES 0647+250 located at R.A._{J2000} 6^h50^m46.5^s, Dec._{J2000} 25°3′0″ ([Healey et al., 2007](#)) was cataloged as a high-synchrotron peaked BL Lac object (HBL) and proposed as a potential TeV emitter by [Costamante and Ghisellini \(2002\)](#) based on its radio to X-ray spectrum. The distance of these sources plays a key role in the

EBL attenuation of its emitted VHE photons, distorting its observed VHE gamma-ray spectrum. The value of its redshift is still under debate, and multiple attempts have tried to constrain it. Its featureless spectrum makes it difficult to determine its distance using spectroscopic techniques. On the other side, imaging of the host galaxy can help derive its redshift. Using this method, [Falomo and Kotilainen \(1999\)](#) and [Scarpa et al. \(2000\)](#) first estimated a lower limit of $z > 0.3$. Years later, using the imaging-redshift technique developed by [Sbarufatti et al. \(2005\)](#) based on the absolute brightness of the host galaxy, [Meisner and Romani \(2010\)](#) measured $z = 0.45 \pm 0.08$ and [Kotilainen et al. \(2011\)](#) inferred a value of $z = 0.41 \pm 0.06$ from i' -band and near-infrared observations, respectively. The most recent spectroscopic measurement of this blazar by [Paiano et al. \(2017\)](#) confirms the absence of features as previously found by [Schachter et al. \(1993\)](#) and [Shaw et al. \(2013\)](#), establishing a lower limit of $z > 0.29$ based on the minimum equivalent width of the absorption lines expected in its spectrum.

1ES 0647+250 was observed for around 30 hours by MAGIC-I (in monoscopic mode) in the VHE gamma-ray band in 2008 ([Aleksić et al., 2011](#)), resulting in non-detection (with flux upper limit of $1.6 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, $E > 120 \text{ GeV}$). Also, VERITAS observed it for about 15 hours as part of its blazar key science project during 2007-2009 with no detection either ([Benbow, 2009](#)). It was not until 2011 that MAGIC announced its detection in the VHE range ([De Lotto and MAGIC Collaboration, 2012](#)) with an integral flux above 100 GeV of $(3.0 \pm 0.7)\%$ Crab units (C.U.) after observations during 2009-2011. Shortly after, VERITAS also reported its detection resulting from the source monitoring between 2010 and 2013 ([Dumm, 2013](#)) with a flux of $(2.9 \pm 0.7)\%$ C.U. for $E > 140 \text{ GeV}$, and deriving a soft spectral index of 3.6 ± 0.8 .

The emission from this source in other wavebands has shown a high variability from multi-year monitoring programs. [Kapanadze \(2009\)](#) observed significant variability in the period 1997-2006 in the optical R-band. However, no intra-night was detected, and due to the significant gaps present in the long-term light curve, they could not draw firm conclusions on the time scale of the variability. [Lindfors et al. \(2016\)](#) found bursts and a significant overall increasing flux variation in the R-band from 2008 to 2013. In the same period, these authors reported that the emission of 1ES 0647+250 in the 15-GHz radio band, even if weak, underwent an increasing long-term trend. Also, [Nilsson et al. \(2018\)](#) reported high significant variability in R-band in a longer term from 2002 to 2012. It has also been observed in X-rays (e.g., [Perlman et al., 2005](#)) after being first discovered in this band in the Einstein Slew Survey ([Schachter et al., 1992](#)). This BL Lac object is also detected in high-energy (HE) gamma rays and therefore

included in the *Fermi*-LAT catalogs from 1FGL to 4FGL and also considered variable at these energies (Abdo et al., 2010; Abdollahi et al., 2020; Abdollahi et al., 2022).

For the first time, we conducted a long-term multi-wavelength study for 1ES 0647+250 that includes VHE gamma-ray data. We present the detection of the VHE gamma-ray emission from this source by the MAGIC telescopes in four observing periods spanning from 2009 to 2020. The details of the observations and analysis are detailed in Section 6.2. Each MAGIC observing epoch corresponds to a different emission state attending to each energy band. VHE observations of this source from 2009 to 2011 followed the interest aroused by the study of the gamma-ray emission above 10 GeV by *Fermi*-LAT (later published as 1FGL catalog by Ackermann et al., 2013). In 2014, MAGIC observed this source triggered by a flare detected in the optical band (Kiehlmann et al., 2014). Years later, in 2019, the all-time-high X-ray flux from the source was detected (Kapanadze, 2019), and follow-up observations in VHE showed that the source was also active at the highest energies (Mirzoyan, 2019b). Recently, the highest-flux state in the VHE band has been measured by MAGIC (Blanch, 2020), triggered again by an enhanced state in X-rays (Kapanadze, 2020).

Using the assembled MWL data set (see Section 6.2), we performed a variability analysis in all the wavebands and a cross-band correlation study between those with a dense sampling, namely, radio, optical and HE gamma rays (Section 6.3). Next, we performed a spectral analysis of the X-ray and gamma-ray observations 6.5. As a side effect, through the joint spectral analysis from *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC observations in 2020, we estimated the still debatable redshift of this blazar (Section 6.6). Finally, we also modeled the MWL emission in each MAGIC observing epoch and proposed two emission models to explain the observed broadband SED (Section 6.7).

6.2 Multi-wavelength data sample

All the multi-instrument observations performed across the electromagnetic spectrum that were used in this work are presented in the following. I performed the MAGIC analysis (together with Jorge Otero Santos), David Paneque analyzed the data from *Fermi*-LAT, and the rest of the data from other instruments (from X-rays to radio) were processed and provided by external collaborators.

VHE gamma rays (MAGIC telescopes)

We used about 45 hours of good-quality data taken by the MAGIC telescopes (see

Table 6.1: Detection significance and integrated gamma-ray flux ($E > 100$ GeV) from the four MAGIC observing epochs of 1ES 0647+250.

Epoch	Year(s) of observation	Time interval [MJD]	Live time* [h]	Significance [Li&Ma]	$f (> 100 \text{ GeV})$ [$10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	$f (> 100 \text{ GeV})$ [% C.U.]
E1	2009-2011	55131.0 - 55620.9	26.7	5.5σ	0.97 ± 0.24	2.0 ± 0.5
E2	2014	56986.2 - 56987.2	2.2	5.3σ	1.62 ± 0.78	3.4 ± 1.6
E3	2019	58819.0 - 58821.2	2.7	6.1σ	3.82 ± 0.88	8.0 ± 1.8
E4	2020	59198.0 - 59208.0	13.5	22.9σ	7.10 ± 0.45	15.0 ± 1.0

*Live time is given for good-quality selected data.

Section 1.5) in stereoscopic mode between November 2009 and December 2020. Observations were split into four epochs (hereafter E1, E2, E3, E4), as indicated in Table 6.1. Most of the observation time corresponds to data collected between November 2009 and March 2011 during 39 days. In November 2014, MAGIC observed this blazar for two days, triggered through the ToO program by a high state in optical and gamma-ray bands. Highly enhanced X-ray fluxes detected recently also triggered MAGIC follow-up VHE observations in 2019 (for two days) and 2020 (around 14 hours spanning over 11 days). MAGIC also observed 1ES 0647+250 briefly in 2016, triggered by detecting a smooth rotation of the electric vector polarization angle (EVPA), although these data did not survive the quality cuts. We select data collected with zenith angles below 50° . Besides, about three hours from observations in E1 were taken under moderate moon conditions, which made us set a lower energy threshold for the analysis of about 100 GeV. We analyzed the data using the MARS described in Zanin et al. (2013); Aleksić et al. (2016) (see also Section 3.5). The significance of the detection in each observing period (see Table 6.1) was calculated following Li and Ma (1983) prescription. We report the integrated flux above 100 GeV in each epoch in the same table. The flux measured increased by about a factor of 7.5 between E1 and E4, reaching 15% C.U., the historical maximum VHE gamma-ray flux for this source. For the integral flux calculation, we assumed the spectral models reported in Section 6.5 for each period. In this work, we refer to E1 as a low state in the VHE gamma-ray regime, while we consider E2-E4 as VHE flaring episodes.

HE gamma rays (*Fermi*-LAT)

Large Area Telescope (LAT) onboard the *Fermi Gamma-ray Space Telescope* has observed 1ES 0647+250 in the HE gamma-ray band from the end of 2008 onward. Data used in this work were analyzed with the standard *Fermi* analysis software tools (version v11r07p00) using the P8R3_SOURCE_V2 response function. We select gamma-ray

Figure 6.1: Distribution of the squared angle between the actual position of the source and the reconstructed gamma rays (θ^2) from the four observing periods of 1ES 0647+250 (see Table 6.1). Filled markers represent the distribution of the on-source signal events peaking at $\theta^2 \rightarrow 0$, where the gamma-ray signal from the source is expected. Normalized background (off-source) distributions are shown as filled areas. The dashed line at $\theta^2 = 0.4(^{\circ})^2$ indicates the cut used to calculate the Li&Ma significance of the signal detection, which is calculated for each period.

events in the range of energy 0.3 – 300 GeV detected inside a region of interest (ROI) with 10° -radius centered on the source location. To avoid contamination from the Earth’s limb, we filter out events with a zenith angle above 100° . Especially for weak sources with hard HE gamma-ray spectra (photon index < 2.0) like the one we are studying here, for which long integration times are needed, increasing the lower end of the energy range (0.3 GeV instead of the typical minimum energy used of 0.1 GeV) improves the angular resolution by about a factor of two (from $\simeq 5^{\circ}$ at 0.1 GeV to $\simeq 2^{\circ}$ at 0.3 GeV). Thanks to this improvement, we reduce the contamination from the diffuse background (photon index > 2.0), hence lowering the systematic uncertainties. The diffuse Galactic and isotropic components were modeled respectively with the files `gll_iem_v07.fits` and `iso_P8R3_SOURCE_V2_v1.txt`¹. The background model ac-

¹<https://fermi.gsfc.nasa.gov/ssc/data/access/lat/BackgroundModels.html>

counts for the point-like sources (from the 4FGL catalog; Abdollahi et al., 2020) within the 10° ROI besides a surrounding 5° -wide annulus.

We use an unbinned maximum likelihood fitting technique for source detection, estimation of the flux, and spectral modeling (Abdo et al., 2009a). For the sources inside the ROI, spectral parameters were set to the values in the 4FGL catalog. For those variable objects with a detection significance $> 10\sigma$, the normalization is left as a free parameter of the fit. The spectral parameters of sources within 5° angular distance from our target and the Galactic and isotropic diffuse emission are not fixed and participate in the fitting. For the spectral model of 1ES 0647+250, we consider a power-law parameterization of the spectrum. We note, however, that in the third release of the 4FGL (4FGL-DR3; Abdollahi et al., 2022), a log parabola is preferred with about 4σ significance. The reason is that we integrate over a much shorter time interval than that used in the catalog. Hence the power-law parameterization better suits the poorer data statistics in our particular case.

For calculating the light curve (in the energy range 0.3-300 GeV), we have used monthly binning due to the poor sensitivity to significantly detect 1ES 0647+250 on shorter timescales, especially when the source is in a low state. We consider that the source is detected in each bin when the resulting fitting test statistic (TS) is above 4. The test statistic is defined as $TS = -2 \ln(L_{max,0}/L_{max,1})$, where $L_{max,0}/L_{max,1}$ is the ratio between the maximum likelihood value for the model without and with a point-like source at the expected location (Mattox et al., 1996). We calculate the spectral index in each time bin as described above and integrated flux for the light curve. Otherwise, when $TS < 4$, we calculate 95% confidence level upper limits to the flux value in each 30-day bin using a power-law spectral index of 1.70 (taken from the 4FGL-DR3; Abdollahi et al., 2022).

We employed different time intervals pursuing the maximum possible simultaneity with the MAGIC data to analyze the broadband SED (see Section) in each MAGIC observation snapshot. Coincident with E1, we calculate the Fermi-LAT spectrum by accumulating two years of data during 2009-2011. For the remaining epochs, we calculate the HE gamma-ray spectrum by combining data over 12 days centered on MAGIC observations in 2014 and 2019, while for E4, a 10-day binning has been used. The spectral analysis outcome can be found in Section 6.5.

X-rays (*Swift*-XRT)

X-ray data were provided by the X-Ray Telescope (XRT) described in Burrows et al. (2004) on board the *Neil Gehrels Swift Observatory*. This telescope performed 70

observations of 1ES 0647+250 from May 2010 to December 2020, some concurrent with MAGIC observing campaigns (E1-E4). During E1, *Swift*-XRT targeted this source 25 times between May 2010 and March 2011 (MJD 55322-55623). It was observed in November 2014 (E2, MJD 56981-56987) five times. Later, between December 2019 (E3) and March 2020 (MJD 58816-58914), more data was collected from 19 individual observations. Finally, *Swift*-XRT pointed to the source eight more times in December 2020 (E4, MJD 59196-59207).

These observations were performed in the so-called windowed-timing and photon-counting readout modes. We processed the XRT data with the XRTDAS software package (v.3.6.0), developed by the *Agenzia Spaziale Italiana* - Space Science Data Center and released within HEASoft (v.6.28, [Nasa High Energy Astrophysics Science Archive Research Center, 2014](#)). The data were calibrated and cleaned with the `xrtpipeline` tool following the standard filtering criteria. We employed the calibration files from the *Swift* calibration database (version 20200724).

To extract the source spectrum in the 0.3–2 keV and 2–10 keV energy ranges, we selected events detected within a 20-pixel radius region corresponding to approximately 46 arcsec and collecting about 90% of the PSF. Respectively, the background is taken from a nearby control region with a 40-pixel radius. The necessary ancillary response files were generated using the `xrtmkarf` tool with corrections for PSF losses and CCD defects. For the spectral fitting, the events were binned employing the `grppha` tool, keeping a minimum of 20 counts per bin.

UV/optical band (*Swift*-UVOT)

Swift satellite is also instrumented with the Ultra-Violet and Optical Telescope (UVOT) detailed in [Roming et al. \(2005\)](#). It performed simultaneous photometric observations to those carried out by XRT described above. They were performed in the optical bands U, B, and V, besides the UV filters UVW1, UVM2, and UVW2. Data were calibrated from counts to fluxes using the standard calibrations ([Poole et al., 2008](#); [Breeveld et al., 2011](#)) from the *Swift*-UVOT calibration database (version 20201026). Next, we corrected for the Galactic extinction considering a mean value of $E(B - V) = 0.0835$ mag ([Schlafly and Finkbeiner, 2011](#)). In addition, we use an interstellar extinction curve from [Fitzpatrick \(1999\)](#) to calculate $\nu F(\nu)$ values at the filter's effective frequencies.

Optical R band

1ES 0647+250 was extensively monitored in the optical R band. Most of the data we

use in this work were taken by the 35 cm Kungliga Vetenskapsakademien (KVA) telescope based at the ORM (island of La Palma) as part of the Tuorla blazar monitoring program² from December 2002 to December 2019 (MJD 52615-58835). The data were processed according to the analysis procedure detailed in [Nilsson et al. \(2018\)](#). Part of that analysis consisted of subtracting the stellar emission from the host galaxy and the extinction of our galaxy.

The most recent observations in this optical band were carried out in December 2020 (contemporary to E4) with the 40 cm telescopes of Las Cumbres Observatory Telescope Network ([Brown et al., 2013](#)), with the infrared-optical instrument of the 2 m Liverpool Telescope ([Steele et al., 2004](#)) at ORM, and with the 43 cm Physics Innovation Robotic Astronomical Telescope Explorer (PIRATE; [Holmes et al., 2011](#)) at the Teide Observatory (Canary island of Tenerife, Spain).

Radio (OVRO)

In radio, this source was densely monitored by the Owens Valley Radio Observatory (OVRO) at a frequency of 15 GHz with the 40 m dish-antenna radiotelescope ([Richards et al., 2011](#))³. Observations span from January 2008 to December 2020, encompassing the MAGIC observations. Data were processed following the method from [Richards et al. \(2011\)](#). Those observations that resulted in signal-to-noise ratio < 3 were considered non-detections and excluded from further analysis. The remaining 446 observations in which radio emission was detected from 1ES 0647+250 are shown in Fig. 6.2, bottom.

The light curves from all the MWL observations presented above are plotted respectively in each of the panels of Fig. 6.2. We note that a monthly binning was used for the MAGIC and *Fermi*-LAT light curve due to their limited capability to significantly detect this blazar in a low-state, whereas 1-day binning was used for the rest of the instruments.

6.3 Variability analysis

We assess the emission variability from this blazar by searching for significant flux variations in the light curves presented above (Fig. 6.2) over different timescales. For

²<http://users.utu.fi/kani/1m/>

³<https://www.astro.caltech.edu/ovroblazars/>

Figure 6.2: MWL light curves of 1ES 0647+250. From top to bottom: MAGIC (> 100 GeV, monthly binning), *Fermi*-LAT flux and spectral index (0.3 – 300 GeV, monthly binning), *Swift*-XRT (0.3-2 keV and 2-10 keV), *Swift*-XRT spectral index, *Swift*-UVOT (B, V, U, UVW1, UVM2, and UVW2 filters), optical R band (KVA, Liverpool Telescope, Las Cumbres and PIRATE telescope) and OVRO (15 GHz). We note that KVA performed all the R-band observations except those from 2020. Owing to a major instrument upgrade of OVRO in 2016, error bars are considerably smaller afterward. MAGIC observing campaigns (E1-E4) are depicted by the vertically shaded regions. Credit: Jorge Otero Santos. 143

that purpose, we first test the constant flux hypothesis for each light curve, provided the data sampling allows.

Regarding the VHE gamma-ray band, the limited time coverage, biased towards flaring episodes, would make this analysis unreliable. Therefore no conclusions can be drawn at this waveband. Descending in energies, 1ES 0647+250 is identified as variable in 4FGL (Abdollahi et al., 2020; Abdollahi et al., 2022) with a *variability index*⁴ of $\simeq 315$. In addition, the fit of the *Fermi*-LAT light curve data points results in a $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.} = 346/143 \simeq 2.4$ (P-value $\sim 10^{-20}$), hence clearly incompatible with that hypothesis when assuming month timescales. The increasing flux trend over the 11-year term was evaluated with a linear fit, which better suits the light curve than the steady-flux hypothesis according to its goodness of fit $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.} = 191/142 \simeq 1.3$ (P-value $\simeq 0.004$). We cannot evaluate flux variations on sub-month timescales due to the used time binning since LAT is not significant enough to detect this source on shorter time intervals.

We find that 1ES 0647+250 is variable on timescales of the order of several months or years from radio to X-rays which agrees with previous variability studies on this source (e.g., Kapanadze, 2009; Kiehlmann et al., 2014; Nilsson et al., 2018; Kapanadze, 2019, 2020). We note that the sampling of the *Swift* light curves (X-rays, UV, and optical bands) is sparse, as in the VHE observations. These data are biased towards isolated snapshots during states of enhanced flux. Hence long-term variability results at these energies must be taken carefully.

The outcome of testing the constant flux hypothesis in different time intervals is presented in Table 6.3. The constant flux is ruled out for all wavelengths when considering the whole dataset (2009-2011). We also notice that optical and radio emission increases globally in the long term, seemingly with the same tendency as the gamma-ray band, also showing variability on shorter timescales. More details on the possible correlation among these bands are presented in Section 6.4. Since E1 and E4 are the periods with the most abundant MWL coverage, we also evaluated the variability of these sub-samples. The results are also indicated in Table 6.3. Significant variability in the X-ray band was found during these two periods, and in the R-band during E1.

Aside from testing the constant flux assumption, fractional variability is commonly used to quantify the intensity of the variability in each energy band, providing insights into the underlying dominant particle population and acceleration processes involved

⁴See definition in Table 6 of Abdollahi et al. (2022).

Table 6.2: χ^2 -statistic of the steady-flux hypothesis for each light curve in Fig. 6.2.

Waveband	$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$		
	2009-2020	2009-2011 (E1)	2020 (E4)
HE gamma rays	346/143 \simeq 2.4	15.7/14 \simeq 1.1	–
X-rays (2-10 keV)	3255/69 \simeq 47.2	582/24 \simeq 24.3	154/7 = 22.0
X-rays (0.3-2 keV)	21575/69 \simeq 312.7	1159/24 \simeq 48.3	995/7 \simeq 142.1
UV (uvw2 filter)	1996/55 \simeq 36.3	66.6/23 \simeq 2.9	6.3/6 \simeq 1.1
Optical (B band)	338/31 \simeq 10.9	1.3/3 \simeq 0.4	4.5/7 \simeq 0.6
Optical (R band)	129851/550 \simeq 236.1	922/76 \simeq 12.1	1.1/12 \simeq 0.1
Radio (15 GHz)	7169/446 \simeq 16.1	26/50 \simeq 0.5	–

in the emission of energy in a particular band. [Vaughan et al. \(2003\)](#) defined this parameter as

$$F_{var} = \sqrt{\frac{S^2 - \langle \sigma_{err}^2 \rangle}{\langle x \rangle^2}}, \quad (6.1)$$

where $\langle x \rangle$ and S^2 are the mean and the variance of the distribution of estimated fluxes, respectively, and $\langle \sigma_{err}^2 \rangle$ mean square error of the data. The corresponding uncertainty can be estimated following the description by [Poutanen et al. \(2008\)](#), formulated in [Aleksić et al. \(2015a\)](#):

$$\Delta F_{var} = \sqrt{F_{var}^2 - err(\sigma_{NXS}^2)} - F_{var}, \quad (6.2)$$

where $err(\sigma_{NXS}^2)$ is the normalized excess variance taken from [Vaughan et al. \(2003\)](#), computed as

$$err(\sigma_{NXS}^2) = \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} \frac{\langle \sigma_{err}^2 \rangle}{\langle x \rangle^2} \right)^2 + \left(\sqrt{\frac{\langle \sigma_{err}^2 \rangle}{N}} \frac{2F_{var}}{\langle x \rangle} \right)^2}, \quad (6.3)$$

where N is the number of data points. The estimation of the fractional variability for each MWL light curve can be seen in Fig. 6.3.

[Aleksić et al. \(2015a\)](#) and [Schleicher et al. \(2019\)](#) discuss the details of the estimation and limitations of the fractional variability method. One of these caveats on the applicability of fractional variability is the dissimilar temporal coverage at different energy bands. In our case, the data in the radio, optical, and HE gamma-ray bands evenly cover the entire 11-year term. In contrast, the available VHE gamma-ray, X-ray, and UV data are, in comparison, much more scarce and unequally distributed over the same period. Therefore, we followed two data selection strategies for the fractional variability computation. On the one hand, we estimate the fractional variability using all the data points of the multi-instrument light curves presented above. On the

Figure 6.3: Fractional variability for 1ES 0647+250 MWL light curves. Open markers correspond to the entire sample of data. Solid markers indicate MWL observations quasi-simultaneous to the MAGIC observing campaigns. The discrepancy between the R-band observations and the UV and optical filters from *Swift* observations is due to the lower time coverage of the data taken with *Swift* filters. This disparity is also seen between optical and UV filters from UVOT for the same reason. The fractional variability values are compatible with coetaneous UV and optical *Swift* observations. Credit: Jorge Otero Santos.

other hand, for a more unbiased comparison, we selected data contemporaneous with the MAGIC observations. Both results are shown with empty and filled markers in Fig. 6.3.

Fractional variability is higher at VHE gamma-ray and X-ray energies. We remark that F_{var} is maximum in the VHE regime despite the considerable statistical uncertainty likely due to the larger errors in their flux measurements and the biased statistics towards active periods. The same tendency concerning flares affects X-ray data, although their flux estimates are more precise than in VHE. Variability is higher than in HE gamma rays, optical, and radio bands, even when accounting only for MAGIC-coinciding data. We also tried to bin the other waveband light curves in 30-day intervals for a more equitable comparison to Fermi-LAT data, finding compatible

values to those plotted in Fig. 6.3. This fact might point towards the dominance of the long-term timescales in the overall variability.

The overall structure of the fractional variability as a function of frequency obtained for 1ES 0647+250 (i.e., higher values in VHE gamma-ray and X-ray bands and lower values for radio and optical and HE gamma-ray observations) is comparable to the trend found in other sources such as Mrk 421 (Aleksić et al., 2015a; Baloković et al., 2016; MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2021b), MAGIC 2001+439 (Aleksić et al., 2014) and 1ES 1959+650 (Kapanadze et al., 2018). In contrast, other sources such as Mrk 501 (Ahnen et al., 2017, 2018) or TXS 0506+056 (Acciari et al., 2022) show a monotonically increasing F_{var} trend from radio to VHE gamma-rays. The different behavior might hint at different particle populations and processes in the jet, besides a higher dominance of the synchrotron acceleration in the jet (Aleksić et al., 2015a). Moreover, the general trend of the fractional variability may vary with time, suggesting changes in the population or the processes in the jet (e.g., Furniss et al. (2015) where F_{var} maxima values at X-rays and VHE gamma-ray domain were documented for Mrk 501. We stress that the associated F_{var} uncertainty is substantial in the gamma-ray domain because of the 30-day binning at the highest energies and poor sampling of MAGIC observations. Hence, the interpretation of the general behavior is inconclusive in these bands.

6.4 Cross-band correlation

We search for possible cross-correlations between different light curves at wavebands (Fig. 6.2). Because of the more extensive time coverage and even sampling, we only compare HE gamma-ray, optical R, and radio bands from 2009 to 2019⁵ For this purpose, we performed an analysis based on an improved version of the discrete correlation function (DCF) by Edelson and Krolik (1988), the Z-transform discrete correlation function (ZDCF, Alexander, 2013), better suited for unevenly sampled data. We followed the method detailed in Max-Moerbeck et al. (2014b), which has been widely used for these cross-correlation studies (e.g., Lindfors et al., 2016; Otero-Santos et al., 2020). To calculate the level of significance, we generated $\sim 10^5$ MC-simulated light curves with identical sampling and power spectral density as our data (with power-law spectral indices $\alpha_{\text{radio}} = 1.26 \pm 0.18$, $\alpha_R = 1.62 \pm 0.13$, and $\alpha_{\gamma \text{ rays}} = 0.75 \pm 0.41$)

⁵We leave out the individual optical observations from 2020 to avoid biases due to the 1-year gap between KVA and the rest of the optical telescopes.

using the package DELCgen (Connolly, 2015) based on the algorithm developed by Emmanoulopoulos et al. (2013).

Figure 6.4: Cross-correlation estimates between each pair of light curves. The solid line depicts the ZDCF with the corresponding 1σ statistical uncertainty band. Dotted lines correspond to the different significance levels derived from the MC artificial light curves. Credit: Jorge Otero Santos.

The outcome of this analysis for each pair of light curves is shown in Fig. 6.4. In all three combinations, we found a positive correlation with significance levels of $\gtrsim 3\sigma$ with respect to the null hypothesis of no correlation. We computed the maximum cross-correlation ZDCF values, their significance, and the time lag at which ZDCF reaches its maximum. Alternatively, we estimated the centroid of the DCF distributions based on the model-independent Monte Carlo flux randomization and random subset selection approach from Peterson et al. (1998, 2004). From the correlation results reported in Table 6.3 can be inferred that the radio emission is delayed compared to that of the optical and gamma-ray energies. We note, however, that the correlation remains highly significant for a wide range of time lags. This fact shows that the long-term trend dominates the correlation and that the correlation only arising at a particular lag is diluted.

Table 6.3: ZDCF cross-correlation and time lags between wavebands and for 1ES 0647+250.

Energy bands	ZDCF _{max}	Significance [σ]	Lag (ZDCF _{max}) ^a [days]	Lag (DCF _{centroid}) ^b [days]
R-band and HE gamma-ray	0.60	3	17 \pm 30	-7 \pm 105
Radio and R-band	0.67	3	-398 \pm 80	-380 \pm 88
Radio and HE gamma-ray	0.50	4	-393 \pm 40	-332 \pm 144

^aMaximum ZDCF and corresponding time lags were calculated following the method by [Alexander \(2013\)](#). ^bTime lag corresponding to the centroid of the DCF distributions following the model-independent Monte Carlo flux randomization and random subset selection approach ([Peterson et al., 1998, 2004](#)).

So far, we have discussed the dominant long-term trend that we had already hinted at from the general increasing flux trend in the gamma-ray, R-band, and radio light curves. In this context, correlations at shorter timescales are hidden under the multi-year trend (see, e.g., [Smith et al., 1993](#); [Lindfors et al., 2016](#); [Raiteri et al., 2021](#)). In order to look for sub-year correlations among these three energy bands, we detrended the long-term flux rise for all of them. The method for finding the common slowly-varying component between each pair of light curves is detailed in [Lindfors et al. \(2016, Sect. 5.1\)](#). We fit the light curve of the lower-energy band to a polynomial that best suits the data. Next, the polynomial function is scaled to match the average flux density from the other light curve, multiplied by a factor from 0.1 to 1, and then subtracted from the other light curve. We used the factor that yielded the minimum root mean squared (RMS)⁶ in the resulting subtracted light curve. Figure 6.5 displays the detrended light curves after applying the procedure just summarized.

By comparing the root mean squared of the polynomial-subtracted light curve to that of the original undetrended light curve, we estimate the fractional contribution of the slowly-varying trend to the total flux variability. In the case of the common component between radio and optical, it accounts for approximately 50% of the total variation. Compared to findings in [Lindfors et al. \(2016\)](#), they report a smaller contribution of 10% in the time interval from 2008 to 2013, which is compatible with our estimation if considering the same period. From 2013 to 2020, we obtain a contribution of 40% instead. Regarding radio and HE gamma-ray bands, the common trend corresponds to around 20% of the total variability. Finally, the slowly-varying component between the optical and LAT light curve explains roughly 25% of the whole flux variation. Finally, we looked for correlation in shorter timescales using those detrended light curves using the ZDCF approach, not finding any significant correlation emission.

⁶Estimated as $\text{RMS} = \sqrt{\sum(x_i - x_{mean})^2/N}$ where x_{mean} is the mean flux of the light curve.

6.5 Spectral analysis

X-ray spectral analysis

We compared the X-ray spectral behavior of 1ES 0647+250 observed in the different MAGIC observing campaigns. Table 6.4 displays the spectral parameters and flux states during each period. We indicate the spectral parameters for the minimum, mean, and maximum flux states during the low state in epoch E1 and the flare from E4 due to the significant variability in the X-ray spectrum. In contrast, the nearest spectra in time to the MAGIC observations are reported for E2 and E3.

The spectra were modeled with a power-law function ($dN/dE = f_0(E/E_0)^{-\alpha}$). A log-parabola fit ($dN/dE = f_0(E/E_0)^{-\alpha-\beta \log(E/E_0)}$) was also tested, although not statistically preferred. Models took into account the photoelectric absorption with a neutral-hydrogen column density fixed to the Galactic value in the direction of 1ES 0647+250,

Figure 6.5: Detrending of the baseline common-varying component from radio, R-band optical, and HE gamma-ray light curves. Dashed lines represent the scaled low-frequency light curve's best polynomial fit, red dots correspond to the original data set and black dots show the detrended light curve. Credit: Jorge Otero Santos.

Table 6.4: Spectral parameters of the X-ray band considering a power law.

Epoch	Time interval [MJD]	$F_{0.3-2 \text{ keV}}$ [$10^{-11} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	$F_{2-10 \text{ keV}}$ [$10^{-11} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	α_{XRT}	$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$
E1 (Minimum)	55516.2	$1.61^{+0.06}_{-0.05}$	$0.73^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$	2.34 ± 0.05	$51.0/49 \simeq 1.0$
E1 (Mean)	55322.3 – 55623.8	$2.26^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	$1.16^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	2.15 ± 0.01	$5.8/5 \simeq 1.2$
E1 (Maximum)	55597.8	$4.12^{+0.13}_{-0.16}$	$3.62^{+0.27}_{-0.24}$	1.95 ± 0.04	$66.7/69 \simeq 1.0$
E2	56987.3	$4.92^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$	$1.62^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$	2.50 ± 0.04	$140.9/121 \simeq 1.2$
E3	58820.2	$12.3^{+0.23}_{-0.25}$	$7.40^{+0.23}_{-0.25}$	2.19 ± 0.03	$151.7/153 \simeq 1.0$
E4 (Minimum)	59200.0	$3.73^{+0.13}_{-0.13}$	$2.48^{+0.25}_{-0.21}$	2.10 ± 0.05	$54.2/47 \simeq 1.2$
E4 (Mean)	59196.5 – 59207.1	$6.67^{+0.06}_{-0.06}$	$3.67^{+0.09}_{-0.08}$	2.27 ± 0.01	$6.4/5 \simeq 1.3$
E4 (Maximum)	59202.0	$9.01^{+0.16}_{-0.14}$	$5.36^{+0.22}_{-0.21}$	2.21 ± 0.03	$188.5/178 \simeq 1.1$

namely $1.20 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (HI4PI Collaboration et al., 2016). We present in both panels of Fig. 6.6 the relation between spectral indices and the fluxes for both X-ray bands (0.3-2 and 2-10 keV) in each observing epoch.

The spectra from E1 show a variation of the spectral index of ~ 0.4 , varying from values of $\alpha_{XRT} \sim 2.4$ when the source is fainter, up to much harder values of $\alpha_{XRT} \sim 2.0$ when the source is in a higher state. The correlation between the spectral index and the X-ray flux was quantified by estimating the Pearson’s linear correlation coefficient for the integral X-ray flux in the 0.3-10 keV band, obtaining a value of $r = -0.65 \pm 0.15$ (P-value = 3×10^{-4}) for E1. This behavior of harder-when-brighter has been seen in the past for other blazars like, for example, 1ES 2344+514 (Acciari et al., 2011b; Aleksić et al., 2013), Mrk 421 (MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2021b) or TXS 1515-273 during bright X-ray flares (Acciari et al., 2021a). Wang et al. (2018) describe this trend as typical behavior for blazars in the X-ray regime.

The spectral analysis for E2 in 2014 reveals a steeper spectrum ($\alpha_{XRT} \sim 2.5$) than those from the low state (E1), as shown in Fig. 6.6. We do not see harder-when-brighter behavior during this epoch. However, this could also be due to the limited time coverage during this period, with only four X-ray observations.

The flaring activity observed in E3 shows the highest X-ray flux ever detected for this source (Kapanadze, 2019). In this period, the measured spectral index as a function of the integrated X-ray flux does not show an evident trend. Nonetheless, Fig. 6.6 suggests the behavior of the lowest-flux data ($F_{0.3-2 \text{ keV}} < 8 \times 10^{-11} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$,

Figure 6.6: Power-law spectral index (α_{XRT}) vs X-ray flux for the different epochs in the energy bands 0.3-2 keV (*left*) and 2-10 keV (*right*). Credit: Jorge Otero Santos.

and $F_{2-10 \text{ keV}} < 4 \times 10^{-11} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, collected after the VHE flare) than that of the brightest measurements (performed during the historically high X-ray activity and approximately concurrent to the observations conducted by MAGIC). We calculated Pearson’s correlation coefficient between the spectral index and the flux for both samples. On the one hand, the lowest-flux subset shows a correlation of $r = -0.64 \pm 0.20$ (P-value = 8×10^{-3}) in the 0.3-10 keV range. On the other hand, the other subset shows no correlation between the flux and the spectral index, which hints at a saturation of the X-ray spectral index for the highest X-ray fluxes during this flare.

In the latest observing period (E4), 1ES 0647+250 showed significant X-ray variability (same as in E1 as reported in Table 6.2). However, contrary to the results from E1, the X-ray observations from this period do not suggest any correlated behavior of the spectral index and the flux.

When considering the integrated flux in the 0.3-10 keV band, the same results were obtained above, suggesting that the spectral index does not vary between the 0.3-2 keV and the 2-10 keV X-ray bands. In summary, in epochs E2 and E4, no apparent behavior in their X-ray spectra is indicated. On the other hand, a harder-when-brighter behavior was detected for both E1 and E3. Besides, an index saturation was found afterward, from observations simultaneous to the brightest X-ray observations and closest to those from MAGIC. This saturation is also observed for other blazars like Mrk 421 (Acciari et al., 2021b). Moreover, the harder-when-brighter trends can be explained in terms of, for instance, a change in the maximum energy of the electrons responsible for the emission (see, e.g., Abeysekara et al., 2017) or hardening of the electron distribution (Xue et al., 2006). A detailed discussion on the spectral variability studied here can be found in Section 6.8. We also searched for hysteresis loops in the X-ray spectral index

Table 6.5: Spectral parameters of the HE gamma-ray spectra from *Fermi*-LAT data.

Epoch	Time interval [MJD]	f_0 [10^{-7} TeV $^{-1}$ cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$]	E_0 [GeV]	Spectral index α	f (0.3 – 300 GeV) [10^{-9} cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$]	TS*
E1	55131.0 – 55622.0	2.1 ± 0.2	3	1.64 ± 0.08	4.2 ± 0.6	336
E2	56981.0 – 56993.0	6.1 ± 2.4	3	1.54 ± 0.25	13.9 ± 6.8	41
E3	58814.0 – 58826.0	7.5 ± 2.4	3	1.68 ± 0.22	20.2 ± 8.7	44
E4	59197.5 – 59206.5	17.8 ± 4.9	3	1.58 ± 0.17	33.0 ± 0.1	84

*Test statistic resulting from the maximum likelihood fit to the model.

evolution during the X-ray flares. However, due to the low coverage and uncertainties in the characterization of the spectral indices, we do not spot any noticeable hysteresis-like behavior.

HE gamma-ray spectral analysis

The HE gamma-ray spectrum and SED of 1ES 0647+250 were extracted for all the analysis epochs using the *Fermi*-LAT data. A PL shape was assumed. This fit was performed in the energy range of 0.3-300 GeV. The low energy photons ($< 3 - 5$ GeV, below the IC peak) dominate the fit of the spectrum, leading to the observed “hard” indices. Table 6.5 shows the spectral parameters of the HE band for the different epochs. No significant variability in the spectral index was detected in the *Fermi*-LAT observations. Moreover, contrary to the results for the X-ray spectrum, we do not see any correlation between the spectral index with the flux. The spectral index light curve is compatible with a constant value, $\alpha_{Fermi} = 1.70 \pm 0.02$ and a value of $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.} = 126.8/143 \simeq 0.9$, which is similar to $\alpha_{Fermi} = 1.73 \pm 0.02$ reported in the 4FGL-DR3 catalogue [Abdollahi et al. \(2020\)](#); [Abdollahi et al. \(2022\)](#).

For the monitoring performed in E1, all the *Fermi*-LAT data from November 2009 to March 2011 were used. For the enhanced states of 2014 (E2) and 2019 (E3), a 12-day integration window centered around the MAGIC detection was used due to the low HE gamma-ray flux displayed by 1ES 0647+250 in shorter time scales during these epochs, leading to a $\text{TS} < 25$ and mostly upper limits in the spectral points. Finally, for the 2020 sample (E4), simultaneous *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC observations were used to compute the spectrum. The spectral parameters of each period are shown in Table 6.5.

VHE gamma-ray spectral analysis

The VHE gamma-ray SED of 1ES 0647+250 was also obtained from the data taken in each analysis period. The spectra from the observations from E1, E2, and E3 were well modeled assuming a power-law parameterization. In contrast, a 3σ preference for

Table 6.6: Spectral parameters of the VHE gamma-ray spectra from MAGIC data.

Epoch	Time interval [MJD]	Fit Model*	f_0 [10^{-10} TeV $^{-1}$ cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$]	E_0 [GeV]	Spectral index α	Curvature β	$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$
E1	55131.0 – 55620.9	PL	0.29 ± 0.07	190	3.12 ± 0.37	–	$1.2/3 \simeq 0.4$
E2	56986.2 – 56987.2	PL	4.40 ± 1.63	100	3.25 ± 0.74	–	$2.1/2 \simeq 1.1$
E3	58819.0 – 58821.2	PL	12.0 ± 2.2	100	3.73 ± 0.58	–	$2.2/2 \simeq 1.1$
E4	59198.1 – 59206.1	PL	16.9 ± 1.0	100	3.70 ± 0.10	–	$18.1/5 \simeq 3.6$
E4	59198.1 – 59206.1	LogP	18.9 ± 1.6	100	3.16 ± 0.21	1.91 ± 0.68	$5.3/6 \simeq 0.9$

*For the 2020 VHE gamma-ray spectrum, both power-law (PL) and log-parabolic (LogP) models were used with a $\sim 3\sigma$ preference for the latter.

a log-parabolic shape was observed in the spectrum of E4. The results of the MAGIC spectral analysis are summarized in Table 6.6 and plotted in Fig. 6.7. The statistics are not high enough for the rest of the periods to evaluate a log-parabolic spectral shape. Since the source’s redshift is still under debate, the spectra and SEDs presented in this analysis correspond to the observed spectra without the correction for EBL absorption.

Figure 6.7: VHE gamma-ray SED from MAGIC observations in each observing epoch.

6.6 Redshift estimation

We used the joint *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC spectra to constrain the redshift of 1ES 0647+250. We followed the procedure proposed by Prandini et al. (2010) to perform this estimation. This method assumes that the VHE gamma-ray spectrum of a blazar cannot be harder than the spectrum in the HE range measured by *Fermi*-LAT after correcting for the EBL absorption. We use the EBL model developed by Franceschini et al. (2008). First, an upper limit of the redshift, z^* , is calculated as the limit value at which the

slopes of the HE and VHE gamma-ray spectra are equal by deabsorbing the MAGIC spectral points until the spectral indices of the HE and VHE spectra are equal. Then, the empirical formula that relates z^* and the reconstructed value of the redshift, z_{rec} , with the updated parameters presented in Prandini et al. (2011), is used to estimate the reconstructed value. We performed this estimation with the *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC SED from E4 (reported in Tables 6.5 and 6.6) due to their higher flux and, therefore, higher statistics and lower uncertainties in the flux and spectral index estimation.

This empirical relation applied to our data leads to a redshift estimation of $z_{rec} = 0.45 \pm 0.05$. This derived value of the redshift is in agreement with the current lower limit of $z > 0.29$ estimated by Paiano et al. (2017) from spectroscopic observations, and the most reliable measurement of the distance by Kotilainen et al. (2011), who reported a value of $z = 0.41 \pm 0.06$ from the detection of the host galaxy. Moreover, the maximum redshift value obtained with this method is $z^* = 0.75 \pm 0.11$, compatible with the estimations of the distance of this blazar cited above.

This method has proven to report accurate values of the distance of several blazars in the past, for instance, MAGIC J2001+435 (Aleksić et al., 2014), or S5 0716+714 (MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2018). However, it has also reported some inconsistent values, for instance, PKS 0447-439, with an estimation of $z = 0.20$ by Prandini et al. (2012), later measured to be $z = 0.343$ by Muriel et al. (2015). We note that this empirical procedure has different caveats and assumptions when estimating the redshift of a source. A detailed discussion of these caveats can be found in Prandini et al. (2010, 2011), where the redshift of several gamma-ray emitting blazars was estimated correctly.

Alternatively, another constraint was derived using a maximum likelihood fit of the joint *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC SEDs from E4 (see Fig. 6.8), using a concave log parabola as the spectral model, as described in Acciari et al. (2019). Using the EBL model from Domínguez et al. (2011), a scan of redshift values was performed, obtaining a likelihood profile from which the redshift can be constrained (see Fig. 6.9). From this profile we estimate a redshift value of $z = 0.54 \pm 0.10(\text{stat})_{-0.13}^{+0.16}(\text{sys})$. A 15% systematic uncertainty in the overall light throughput was considered following the studies in Aleksić et al. (2016). Under these considerations, the 95% confidence level (CL) upper limit for the redshift z is 0.81 (Fig. 6.9, right).

In the following SED modeling, we assumed the value of $z = 0.41$ from Kotilainen et al. (2011), which agrees with the value we derived from the empirical relation.

Figure 6.8: Maximum likelihood joint fit of gamma-ray SED from *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC observations in E4 assuming $z \simeq 0.54$ as reported in the text. SED is deabsorbed from the EBL at the highest energies assuming the model by Domínguez et al. (2011). *Fermi*-LAT spectral parameters are set to: a spectral index of 1.58 ± 0.16 , pivot energy of 3 GeV, flux normalization at the pivot energy of $2.5 \pm 0.7 \times 10^{-11}$ erg $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Figure 6.9: Likelihood profile of the joint fit of gamma-ray SED from *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC observations in E4 for the constraint of 1ES 0647+250 redshift. The solid blue line indicates the nominal light collection efficiency relation between MC simulated and observed data. Orange and green lines indicate the result when assuming $\pm 15\%$ variation of the ratio between MC and observations. The redshift value that minimizes the χ^2 distribution (left panel) is the most plausible estimation from this analysis. Additionally, the 95% CL UL to the redshift is 0.71 (right panel). However, when considering the systematics on the light efficiency, the very conservative UL (95% CL) would be 0.81, provided there was 15% more light in the observed data than in the MC.

6.7 Broadband SED

The broadband emission of blazars has been successfully described in the past with models based on leptonic emission processes. However, due to the still debatable origin of the high-energy SED peak, hadronic models have also been successful on several occasions, especially in the scenario of neutrino emission (e.g., [Petropoulou et al., 2017](#); [Kreter et al., 2020](#); [Petropoulou et al., 2020a,b](#)). Each model has its strengths and limitations, with the hadronic models being favored by uncorrelated optical, X-ray, and gamma-ray variability (e.g., [Dimitrakoudis et al., 2012](#); [Böttcher et al., 2013](#)). Considering the correlated MWL variability observed for this source, we propose an interpretation based on leptonic models. While one-component models provide a more straightforward solution due to the smaller number of free parameters, they have not always been adequate to reproduce the emission of gamma-ray blazars compared to two-component models ([MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2020a](#)).

We present the modeling with both one- and two-component leptonic models, comparing their performance and capability to reproduce the observed features. The modeling was performed assuming the cosmological parameters reported by [Planck Collaboration et al. \(2020\)](#): a Hubble parameter of $H_0 = 67.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, a matter density of $\Omega_m = 0.315$ and a dark energy density $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$. The models used here are not time-dependent. Hence, the different epochs are modeled independently. Given the sparse data sets and the large time separations between the different SEDs, no firm conclusions can be drawn on the temporal evolution of the model parameters.

One-component model

As an initial approach, a one-component SSC model was used to reproduce the broadband SEDs of 1ES 0647+250 ([Tavecchio et al., 1998](#)). This model assumes the existence of a single, homogeneous, spherical emitting region in the jet with size R , Lorentz factor γ , and magnetic field B . The low-energy bump of the SED is due to synchrotron radiation, while the high-energy bump is modeled through SSC. The population of electrons inside the emitting region is assumed to follow a broken power-law distribution with the Lorentz factor, described by

$$N(\gamma) = K\gamma^{-n_1} \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma_b}\right)^{n_1-n_2}, \quad \gamma_{min} < \gamma < \gamma_{max}. \quad (6.4)$$

The distribution has a normalization K between γ_{min} and γ_{max} and slopes n_1 and n_2 below and above the break in the electron distribution, γ_b ([Maraschi and Tavecchio, 2003](#)).

The parameters of the one-component models for each epoch are reported in Table 6.7. The resulting models during each VHE gamma-ray detection are shown in Fig. 6.10. We scanned several combinations of the parameters described above to perform the modeling. The agreement between the model and the data is evaluated through visual inspection of the SEDs shown in Fig. 6.10. The one-component SSC model can well describe the observational data from optical to VHE gamma rays. However, the radio data are strongly self-absorbed, and thus, the emission at radio wavelengths is assumed to arise from a different region (Tavecchio et al., 1998). Therefore, this model is not able to reproduce the radio emission.

Two-component model

Alternatively, we modeled the SEDs in different epochs with a two-component model based on Tavecchio et al. (2011). This model calculates synchrotron and SSC emission for spherical emission regions while considering synchrotron-self absorption. The strength of the magnetic field is typically assumed to scale with the distance from the central engine as d^{-1} . If the two components are separate, the one responsible for the X-ray and VHE gamma-ray emission is closer to the central engine than the one responsible for radio and optical emission. Therefore, the former needs a stronger magnetic field than the latter component, ~ 1 G. Tavecchio and Ghisellini (2016) show that the magnetic field strengths tend to be significantly lower than the values required for equipartition in one-component models. Moreover, in two-component models, it is difficult to reproduce the observed SED with the magnetic field strength values ~ 1 G. Re-connection layers and radial structures of magnetic fields across the jet are possible ways to invoke reduced local magnetic field strengths (see discussion in Nalewajko et al., 2014). Therefore, similar to the approach used in MAGIC Collaboration et al. (2020a), we assumed two co-spatial and interacting emission regions to mimic a simple spine-sheath model. The two spherical emission regions are called “core” and “blob”, with sizes $R_{\text{core}} > R_{\text{blob}}$. The regions are filled with electrons distributed in Lorentz factor according to a smoothed broken power law (see Equation 6.4), and the physical quantities are expressed in the co-moving frame of each region. Each emission region has a Lorentz factor γ , size R , and magnetic field strength B . The following constraints are employed to reduce the number of free parameters for this model:

- The measured full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) values of the major axis of the VLBI core can be used to calculate the upper limit of the size of the core emission region. The measured FWHM value of the major axis is 1.88 arcsec (Piner and

Figure 6.10: Broadband SEDs of 1ES 0647+250 for the different observing campaigns described with one-component and two-component SSC emission models. *Top left*: 2009-2011. *Bottom left*: 2014. *Top right*: 2019. *Bottom right*: 2020. Filled blue dots correspond to the MWL simultaneous data of each period. Empty dots represent the archival data extracted from the Space Science and Data Center (SSDC) database (<https://www.ssdsc.asi.it>). The dotted lines correspond to the fitted one-component SSC model. Black lines represent the total two-component SSC model. The dashed and dotted-dashed lines correspond to the blob and core components of the two-component model, respectively. Credit: Vandad Fallah Ramazani.

Edwards, 2014), which corresponds to $R_{\text{core}} \leq 3.3 \times 10^{19}$ cm, assuming a flat universe and $z \simeq 0.41$ (Kotilainen et al., 2011).

- The size of the blob can be constrained from the shortest variability time scales observed as $R \leq \delta c\tau / (1 + z)$, where δ is the Doppler factor and τ the variability time scale observed.
- The bulk Lorentz factor of the core region is limited to 4, which is typical for TeV blazars (Piner and Edwards, 2018). The bulk Lorentz factor is then converted to Doppler factor assuming a jet viewing angle $\sim 1/\Gamma$ and thus $\delta \sim \Gamma$.
- The magnetic field strength of the core can be estimated from the very-long-baseline-interferometry “core shift” measurements (Pushkarev et al., 2012) or considering the cooling timescale of the electrons from the variability time scale in

Table 6.7: SED modeling parameters for one-component SSC and two-component models.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Epoch	Model (region)	γ_{\min} ($\times 10^3$)	γ_b ($\times 10^4$)	γ_{\max} ($\times 10^5$)	n_1	n_2	B (G)	K ($\times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$)	R ($\times 10^{15} \text{ cm}$)	Γ	U'_B/U'_e
E1	one-comp	5.8	2.1	6.5	2.0	3.1	0.16	2.0	34	18	0.39
	2-comp (blob)	4.5	1.9	5.5	2.0	2.9	0.16	1.0	38	18	0.82
	2-comp (core)	0.2	2.2	0.4	2.0	2.4	0.16	0.04	720	4	12.09
E2	one-comp	7.0	6.3	3.4	2.02	3.6	0.16	2.5	34	18	0.23
	2-comp (blob)	5.0	6.5	3.1	2.04	3.25	0.16	2.5	35	17	0.27
	2-comp (core)	0.18	2.2	0.4	2.0	4.6	0.16	0.04	790	4	5.96
E3	one-comp	4.0	9.4	3.9	2.07	2.9	0.18	3.9	34	18	0.30
	2-comp (blob)	9.5	9.5	5.7	2.08	3.7	0.16	2.1	37	23	0.49
	2-comp (core)	0.21	2.2	0.4	2.0	4.6	0.16	0.04	770	4	6.14
E4	one-comp	2.5	4.7	5.0	2.0	3.12	0.16	4.5	30	17	0.09
	2-comp (blob)	9.5	5.5	6.7	2.08	3.6	0.16	7.5	29	20	0.16
	2-comp (core)	0.19	2.2	0.4	2.0	4.6	0.16	0.04	770	4	6.02

Columns: (1) Observation campaign/state. (2) Model (emission region). (3), (4) and (5) Minimum, break and maximum electron Lorentz factor. (6) and (7) Slopes of electron distribution below and above γ_b . (8) Magnetic field strength. (9) Electron density. (10) Emission-region size. (11) Bulk Lorentz factor. (12) Ratio between the energy density of the magnetic field and the relativistic electrons.

the X-ray band (Bhatta et al., 2018; Acciari et al., 2021a). Such observations are not available for the source. Therefore, we follow the same assumption employed in MAGIC Collaboration et al. (2020a) (i.e., $0.1 \leq B \leq 0.4$ G and similar for core and blob).

The parameters of both the core and blob for the different two-component models of 1ES 0647+250 are reported in Table 6.7, and the models are displayed in Fig. 6.10. We can only set constraints on the size of the blob through the X-ray variability during 2020, with variability on time scales as short as one day. Considering the minimum and maximum Lorentz factors derived for the blobs, this leads to a blob size $R \leq 3.1 \times 10^{16} - 4.2 \times 10^{16}$ cm. For previous epochs, the variability time scales are longer; thus, the blob size can also adopt higher values. As for the one-component model, the fit is evaluated by visual inspection after scanning the parameters describing the broadband emission. All the two-component models can reproduce the broadband emission of our source satisfactorily. The comparison and interpretation of both models with the rest of the results from this study are discussed in Section 6.8.

Table 6.8: Results of the SED modeling for one-component SSC and two-component models.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
Epoch	Model (region)	L_B	L_e ($\times 10^{43}$ erg s $^{-1}$)	L_p	L_{jet}	$\log P_B$	$\log P_e$	$\log P_p$ (erg s $^{-1}$)	$\log P_{\text{jet}}$
E1	one-comp	4.79	12.3	1.06	18.1	43.55	43.96	43.96	44.34
	2-comp (core)	106.1	12.04	8.81	127.0	44.89	43.80	43.80	44.95
E2	one-comp	4.79	21.2	1.30	27.3	43.55	44.20	44.20	44.55
	2-comp (core)	127.8	21.49	23.55	172.8	44.97	44.19	44.19	45.09
E3	one-comp	6.07	20.1	2.09	28.3	43.66	44.18	44.18	44.54
	2-comp (core)	121.4	19.82	19.15	160.4	44.95	44.16	44.16	45.07
E4	one-comp	3.33	36.9	5.46	45.7	43.39	44.44	44.44	44.76
	2-comp (core)	121.4	20.1	21.19	162.7	44.95	44.17	44.17	45.07

Columns: (1) Observation campaign/state. (2) Model (emission region). (3), (4), and (5) Kinetic power of the magnetic field, electrons and cold protons, respectively (for the core in the case of the two-component model). (6) Total kinetic power of the jet. (7), (8) and (9) Jet power carried by the jet in the form of magnetic field, electrons and cold protons, respectively. (10) Total power carried by the jet.

6.8 Discussion

This manuscript reports the first detailed study of the broadband emission from radio to VHE gamma rays for the blazar 1ES 0647+250. The study uses a data set from 2009 to 2020, which allows the evaluation of the multi-band variability and correlations over one decade. For this, along with the observations performed by the MAGIC telescopes, we make use of radio data from OVRO, several optical telescopes (KVA, LT, LCOGT, and PIRATE), observations performed by *Swift* and its instruments UVOT in the optical and UV regime, and XRT in the X-rays, and HE gamma-ray data from *Fermi*-LAT. In the following subsections, we discuss the results reported in previous sections.

Variability

The variability analysis for this source reveals that its broadband emission is variable during the monitored period. The maximum of F_{var} appears at X-ray and VHE gamma-ray wavelengths, as shown in Figure 6.3. The minimum time scale detected in these bands with significant variability ($> 5\sigma$, see Table 6.2) was one day in X-rays, only during the flaring state of E4. Moreover, when using a 30-day binning for all bands, no significant difference is observed in the behavior of F_{var} , which is consistent with the fact that the variability is dominated by the long-term variations of the contribution from a common component (see correlation analysis).

The fact that F_{var} has its maximum in X-rays has been related in the past with a higher dominance of the synchrotron emission (Aleksić et al., 2015a). This structure of F_{var} can reveal fundamental differences related to the particle populations and processes producing the broadband emission in blazars. Aleksić et al. (2015a) find a similar F_{var} structure in Mrk 421 to the one shown by 1ES 0647+250. One can compare its behavior with that reported for Mrk 501 by Ahnen et al. (2017) or Aleksić et al. (2015b), where F_{var} increases with the frequency, reaching its maximum at the VHE gamma-ray band. In the typical one-component model framework, the X-ray emission is mainly generated by high-energy electrons. On the contrary, the VHE gamma-ray emission is due to a combination of low-energy and high-energy electrons in Thomson and Klein-Nishina regimes, respectively (Abdo et al., 2011). Thus, a higher F_{var} in the X-ray domain, as for the case of 1ES 0647+250, may indicate higher variability of the high-energy electron population. In contrast, the combined low- and high-energy electron distribution may dominate during the gamma-ray flares, leading to a high F_{var} in VHE gamma rays.

Correlation and contribution of the two components

Several studies found long-term correlations between the optical and radio emission of different sets of blazars, with the optical emission leading the radio counter-part by a few hundred days (e.g., Hufnagel and Bregman, 1992; Tornikoski et al., 1994; Hanski et al., 2002; Ramakrishnan et al., 2016; Acciari et al., 2021b). Here, we detect a correlation between the radio and optical emission of 1ES 0647+250, with the optical contribution leading the radio one by 398 days, and between the radio and HE gamma-ray emission, with the gamma rays leading the radio by about 393 days. These correlations have been detected at $\gtrsim 3\sigma$ level, in line with the studies mentioned above. Additionally, a correlation between the optical and gamma-ray emission was found with a time lag compatible with zero. Due to the long-term nature of the flux variability that leads to the correlations reported here, multi-year data sets are needed to increase the statistical significance of these results.

Hufnagel and Bregman (1992) interpreted these correlations as physically related regions, however, on different time scales. This has also been stated by other authors (e.g., Zhang et al., 2017), and the time lags are interpreted as different cooling times between the electrons responsible for the radio and optical emissions (Bai and Lee, 2003). Another plausible explanation is that the radio emission comes from an outer region but is triggered by the same physical mechanisms as the optical and gamma-ray emissions. Max-Moerbeck et al. (2014a) explains this behavior as due to the different

opacities for the radio and gamma-ray wavelengths to become observable. Under this scenario, we can estimate the distance between the radio and gamma-ray emitting regions using Eq. 1 from [Max-Moerbeck et al. \(2014a\)](#). For this estimation, we use the value of the bulk Lorentz factor $\Gamma = 4$ obtained from the core of the two-component SED modeling. The Doppler factor δ is then obtained from the Lorentz factor assuming the approximation of $\delta \sim \Gamma$ for a viewing angle $\theta \sim 1/\Gamma$. The redshift value of $z = 0.41 \pm 0.06$ from [Kotilainen et al. \(2011\)](#) was used. We obtain for a time lag of -393 ± 40 days a distance $d = 3.6 \pm 0.4$ pc. We also estimated the distances for changes on Lorentz factors by a factor of 2 ($\Gamma = 2$ and $\Gamma = 8$) as a conservative comparison of the derived value of d for different values of Γ , obtaining distances of $d = 0.8 \pm 0.1$ pc, and $d = 14.9 \pm 1.7$ pc, respectively. Under this interpretation, the radio and MWL emissions would come from physically separated regions. [Tramacere et al. \(2022\)](#) presents another plausible interpretation in the one-component model scenario, in which the delay between the radio and MWL emissions would be driven by an adiabatic expansion of the emitting region during its propagation along the jet. This expansion leads to a shift of the synchrotron self-absorption frequency to values comparable to or lower than the frequency of the radio emission.

We also searched for correlations at shorter time scales, finding no significant correlated emission between the radio, optical, and HE gamma-ray bands. For this purpose, we detrended the common-varying component from the light curves relying on the fact that the overall emission comes from a combination of a mutual and an independent component (see [Lindfors et al., 2016](#)). We estimated the contribution of this common component to the emission for each pair of light curves. The values found for the radio-optical, radio-gamma-ray, and optical-gamma-ray pairs were 0.53, 0.23, and 0.24, respectively. These values are compatible with those reported by [Lindfors et al. \(2016\)](#) for this source.

The existence of a common component for the different bands, and the fact that the emission is uncorrelated after subtracting this contribution, suggests that the multi-year variations are driven by the same mechanism and produced in a common emitting region. The two-component model would be favored in this scenario, as the emission would not come from physically separated emitting regions. On the other hand, the variations in the sub-year timescale would be due to the components that do not have a common emission process. This outcome would agree with the results presented by [Ramakrishnan et al. \(2016\)](#), who state that long-term variations and intense flares are correlated between the radio and optical bands in blazars. Additionally, marginal evidence of the correlation between radio and gamma-ray emission was also reported

by these authors. [Ramakrishnan et al. \(2016\)](#) also reports a robust optical-gamma-ray correlation for a set of blazars, compatible with the results found for 1ES 0647+250. We note, however, that this blazar sample is mainly composed of FSRQs, indicating that these correlations may be present in both low- and high-peaking blazars. Finally, [Liodakis et al. \(2018, 2019\)](#) find significant long-term correlations between the radio, optical and gamma-ray bands for more than 100 sources on a sample of 178 blazars, including several HBLs. The optical and gamma-ray emission generally shows time lags compatible with zero, while the radio emission is usually delayed by a few hundred days. Moreover, they also found that variability on shorter timescales is not necessarily correlated with detecting a significant fraction of optical and gamma-ray orphan flares.

Spectral analysis results

The spectral analysis on the X-ray data of 1ES 0647+250 reveals different behaviors for the observing epochs. During the low state, a clear harder-when-brighter trend between the X-ray flux and the spectral index was observed. X-ray brightening in HBLs has been related in the past to spectral hardening rather than to an overall flux enhancement ([Giommi et al., 2021](#)), leading to the commonly observed harder-when-brighter evolution for BL Lac objects (see, e.g., [Pian et al., 1998](#); [Acciari et al., 2011b](#); [Aleksić et al., 2013](#); [Kapanadze et al., 2014](#); [Baloković et al., 2016](#); [Wang et al., 2018](#); [MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2021b](#)). Several conjectures have been proposed to explain such a trend. A possible explanation could be a hardening or softening of the electron distribution responsible for the synchrotron emission, leading to a hardening (softening) trend with the increasing (decreasing) flux ([Xue et al., 2006](#)). This effect could also be due to an increase in the maximum electron energy or a shift of the synchrotron peak towards higher frequencies ([Abeysekara et al., 2017](#)). However, this latter effect is not evident in the different broadband SEDs.

Moreover, no hardening or softening of the X-ray spectrum was observed during the flares registered. However, the faintest observations from E3, performed after the MAGIC VHE detection, display again the hardening of the spectrum with the flux increase. On the other hand, the brightest observations and closest to the flare show a relatively constant index, which could indicate the presence of a spectral index saturation during this flare. This behavior has also been reported in [Acciari et al. \(2021b\)](#) for Mrk 421, which shows a harder-when-brighter behavior for an extensive range of X-ray fluxes. However, it displays a saturation for the very high (and very low) X-ray fluxes ([Acciari et al., 2021b](#)). In this case, saturation is present in both the X-ray and VHE bands.

We also searched for hysteresis processes in the X-ray evolution of the observed flares. These processes have been detected during flares for several blazars, both in X-rays and gamma rays (e.g., [Nandikotkur et al., 2007](#); [Abeysekara et al., 2017](#); [Wang et al., 2018](#)). These processes provide unique information regarding the acceleration, cooling, and energy loss time scales ([Böttcher and Chiang, 2002](#)), or possible lags between hard and soft X-rays ([Wang et al., 2018](#)). Nonetheless, no evidence of hysteresis processes was found in the X-ray spectral analysis of 1ES 0647+250.

Concerning the gamma-ray band, we do not detect any harder- or softer-when-brighter trend in the long-term variability of 1ES 0647+250. Although the harder-when-brighter trend has been seen in the past also in the HE and VHE gamma-ray domains for some blazars (e.g., [Acciari et al., 2011a](#); [Abeysekara et al., 2017](#); [MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2021b](#)), it has not been systematically observed. Authors like [Nandikotkur et al. \(2007\)](#) or [Abdo et al. \(2010\)](#) did not find clear correlations between the hardness index and the gamma-ray flux of HBLs. However, our results may be biased by the wide binning of the *Fermi*-LAT and MAGIC data.

Comparison of one-component and two-component models

Both models can reproduce the MWL emission from 1ES 0647+250 at face value. The one-component and two-component models explain the broadband SEDs with a magnetic field of $B = 0.16$ G, except for the one-component model from E3. The latter needs a slightly higher magnetic field ($B = 0.18$ G) due to the high dominance of the synchrotron emission over the SSC scattering after the most increased X-ray flux detected for this source. In this case, a magnetic field of $B = 0.16$ G cannot reproduce the broadband emission satisfactorily, leading to considerable differences between the model and the data regardless of the values of the other parameters of the model. These values agree with the characteristic magnetic fields derived for BL Lacs through a one-component SED modeling by [Ghisellini et al. \(2010\)](#), with $B \sim 0.05 - 1$ G. Moreover, the Lorentz factor of the one-component model is similar to or lower than that of the blob of the two-component, while the core shows a relatively small gamma. [Ghisellini et al. \(2010\)](#) infer $\Gamma \sim 10 - 20$ for a large sample of BL Lacs, compatible with those used in this work to reproduce the broadband emission. Furthermore, the Lorentz factors and the parameters describing the distribution of the electron population γ_b and γ_{max} are also compatible with those derived by these authors.

The one-component model reproduces the broadband emission from the optical regime up to VHE gamma rays. However, it cannot explain the radio emission with its emitting region. This is in line with the results obtained through the correlation

analysis, where the radio was found to be delayed relative to the optical and gamma-ray emission. Since the radio photons suffer from strong absorption in the inner regions of the jet, this emission is most likely generated in the outer part of the jet. Thus the one-component model does not reproduce the radio emission since this emission is not co-spatial.

On the other hand, the two-component can naturally reproduce the emission of 1ES 0647+250 from radio to VHE gamma rays with co-spatial blob and core regions. In this framework, the core provides seed photons for the inverse Compton (IC) scattering occurring in the blob. The core dominates the emission from radio to optical wavelengths. At the same time, the blob is the main contributor to the emission from X-rays to VHE gamma rays, consistent with the results found in [MAGIC Collaboration et al. \(2020a\)](#). This leads to higher γ_{min} values for the blob, as shown in Table 6.7.

Using a two-component model that reproduces the radio is consistent with the long-term slow trend displayed by 1ES 0647+250. The derived sizes suggest variability timescales shorter than those obtained for the slowly varying component from the data. This means that the slow variability cannot be caused by core-size or acceleration/-cooling processes which are generally assumed as the origin of the faster variability but instead traces, for instance, injection or decay phases of the core engine.

Equipartition and jet power

We have calculated the contributions of the magnetic and electron energy densities (see Table 6.7). For the one-component model, [Tavecchio and Ghisellini \(2016\)](#) show that, for BL Lacs, the magnetic energy density is typically 1-2 orders of magnitude lower than the electron energy density. Here, we found that, except for the model derived for 2020 flare, the parameters suggest the existence of equipartition within a factor of a few. This result agrees with the results presented by [Nievas Rosillo et al. \(2022\)](#), where one-component models have been used to reproduce the broadband emission of a sample of HBLs/EHBLs. [Tavecchio and Ghisellini \(2016\)](#) also note that it is possible to reproduce the observed SEDs of BL Lacs assuming equipartition between both energy densities when assuming two-component scenarios. However, other studies based on two-component models, e.g., for TXS 1515-273 ([Acciari et al., 2021a](#)) show that these models can lead to solutions close to equipartition during low activity states as reported by [Tavecchio and Ghisellini \(2016\)](#), although this does not seem to be always possible, especially during flares.

In the case of two-component models, we found that for the core component, the magnetic energy density is dominant over the electron energy density in all cases by

one order of magnitude. This ratio for the blob components is similar to that from the one-component model. However, the magnetic and electron energy density ratio is closer to equipartition, which is expected since the blob component is much denser and filled with more-energetic particles than the core. We calculated the equipartition value for the system of two interacting regions using equations 5, 9, 16, and A1 from [Tavecchio and Ghisellini \(2016\)](#). The energy ratios carried out by the magnetic field to that by electrons are 38, 0.3, 1.1, and 0.3 for the E1, E2, E3, and E4 data sets. This is in line with the VHE gamma-ray state of the source during these epochs. During E1, the source was in a low state when comparing its X-ray and VHE gamma-ray emission with other periods. Therefore, the contribution of energy carried by the electrons is far less than that of the magnetic field. This is reflected in the equipartition values of the whole system as well. It is also evident that during this period, a larger amount of emission in the VHE gamma-ray band comes from the interaction between the components. Such a contribution is smaller for the other periods where the emission from the blob dominates the VHE gamma-ray emission.

We also estimated the kinetic energy carried by protons, electrons, and the magnetic field of the emitting region. Assuming the simple solution with one proton per injected electron, we used Eqs. 1 to 3 of [Celotti and Ghisellini \(2008\)](#). The results are shown in Table 6.8, columns (3), (4), and (5). For the one-component model, we find that L_e is about one order of magnitude higher than L_B , as expected from the results reported by [Celotti and Ghisellini \(2008\)](#) for a much larger population of blazars. This comes from the fact that for BL Lacs, the high-energy emission is in the same order as the synchrotron contribution, and SSC scattering is the only radiative process involved. For the case of the core in the two-component models, we found that the kinetic energy carried by protons, electrons, and the magnetic field is higher than the one obtained in the one-component model.

Finally, we also estimated the power carried by the jet using Equation 6 from [Ghisellini et al. \(2009\)](#). This estimation was made again under the assumption of one proton per electron, thus, $P_e \sim P_p$. The estimated values are shown in Table 6.8 along with the total jet power. The results derived from the one-component model suggest that the power carried by electrons (and protons) tends to be higher than that of the magnetic field. In the context of SSC models, this is a signature characteristic of BL Lacs, where almost all the power of the jet is producing the observed radiation. The values obtained here are also compatible with those estimated for a large sample of BL Lacs, as reported in Figure 4 from [Ghisellini et al. \(2010\)](#). The values derived from the two-component model are also compatible with those reported by these authors.

However, in this case, we observed a higher power carried by the magnetic field, in contrast with the lower value for the one-component model.

6.9 Conclusions

For the first time, we have presented a detailed study of the broadband emission from radio to VHE gamma-ray band for the BL Lac object 1ES 0647+250 between 2009 and 2020. The main results of this study are summarized as follows:

- The MWL emission is variable on long timescales, with an increasing trend in radio, optical, and gamma-ray emission. This behavior is consistent with variations in the conditions of the accretion disc, as also reported for other blazars (e.g., 1ES 1215+303, [Valverde et al., 2020](#)). While this interpretation applies to the 11-year data set from 1ES 0647+250, more data would be necessary to confirm or rule out this hypothesis entirely.
- A long-term correlation with no delay is measured between the optical and gamma-ray emission at a confidence level of $\sim 3\sigma$. The radio is correlated with the optical and gamma-ray bands (at the level of 3σ and 4σ significance) with time lags of 393 ± 40 days and 398 ± 80 days, respectively. This time delay is compatible with the radio emission originated in a distinct region of the jet, at a distance of $d = 3.6 \pm 0.4$ pc, assuming $\Gamma = 4$, $\delta \sim \Gamma$ and $\theta = 1/\Gamma$.
- A harder-when-brighter behavior in the X-ray spectra is observed during the low state and for the flare from 2019 (E3), followed by a spectral index saturation in the latter case. No clear relation is observed in the gamma-ray domain.
- We estimated the redshift of this object by comparing its simultaneous GeV and TeV spectra under the influence of the EBL absorption during a flaring activity using the method described in [Prandini et al. \(2010\)](#), yielding a value of $z = 0.45 \pm 0.05$, which agrees with previous measurements reported in the literature.
- The broadband SED is modeled within one- and two-component leptonic scenarios in each epoch, namely the low activity in 2009–2011 (E1) and three flaring activities in the years 2014 (E2), 2019 (E3) and 2020 (E4). All the models use a magnetic field of about $B = 0.16$ G, and the energy loss of the electron population is dominated by synchrotron emission (needed to match the high X-ray

flux and spectra collected during the different epochs). The model parameters required by the two theoretical scenarios to describe the broadband SEDs are similar to those from typical BL Lacs reported in [Ghisellini et al. \(2010\)](#), and [Tavecchio and Ghisellini \(2016\)](#) for a large sample of objects.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

In this thesis, I have worked on different aspects of high-energy astrophysics that can be divided into two main parts: technical and scientific. This dualism reflects the usual way of working in this field, especially influenced by the context nowadays: the current generation of mature VHE instruments is eager for scientific exploitation, whereas the just-born new generation of IACT needs more software and hardware technical effort.

On the technical side, I have contributed to developing MC simulation software, key for the characterization of the response of the detectors and the reconstruction of the signals recorded by these instruments. I have also collaborated in developing analysis software for the new generation of Cherenkov telescopes. Finally, I have also participated in the validation of the performance of the first LST that will be part of CTA. On the other hand, on the scientific side, I have worked on studying and characterizing the multiwavelength emission of the blazar 1ES 0647+250. The conclusions of each of these four points are discussed below.

7.1 Fluorescence relevance in the Cherenkov technique

We implemented the atmospheric fluorescence emission in the CORSIKA code similarly to the Cherenkov light production. Based on this development, we quantified the fluorescence relevance in the signals recorded by ground-based air-Cherenkov telescopes, so far ignored in the reconstruction of EASs.

Due to the very different angular distributions of these two light components, the Cherenkov one dominates within the light pool. Besides, the fluorescence contribution is strongly suppressed in telescopes with a narrow FoV, such as IACTs. We find that the fluorescence contamination is, as expected, negligible at a few hundred meters from the impact point. However, it starts being significant ($> 5\%$) at a core distance of 1000 m. Thus ignoring this effect would impact VHE gamma-ray observations carried out by kilometer-scale arrays of IACTs that collect measurable signals at large core distances, such as the future CTA. Our systematic simulation study reveals that the fluorescence contamination in IACTs is nearly independent of the shower energy and somewhat dependent on the zenith angle for a given distance to the shower core. We also found that off-axis observations lead to an increase in fluorescence contamination.

In contrast, our simulations indicate that arrays of WACDs are strongly affected by fluorescence contamination, particularly for the highest energy showers. In the PeV

region, the signals of detectors located 1000 m from the shower core can contain up to 45% fluorescence.

In future work, we plan to implement the fluorescence emission in the new CORSIKA8 code, currently in development, making it available for detailed simulations of IACTs and arrays of WACDs working at conditions where fluorescence contamination is expected to be non-negligible. In these cases, fluorescence should be accounted for in end-to-end shower and instrument simulations to avoid systematics of a few percent because of not completely neglecting the fluorescence component. Finally, the implementation in the CORSIKA framework and the complementary semi-analytical modeling tool, ShowerModel, will allow for a detailed investigation of the feasibility of using an array of IACTs in fluorescence mode.

7.2 Development of the on-site analysis pipeline for LST-1

The on-site analysis pipeline for the LST-1, `1stosa`, has been a helpful tool during the commissioning phase of the telescope prototype. Thanks to this pipeline, we have automated the data processing of the massive amount of observations collected daily with the telescope, close to 3 Petabytes at the time of writing, providing reduced data to the rest of the LST Collaboration. This standardization has facilitated the handling the low-level processing, minimizing potential human errors and also making efficient use of the computational capacity of the on-site data center.

On the one hand, the on-site data processing framework has allowed us to perform the next-day data reduction daily, within a few hours the day after data taking. This has been particularly helpful for promptly performing preliminary high-level analyses and obtaining a first estimate of the emission status of sources undergoing flaring periods. In these cases, time is critical to accordingly schedule multiwavelength follow-up observations with enough time. In addition, especially important during the commissioning period, the next-day processing of the data has also helped quickly spot problems so that experts could fix them as soon as possible. The on-site analysis pipeline has been especially important for the LST-1 as no real-time analysis has been available yet. On the other hand, the on-site analysis system has been a crucial tool for several large-scale reprocessing of the entire sample of observations taken by the LST-1 each time the analysis library significantly improved.

Further developments could improve the system with new capabilities, such as an automatic fast high-level analysis. Finally, some lessons could be highlighted from our work regarding the future data processing framework that CTAO will use:

- We propose to use existing tools for handling analysis pipelines. They should be extensible and configurable.
- The pipeline for processing the observed data should be closely connected to the one orchestrating the analysis of the MC simulations, as both data are related. MC simulations must be produced and adjusted according to the observations.
- The metadata is an essential input argument for the analysis because they help to automate the data processing.
- Implement a good provenance system for the data products to ensure traceability and reproducibility.

7.3 Performance of the LST-1 from Crab Nebula observations

This work describes the first study of the single-telescope performance of the LST-1. It is based on MC simulations and data from Crab Nebula observations carried out during the commissioning phase of the telescope prototype. The reduction of observed data was made with the LST-1 on-site analysis pipeline developed in this thesis. The simulated data was fine-tuned according to the Crab observations reaching an excellent agreement between them essential to obtain a satisfactory comprehension of its performance.

The analysis energy threshold is estimated to be about 30 GeV and is therefore sensitive to the low energies for which it was designed within the CTA scheme. We assess the telescope's performance by using two analysis approaches: source-dependent and source-independent methods. Instrument response functions from both analyses are comparable, except for the energy resolution, which is significantly better in the source-dependent case near the energy threshold. Both analysis types give similar flux sensitivities, about 1.5 times worse on average than the MAGIC telescopes. This discrepancy is expected as we compare a single telescope's performance to a stereo system with substantially better reconstruction capabilities.

Finally, the computed spectrum of the Crab Nebula using both analyses is consistent with that reported by other instruments within statistical and systematic uncertainties.

We note that in cases of Crab-like sources observed during a long period, systematic uncertainty dominates over the statistical. At the lowest energies (below 100 GeV), the systematic uncertainty from the background normalization is especially noticeable. The light curve above 100 GeV also agrees with the value reported in the literature when 5% systematic uncertainty in the flux values is considered.

This work will serve as a benchmark and reference for any standard analysis performed on other sources observed by the LST-1. The analysis of observations under different conditions, such as higher zenith angles or higher NSB, needs further and dedicated studies. Moreover, a more detailed investigation of the systematic uncertainties of the LST-1 data analysis is required.

Considering all the above, the LST-1 has performed reliably during its first years of operation. We conclude that the telescope is ready to produce scientific results, especially in extragalactic gamma-ray astrophysics, in whose energy domain the sensitivity of LSTs is centered.

7.4 Long-term MWL characterization of the BL Lac object 1ES 0647+250

We describe a new and comprehensive study of the MWL emission from blazar 1ES 0647+250, one of the few distant gamma-ray blazars detected at VHE. Based on the decade of MWL observations, we find that its emission is variable on long timescales, with a significant multiyear flux increase in radio, optical, and gamma-ray bands. This finding might hint at an increasing activity in the accretion rate.

We found indications of correlation at the $3-4\sigma$ level between radio, optical and gamma-ray emissions, with no delay between optical and gamma-ray bands. However, a delay of several hundred days is found between the radio emission and the two other components, which suggests that the radio emission would have occurred in a different jet region.

Regarding the redshift of this object, whose value is still under discussion, we also present a convincing estimate of the redshift of this source by comparing its simultaneous GeV and TeV spectra under the influence of the EBL absorption. The redshift inferred, $z = 0.45 \pm 0.05$, is consistent with previous measurements.

Finally, we modeled the SED in four snapshots centered on the MAGIC observing campaigns, the first during low VHE gamma-ray activity and the other three during short flaring episodes. The broadband spectra can be characterized with one- and

two-component leptonic models whose resulting physical parameters are comparable to those of other previously observed BL Lac objects.

Appendix A

Analysis of other blazars within MAGIC Collaboration

Aside from the work presented in Chapter 6 on the study of the MWL emission of the blazar 1ES0647+250 after decade-long monitoring, I have been involved in the analysis of gamma-ray data taken by MAGIC from 1ES 1959+650 and BL Lacertae, two well-known blazars in the TeV sky.

Regarding the BL Lac 1ES 1959+650 object, during a substantial time of my thesis, I participated in the yearly monitoring proposal for this source to use the data collected in a multiwavelength study. The blazar 1ES 1959+650, one of the most intense sources in the high-energy regime, can be observed even under intense moon conditions. Because of this advantage, this source has been one of the most regularly observed by the MAGIC telescopes for several years. After a few years of data collected from 1ES 1959+650 with more than 300 elapsed hours since 2016, we decided to freeze the data set to work on a publication gathering also MWL data observed in that period. I worked together mostly with Shunsuke Sakurai and Daniela Dorner on this project, as well as other collaborators in charge of providing the data from other instruments. However, the project did not go through. The amount of VHE data to be analyzed and the different periods and conditions in which they were taken made the analysis enormously complicated. We eventually needed more workforce to carry out the project. In my case, due to the other time-consuming duties and projects in which I was involved at that time, I could not devote more time to push the project forward. We nonetheless presented some preliminary results at an international conference [MAGIC Collaboration et al. \(2021a\)](#). They are summarized in Sect. [A.1](#).

Finally, part of the work that mainly Ph.D. students do regularly within the extragalactic physics working group is the fast next-day analysis of sources in a possible high-emission state. The observations of these sources were triggered within the

ToO program of MAGIC. Other instruments alert the MAGIC collaboration of flaring sources suggesting follow-up observations. People in charge of this task (nicknamed “flare advocates”) share the workload, alternating every month. Sometimes the alerts result in observations of flaring sources, mainly blazars¹, ending up with interesting data sets for publications.

During the time I was in charge of the next-day high-level analysis of flaring sources, we detected a flaring episode from BL Lacertae during a few days in May 2019. Several other flaring episodes were followed up in the subsequent months. Later, we arranged to publish this data set and simultaneously multiwavelength collected from other instruments.

A.1 1ES 1959+650

1ES 1959+650 (R.A. $19^{\text{h}}59^{\text{m}}59.8^{\text{s}}$, Dec. $65^{\circ}8'55''$, J2000.0) is one of the nearest ($z = 0.048$, [Perlman et al., 1996](#)) and brightest HBL emitting in VHE gamma-ray band. It is among the first TeV blazars detected roughly 20 years ago by [Nishiyama et al. \(1999\)](#), and therefore it is one of the most studied BL Lacs. HBLs, 1ES 1959+650 among them, are considered as possible neutrino emitters. The detection of a neutrino candidate was reported by [Halzen and Hooper \(2005\)](#) coincidentally with a gamma-ray flare in the absence of X-rays contemporaneous enhancement activity, which pointed towards hadronic acceleration scenarios. Later on, the source underwent a period of extreme activity in 2016, reaching more than 3 C.U. ([MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2020b](#)) – its highest flux level since the major outburst in 2002 ([Aharonian, F. et al., 2003](#)). During the 2016 flare, intra-night variability at sub-hour scales was found. Searches for neutrino candidates coincidental with the location of 1ES 1959+650 during this major flare were conducted without success ([Kintscher et al., 2017](#)).

We present here the long-term MWL dense monitoring of 1ES 1959+650 in the last few years (Section [A.1.1](#)). Subsequently, we present the preliminary results by comparing its different flux states to those reported on the unusual 2016 VHE flare.

A.1.1 Multi-wavelength observations and analysis

1ES 1959+650 was monitored by several instruments along the entire electromagnetic spectrum. We describe next the different MWL observations included in this work.

¹Also alerts from GRBs, detection of astrophysical neutrino candidates and gravitational waves.

MAGIC: MAGIC has been densely observing 1ES 1959+650 since 2016 for more than 300 hours, although there are previous sparser observations. MAGIC data included in this work are from 2015 to 2019. We only consider observations carried out with low NSB and in the range of zenith angles 35-50 degrees which allow for safely establishing an energy threshold of 300 GeV for the MAGIC light curve. The bulk of the data set was collected under several moon-brightness conditions. This fact makes the analysis considerably more difficult as IRFs need to be produced for all the combinations of zenith angles, NSB level, and period of observation with stable conditions such as light collection efficiency. The data analysis was done using MARS (Zanin et al., 2013; Aleksić et al., 2016).

FACT: 1ES 1959+650 has been densely monitored by FACT. From 2015 to 2019, 1830 hours of physics data were collected. The energy threshold for the light curve is about 700 GeV. The temporal binning chosen was mixed, that is, nightly for 2016 and wider bins for the rest of the observations during the low state of the source. Data were analyzed using the Modular Analysis, and Reconstruction Software Bretz and Dorner (2010).

Fermi-LAT: LAT (Atwood et al., 2009) is one of the instruments installed on the *Fermi* Gamma-ray Space Telescope, launched on 11 June 2008. The energy range covered by LAT is between 20 MeV and 300 GeV. LAT monitors the entire sky every three hours. We performed the binned likelihood analysis of the data from 24 November 2016 (MJD: 57716) to 6 December 2019 (MJD: 58823) in the energy range 0.3-300 GeV using 3-day and 7-day binning.

Swift-XRT and Swift-UVOT: The Neil Gehrels *Swift* Observatory was designed for Gamma-Ray Burst observations and had been operating since 2004. The XRT (Burrows et al., 2004) observes in the energy range 0.2-10 keV. The UVOT (Roming et al., 2005) performs simultaneous observation with XRT using ultraviolet and optical band filters (UVW1, UVM2, UVW2, and U, B, V, respectively) covering the wavelength range 170-650 nm. Both instruments onboard the Neil Gehrels *Swift* satellite have regularly observed 1ES 1959+650, resulting in a good observations coverage for the period studied here.

Tuorla observatory: 1ES 1959+650 was regularly observed in the optical R-band as part of the Tuorla blazar monitoring program² with the 60 cm telescope KVA also located on La Palma. Data were analyzed as described in [Nilsson et al. \(2018\)](#).

OVRO: We collected radio data at 15 GHz with the OVRO 40-m telescope. The observations and data reduction were performed following the procedure detailed in [Richards et al. \(2011\)](#).

The long-term MAGIC light curve ($E > 300$ GeV) from the source monitoring is presented in Fig. [A.1](#). The observing period spans from 2015 to 2019. We identified several flux states of the source. Apart from the unprecedented outburst that happened in 2016 (see [MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2020b](#)), there were three flaring episodes in 2015, 2017, and 2018 in which 1ES 1959+650 reached Crab-like flux levels. On the other hand, the observations from 2019 displayed a steadily low-flux state at the level of about 0.2 C.U.. The flux values from the 2016 observations ([MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2020b](#)) are also included for comparison.

Furthermore, the rest light curves from the MWL observations described above are presented in Fig. [A.2](#). We first note that the extreme gamma-ray flare in 2016 was not followed in other energy bands, whereas in 2017, the flare in VHE gamma rays was accompanied by high states in X-ray, UV, optical, and radio bands. This behavior results in a change of dominance between the synchrotron and inverse Compton emission components in the broadband SED.

On the other hand, during the VHE low-flux state in 2019, the activity in the optical to radio bands was enhanced. To compare the large flaring state from 2016 with the low-activity period in VHE gamma rays from 2019, we selected a period representative of this low-flux state for which there were contemporaneous MAGIC and *Swift* observations (i.e., August 2019).

The integral flux from this data sample is presented in Table [A.1](#) and compared to the exceptional flux from the 2016 flare when the source reached more than 3 C.U.. We also characterized the VHE gamma-ray SED from this period. The spectral parameters assuming a power-law function are presented in Table [A.1](#). The corresponding values from the 2016 flare are also shown for comparison. VHE gamma-ray spectra from MAGIC observations were de-absorbed using the EBL model described in [Domínguez et al. \(2011\)](#).

A detailed description of these results, including variability, correlation, and theoretical interpretation of the broadband emission, paying particular attention to the

²<http://users.utu.fi/kani/1m/>

Figure A.1: 1ES 1959+650 light curve (1-day binning) above 300 GeV from MAGIC observations (taken under low NSB) from 2015 to 2019 (preliminary). The flux from the Crab Nebula (Aleksić et al., 2015c) is depicted for reference by the dashed line. Data points from 2016 (grey) were already published in MAGIC Collaboration et al. (2020b).

Table A.1: MAGIC flux integrated above 300 GeV and fit spectral parameters from August 2019 SED (values are preliminary). Integral flux and spectral parameters from 13 June 2016 when the source was flaring (MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2020b) are also included for comparison.

Date	Flux ($E > 300$ GeV) [C.U.]	f_0 [$\text{TeV}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]	E_0 [TeV]	Spectral index
2016-06-13	3.4 ± 0.1	$(1.81 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-9}$	0.3	-2.00 ± 0.02
August 2019	0.12 ± 0.01	$(4.9 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-11}$	0.4	-2.5 ± 0.1

Figure A.2: MWL light curves from all the instruments indicated in section A.1.1. From top to bottom: VHE gamma rays from FACT ($E_{\text{Th}} \sim 700$ GeV). HE gamma rays with energies in the range 0.3-300 GeV from *Fermi*-LAT. X-rays in the energy range 0.3-10 keV from *Swift*-XRT. Optical and UV observations in different bands by *Swift*-UVOT. Optical data in R band centered at 658 nm from Tuorla observatory. The bottom panel shows radio observations at 15 GHz from OVRO.

evolution of the emission between high and low flux states, will be reported in a future publication.

A.2 BL Lacertae

BL Lacertae is the prototypical example of blazars that are named after it, those not showing strong features in their optical spectra if any. Attending to the position of the synchrotron peak, it is usually classified as an intermediate-energy-peaked (IBL) or low-energy-peaked BL Lac object (LBL). It is located at R.A. $22^{\text{h}}2^{\text{m}}43.3^{\text{s}}$, Dec. $42^{\circ}16'40''$ (J2000.0) and has a redshift of $z = 0.0686$ (Miller and McGimsey, 1978). BL Lacertae is well known for being a highly variable blazar in several energy bands (see, e.g., Weaver et al., 2020; MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2019), first detected in the VHE gamma-ray band by MAGIC (Albert et al., 2007b). In a recent publication, MAGIC Collaboration et al. (2019) describe the characterization of the broadband emission from BL Lacertae during a flaring episode in 2015.

The genesis of this project is a flare in VHE gamma rays detected by MAGIC in early May 2019 (Mirzoyan, 2019a), reaching around 30% of the Crab Nebula flux above 300 GeV. MAGIC observations were triggered because of high-flux activity in the HE gamma-ray band and increased flux reported in the optical R-band the previous days. The episode of high activity lasted only a few days, returning the source to being undetectable in the VHE gamma-ray domain. Subsequent episodes of HE gamma-ray flares occurred in the next months. The MAGIC telescopes followed up on these alerts, failing to detect the source, even though the state of the source in the LAT band was comparable to that of the initial detection in VHE gamma rays.

Several months later, BL Lacertae underwent a period of high variability, showing historically maximum flux values in the VHE and HE gamma-ray and optical bands during 2020 and 2021 (see, e.g., Kunkel et al., 2021; Buson and de Menezes, 2021). Moreover, we detected the source in one of these brightening periods in the VHE gamma-ray band with the LST-1 in July 2021 (Cortina and CTA LST Collaboration, 2021). Although not from an unusual flaring activity, this milestone detection has been the first official scientific report to the astronomical community from a telescope that will be part of the future CTA observatory.

In this project, we focused on the multi-wavelength BL Lacertae observations collected from March 2019 to March 2020, which led to the detection of a flare in VHE gamma rays and enhanced flux states in other wavebands.

Figure A.3: MAGIC light curve of BL Lacertae (1-day binning) integrated above 300 GeV. In the case of non-detections upper limits (95% C.L.) are shown.

A.2.1 Multi-wavelength observations and analysis

For this study, data from different instruments have also been compiled across the electromagnetic spectrum, from the radio band to VHE gamma rays. Starting at the highest energies, MAGIC observations can be grouped into three different periods: May 2019 (five days), July 2019 (six days), and December 2019 (one day) to January 2020 (five days). Most of the data were collected up to roughly 62° zenith angle and under dark NSB conditions. However, some were taken under moderate moon brightness, requiring special treatment, which includes a harder image cleaning and IRFs generated accordingly. Data were reconstructed and analyzed using MARS (Zanin et al., 2013; Aleksić et al., 2016). All things considered, we established an analysis energy threshold of 300 GeV for the computation of the MAGIC light curve.

The source was significantly detected ($> 5\sigma$ level of significance based on Li and Ma, 1983) only during the first three days of the campaign in May 2019. It was detected ($\gtrsim 5\sigma$) during the first observation of 45 minutes of live exposure. Stacking the data of those first five days (live exposure of 5.1 hours), we reached 22.6σ detection significance. Later, in July 2019, the source was not significantly detected. Stacking the data taken during those six days (3.9 hours), we ended up with 4.0σ , hence only a hint of detection. MAGIC did not detect the source either (1.5σ) in the third epoch's observations elapsed over 4.2 hours. Figure A.3 presents the MAGIC light curve of all the observations considered in this work.

Zooming in on the time interval when the MAGIC telescopes detected the source, we can see an asymmetry between the time of flux rise and decay. Even with such a few data points, we try to quantify these timescales by fitting the light curve to a piecewise exponential function:

$$F(t) = F_0 \exp\left(-\frac{|t - t_{\text{peak}}|}{t_{\text{raise,decay}}}\right), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Figure A.4: Rise and decay timescales of the May 2019 BL Lacertae VHE gamma-ray flare detected by MAGIC.

with t_{raise} for $t < t_{\text{peak}}$ and t_{decay} for $t > t_{\text{peak}}$. The resulting parameters reported in Fig. A.4 indicate day-scale variations, with the flux increasing by about a factor of 3. Aside from that, we did not find significant intra-night variability on shorter timescales in any of the three nights with the highest flux. BL Lacertae showed intra-night variability in a flare that happened in 2015, with a flux halving time of around 30 minutes (MAGIC Collaboration et al., 2019), and in 2016 detected by VERITAS (see Abeyssekara et al., 2018), also with rise-and-decay timescales of hours. The timescale of these flux variations is critical in the blazar context as it provides constraints on the size of the emitting region (see Dermer et al., 2008; Levinson, 2009).

Data from *Fermi*-LAT were analyzed using *Fermipy* (v1.2 Wood et al., 2021), selecting events inside the energy range 0.1 - 300 GeV within a search radius of 10° centered at BL Lacertae coordinates. Maximum likelihood fitting performed includes the Galactic and isotropic diffuse emission models (`gll_iem_v07.fits` and `iso_P8R3_SOURCE_V3_v1.txt`, respectively). For the one-year-long light curve calculation from March 2019 to March 2020, we use 1-day temporal binning.

Reduced data from other wavelengths are provided by external collaborators. Most of the analysis details are comparable to those described already in Sect. 6.2, hence to avoid duplication, some of the details are omitted here. X-ray data in the energy range 0.3-10 keV from the *Swift*-XRT (Burrows et al., 2004) were taken during this period, split into four campaigns, two concurrent with MAGIC observing periods in May and July 2019. Fluxes are corrected for Galactic absorption. Optical R-band data were collected by the blazar monitoring program from Tuorla Observatory (Nilsson et al., 2018), using the KVA telescope. Moreover, much denser observations in the optical R-

band were performed by the Whole Earth Blazar Telescope (WEBT) ³. Collaborators from POLAMI (Polarimetric Monitoring of AGN at Millimetre Wavelengths) program [Agudo et al. \(2017\)](#) provided us with millimeter data (at 3.5 and 1.3 mm) from the IRAM 30 m telescope, including flux densities and polarimetric measurements. Finally, radio data were collected by two radio telescopes, 14 m dish Metsähovi ([Terasranta et al., 1992](#)) at 37 GHz and 40 m telescope OVRO ([Richards et al., 2011](#)) at 15 GHz.

Completing the MWL picture, Fig. A.5) shows the light curves from these other instruments covering the three MAGIC observing periods considered in this work. We see that in all bands, there are evident flux variations. In addition, different episodes of high activity are located in different bands. In the gamma-ray band, the flare in VHE is delayed a few days with respect to the flare occurring in the HE band. In the rest of the wavelengths, the flux is not exceptionally enhanced. In July 2019, there was a flare in X-rays, accompanied by an increased state in HE gamma rays, not exceptionally high at other wavelengths. Also, at the end of January 2020, the highest flux in the optical range in this period coincides with high fluxes in radio, and convulsive enhanced in HE gamma rays. With this collection of light curves covering the electromagnetic spectrum in mind, we can characterize their broadband emission in different screenshots over the year-long duration of this project, testing, for example, the same emission mechanism scenarios considered in [MAGIC Collaboration et al. \(2019\)](#). This further study will be published elsewhere.

³<https://www.oato.inaf.it/blazars/webt/>

Figure A.5: BL Lacertae MWL light curves (1-day binning) from March 2019 to March 2020. From top to bottom: MAGIC (> 300 GeV), *Fermi*-LAT (0.1-300 GeV), *Swift*-XRT (0.3-10 keV), WEBT and Tuorla observatory (optical R-band), IRAM (1.3 and 3 mm, including polarimetry), Metsähovi (37 GHz) and OVRO (15 GHz). Light-shaded areas indicate the MAGIC observing campaigns. Darker areas depict shorter snapshots of enhanced emission states. They were selected considering the availability of simultaneous multi-band data that could be used to extract the broadband SED for each state.

Appendix B

Stay at Whipple observatory: VERITAS and pSCT-CTA

During my 3-month stay at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Astrophysical Observatory (FLWO), part of the Harvard-Smithsonian center for astrophysics, I worked together with the VERITAS and Prototype Schwarzschild-Couder Telescope (pSCT) collaborations, whose telescopes are located in this observatory.

On one side VERITAS (see description in [Holder et al., 2006, 2008](#)), an IACT array system consisting of four Cherenkov 12 m diameter telescopes (see Fig. [B.1](#)), has been observing the TeV gamma-ray sky since 2007, following the experience of Whipple 10 m telescope ([Kildea et al., 2007](#)), the pioneer in VHE gamma-ray field using the Cherenkov technique.

Figure B.1: VERITAS telescopes at FLWO basecamp located in southern Arizona. The control building is located in the middle of the array. Credit: VERITAS/NSF.

On the other hand, pSCT is part of the new generation of Cherenkov telescopes. It is a prototype telescope with novel technology proposed to be one of the telescopes comprising the future CTAO. A summary of pSCT specifications can be found in Table

1.1. The pSCT’s dual reflector system boost its optical PSF enabling better angular resolution and has a finely-pixelated camera based on SiPM detectors with 8° wide FoV.

Throughout these three months, I participated in the nightly operation shifts of the VERITAS telescopes for several weeks, mainly devoted to gamma-ray sources observations. These regular operations are conducted during the darker phases of the moon periods. To carry out the observations, the on-site crew is usually in touch with more experienced VERITAS members, who also decide daily the observation schedule depending on conditioning factors such as the source proposal category and weather conditions. On-site shifters are in charge of setting up the telescopes at the beginning of the shift and checking that none of the telescopes’ subsystems is out of order so the telescopes can be operated safely. Then, during the night, we help with setting up the camera PMTs’ high voltage, the observing configuration for each source, changing the telescope target, and monitoring that observations are being carried out without hiccups.

On the other hand, I participated in stellar intensity interferometry observations, whose objective is to infer the diameter of stars, typically in the order of one milli-arcsecond. This technique takes advantage of the VERITAS telescopes, with a baseline of about hundreds of meters, adapted with minimal additional recording instrumentation. This program has been successfully conducted for a few years, as reported in [Abeysekara et al. \(2020\)](#), reviving a field that had gone quiet for several decades. In contrast to the regular gamma-ray operations, these optical observations are done instead during bright moon periods. We used a different detection setup, consisting of a different single PMT with an interferometric filter placed on top of each camera. The narrow bandpass filter allows observations even under bright conditions when gamma-ray observations are not feasible. Digitized starlight signals by each of the telescopes are correlated among them, and the resulting measurements can, in turn, be used to infer the angular size of stars.

Aside from night observations, I also worked on daily hardware maintenance tasks helping the telescope personnel and specialists. One of the projects was diagnosing problematic camera pixels of the VERITAS telescopes. These pixels with persistent problems might significantly distort the image reconstruction. The aim of this identification was that, later, we could inspect the possible hardware causes of these faulty pixels and fix them. For this task, I used one of the analysis and reconstruction software developed by the collaboration, `Eventdisplay` ([Maier and Holder, 2017](#)), to inspect

the camera events from the flasher runs taken nightly. These runs are taken by illuminating the camera uniformly with a diffused light source of known properties from which we expect to detect “healthy” traces or waveforms. The causes of defective pixels can be varied, e.g., very bright stars, problems with high voltage, digitization problems in FADC boards, loose cable connection to the PMTs, and deteriorated quantum efficiency. Each problem is manifested by specific parameters: the current and voltage measured in the PMTs, the shape of the digitized pulses, and whether they lie within the expected time window. In another project I got involved in, I assisted with the inspection and replacement of defective electronic components of an uninterruptible power supply system used to provide a stable source of electricity to the electronic components of the telescope cameras.

Figure B.2: Distribution of charges in an event from a flasher run taken with VERITAS telescope 1 trying to spot problematic pixels.

Finally, I also participated in several activities related to the commissioning of the pSCT. This telescope prototype, inaugurated in 2019, detected the gamma-ray emission from the Crab Nebula in early 2020 (Adams et al., 2021), even having a camera not entirely populated with silicon PMTs modules as in its final configuration. These activities have consisted of performing calibration tests of its camera, such as rate scans, used to assess the adequate trigger threshold for reading out Cherenkov events with the highest rate possible, avoiding as many accidental triggers as possible due to NSB. I also helped diagnose some of the defective actuators responsible for focusing panels that comprise the segmented mirror of the telescope, which happened to have communication problems.

Figure B.3: *Left:* overview of the pSCT proposed for the future CTAO. The telescope prototype is also based at FLWO, near the VERITAS array. *Right:* Close-up look of the secondary mirror facing the camera (inside the red box between the two reflectors) and the primary dish. The actuators of the mirror panels can be seen below the primary dish (lower side of the image).

In conclusion, it has been a fruitful stay that has enriched my knowledge of the operation and maintenance of atmospheric imaging Cherenkov telescopes. Until this stay, I had only participated in the operation and data acquisition with the MAGIC

and LST-1 telescopes. Thanks to the operation of VERITAS I have been able to verify the differences between both experiments. In addition, at FLWO I have participated for the first time in maintenance tasks, seeing the daytime part for the first time, which is especially important for astronomical observations to be carried out smoothly, minimizing the time lost due to faulty equipment.

Acronyms

ADC Analog-to-Digital Converter.

AGN Active Galactic Nuclei.

AMC active mirror control.

API application programming interface.

C.U. Crab units.

CI continuous integration.

CI/CD continuous integration and continuous delivery.

CTA Cherenkov Telescope Array.

CTAO Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory.

DAQ data acquisition system.

DPPS Data Processing and Preservation System.

DRS4 Domino Ring Sampler 4th generation.

EAS extensive air shower.

EBL extragalactic background light.

EC external Compton.

ECSV enhanced character separated values.

EVB Event Builder.

FEFS Fujitsu Scalable Cluster File System.

FLWO Fred Lawrence Whipple Astrophysical Observatory.

FoV field of view.

FSRQ Flat Spectrum Radio Quasars.

GPS Global Positioning System.

GRB gamma-ray burst.

H.E.S.S. High Energy Stereoscopic System.

HAWC High-Altitude Water Cherenkov Observatory.

HBL high-synchrotron peaked BL Lac object.

HE high-energy.

IACT Imaging Atmospheric Cherenkov Telescope.

IC inverse Compton.

INFN-CNAF National Center for Frame Analysis of the Italian Institute for Nuclear Physics.

IRF Instrument Response Function.

IVOA International Virtual Observatory Alliance.

KVA Kungliga Vetenskapsakademien.

LAT Large Area Telescope.

LED light-emitting diode.

LHAASO Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory.

LIDAR Light Detection and Ranging system.

LST-1 Large-Sized Telescope prototype.

MAGIC Major Atmospheric Gamma Imaging Cherenkov telescopes.

MARS MAGIC analysis and reconstruction software.

MC Monte Carlo.

MWL multiwavelength.

NSB night sky background.

ORM Observatorio del Roque de los Muchachos.

OSA onsite analysis.

OVRO Owens Valley Radio Observatory.

p.e. photoelectrons.

PIC Port d'Informació Científica.

PMT photo-multiplier tube.

PPS pulse per second.

pSCT Prototype Schwarzschild-Couder Telescope.

PSF point spread function.

PWN pulsar wind nebulae.

reST reStructuredText.

RF random forest.

RMS root mean squared.

ROI region of interest.

RTA real-time analysis.

SAG science alert generation.

SED spectral energy distribution.

SLURM Simple Linux Utility For Resource Management.

SSC self-synchrotron Compton.

SWGGO Southern Wide-field Gamma-ray Observatory.

TAI International Atomic Time.

TCU telescope control unit.

TIB Trigger Interface Board.

ToO time of opportunity.

UCTS Unified Clock and Trigger System.

UTC Coordinated Universal Time.

UVOT Ultra-Violet and Optical Telescope.

VERITAS Very Energetic Radiation Imaging Telescope Array System.

VHE very-high-energy.

W3C World Wide Web Consortium.

WEBT Whole Earth Blazar Telescope.

XRT X-Ray Telescope.

List of Figures

1.1	Sources in the VHE gamma-ray sky	3
1.2	Crab nebula and pulsar broadband spectral energy distribution.	4
1.3	Overview of AGN unification model.	5
1.4	Components of a cosmic-ray initiated extensive air shower.	7
1.5	Comparison of simulated air showers (seen sideways) initiated by protons and gamma rays.	8
1.6	Cherenkov effect.	9
1.7	Cherenkov light pool.	10
1.8	Cherenkov light spectrum.	11
1.9	Nitrogen molecular levels responsible for the air-fluorescence.	12
1.10	Air fluorescence spectrum measured by AIRFLY.	13
1.11	Photograph of MAGIC telescopes.	17
1.12	Rendering of CTA telescopes.	19
1.13	CTA layout for the North and South arrays.	20
1.14	Differential flux sensitivity of both CTA arrays.	22
1.15	Photograph of the LST-1.	23
1.16	Module of 7 photo-multiplier tubes that composes the LST-camera.	24
1.17	Overview of the LST IT onsite data center and other subsystems net- worked to it.	26
2.1	Workflow diagram of CORSIKA.	31
2.2	Longitudinal distribution of deposited energy from all the shower com- ponents.	33
2.3	Schematic view of particle transportation between interaction points (step) and generation of bunches of Cherenkov and fluorescence photons.	34
2.4	Schematic view of a spherical detector mimicking an IACT in CORSIKA.	35
2.5	Output format according to the selected compiling options.	38

2.6	Geometry and coordinate system adopted in the simulations of Cherenkov and fluorescence light in CORSIKA.	39
2.7	Averaged spatial distributions of Cherenkov (left) and fluorescence (right) light on ground from 10 TeV γ -ray vertical showers.	39
2.8	Radial distributions of Cherenkov and fluorescence light obtained after averaging the 2D distributions of Fig. 2.7 over azimuth angle.	40
2.9	Air shower as seen by an IACT separating the Cherenkov and fluorescence components.	41
2.10	Lateral profiles of Cherenkov and fluorescence photons on the ground and fluorescence contamination as a function of the impact point.	42
2.11	The same as Fig. 2.10, but for IACTs with two hypothesis of FoV: 10° and 20° , and on-axis observation.	44
2.12	Fluorescence contamination as a function of the shower energy and core distance for WACDs.	45
2.13	The same as Fig. 2.12, but for IACTs with a FoV of 10° centered at the arrival shower direction.	46
2.14	Fluorescence contamination as a function of zenith angle and x distance for WACDS with FoV of 60° in the vertical direction. Results were obtained for 100 TeV γ -ray showers.	47
2.15	The same as Fig. 2.14, but for IACTs with a FoV of 10° centered at the arrival shower direction.	47
2.16	Fluorescence contamination as a function of telescope off-axis angle and x distance for IACTs with a FoV of 10°	49
2.17	Shower track projections of an air shower observed by a fluorescence telescope and signal produced from the Cherenkov and fluorescence light components modeled by <code>ShowerModel</code>	50
2.18	Cherenkov and fluorescence photon densities at ground level.	51
2.19	Air shower observed by an observatory of 6 telescopes. Green dots mark the telescope positions and their relative signal sizes.	51
2.20	Camera images of an air shower observed by an array of six IACTs.	52
2.21	Schematic representation of an imaging Cherenkov telescope operating in <i>fluorescence mode</i>	53
3.1	Uncalibrated waveforms from a given event for all the pixels of an LST camera (left) and two single pixels with and without shower signal (right).	56

3.2	DL1a and DL1b information: example of a calibrated image of an event in the LST camera.	57
3.3	Scheme of some of the Hillas parameters obtained from a cleaned camera image.	58
3.4	Data reduction flow scheme for the LST-1 low-level analysis.	60
3.5	Scheme of the wobble observation mode.	63
3.6	Gammapy analysis workflow.	66
3.7	Overview of the MAGIC analysis pipeline.	68
3.8	Example of θ^2 distribution from MAGIC observations.	70
3.9	Example of sky map from MAGIC observations.	71
3.10	Example of effective area calculation and migration matrix.	71
3.11	Example SED and light curve from MAGIC observations.	72
4.1	Assessment of the timestamp validity in LST-1.	79
4.2	Web site of the <code>cta-1stchain</code> documentation.	83
4.3	General workflow of <code>1stosa</code>	85
4.4	Data processing monitoring of <code>1stosa</code>	87
4.5	LST-1 analysis flow within <code>1stosa</code>	89
4.6	W3C provenance model concept.	91
4.7	Website of the <code>1stosa</code> documentation.	93
4.8	LST-1 observing time during the commissioning period.	94
4.9	Time elapsed and memory usage in LST-1 on-site analysis jobs.	95
4.10	Time devoted by <code>1stosa</code> for next-day data processing.	96
5.1	Distribution of intensity of shower images for the LST-1.	105
5.2	Pointing directions for simulating the training nodes and testing nodes for LST-1 Crab analysis.	109
5.3	Overall optical throughput of the LST-1 from muon ring analysis.	110
5.4	Importance of the features used to train each Random Forest model for LST-1 Crab analysis.	113
5.5	LST-1 analysis energy threshold.	114
5.6	Comparison of θ^2 distribution from gamma-ray excess in simulations and Crab Nebula observations with LST-1.	116
5.7	Comparison of gammaness distributions from LST-1 simulated and observed events.	118
5.8	Comparison of length and width distributions from LST-1 simulated and observed shower events.	118

5.9	LST-1 IRFs as a function of the efficiency of the gamma-ray selection. . .	120
5.10	LST-1 IRFs as a function of the zenith angle.	121
5.11	LST-1 differential flux sensitivity.	123
5.12	Energy-dependent gammaness and θ selection cuts based on gamma-ray efficiency for LST-1 observations.	125
5.13	Search for pivot energy for Crab Nebula SED model fitting from LST-1 observations.	126
5.14	Crab Nebula SED from LST-1 observations during its commissioning phase.	128
5.15	Crab Nebula spectrum as measured by <i>Fermi</i> -LAT, LST-1 and LHAASO.	129
5.16	LST-1 Crab Nebula SED before and after trigger setting updates.	130
5.17	Crab Nebula light curve above 100 GeV from LST-1 observations.	131
5.18	Phaseogram of the Crab pulsar from LST-1 observations.	132
6.1	θ^2 distributions of the signal detection for 1ES 0647+250.	139
6.2	MWL light curves of 1ES 0647+250.	143
6.3	Fractional variability for 1ES 0647+250 MWL light curves.	146
6.4	ZDCF inter-band correlation for 1ES 0647+250.	148
6.5	Detrending of the baseline slow-varying component from 1ES 0647+250 light curves.	150
6.6	Power-law spectral index (α_{XRT}) vs X-ray flux for the different observing epochs of 1ES 0647+250.	152
6.7	VHE gamma-ray SED from MAGIC observations in each observing epoch.	154
6.8	Joint fit of <i>Fermi</i> -LAT and MAGIC spectra to constrain 1ES 0647+250 redshift.	156
6.9	Likelihood profile of the joint fit of HE and VHE gamma-ray SED from <i>Fermi</i> -LAT and MAGIC observations for constraining 1ES 0647+250 redshift.	156
6.10	Broadband SEDs of 1ES 0647+250 characterized by the one-component and two-component SSC emission models.	159
A.1	Light curve from 1ES 1959+650 MAGIC observations.	180
A.2	MWL light curves from 1ES 1959+650 multi-instrument observations.	181
A.3	MAGIC light curve of BL Lacertae above 300 GeV (May 2019 to January 2020).	183
A.4	Rise and decay of the BL Lacertae flare in May 2019.	184
A.5	BL Lacertae MWL light curves (March 2019 to March 2020).	186

B.1	VERITAS telescopes at FLWO (Arizona).	187
B.2	Spotting problematic pixels in the camera of one of the VERITAS telescopes using a flasher run.	189
B.3	Prototype Schwarzschild-Couder Telescope for CTA at FLWO	190

List of Tables

1.1	Specifications of CTA telescopes.	18
5.1	Settings of the LST-1 MC simulations.	107
5.2	Image parameters used as input for training the Random Forest models for LST-1 Crab analysis.	113
5.3	Spectral parameters of the best-fit log-parabola model for the source- independent analysis of the Crab Nebula with LST-1.	127
5.4	Covariance matrix for the best-fit parameters indicated in Table 5.3 for the LST-1 solo fit.	127
6.1	Detection significance and integrated gamma-ray flux ($E > 100$ GeV) from the four MAGIC observing epochs of 1ES 0647+250.	138
6.2	χ^2 -statistic of the steady-flux hypothesis for each light curve in Fig. 6.2.	145
6.3	Cross-correlation and time lags between wavebands and for 1ES 0647+250.	149
6.4	Spectral parameters of the X-ray band considering a power law.	151
6.5	Spectral parameters of the HE gamma-ray spectra from <i>Fermi</i> -LAT data.	153
6.6	Spectral parameters of the VHE gamma-ray spectra from MAGIC data.	154
6.7	SED modeling parameters for one-component SSC and two-component models.	160
6.8	Results of the SED modeling for one-component SSC and two-component models.	161
A.1	MAGIC flux integrated above 300 GeV and fit spectral parameters from August 2019 1ES 1959+650 SED.	180

Bibliography

- Simulation of the fluorescence detector of the Pierre Auger Observatory. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 545(3):632–642, 2005. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:[10.1016/J.NIMA.2005.01.346](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NIMA.2005.01.346).
- Abdalla, H. et al. The H.E.S.S. Galactic plane survey. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 612:A1, 2018. ISSN 0004-6361. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201732098](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201732098).
- Abdo, A.A. et al. Fermi/large area telescope bright gamma-ray source list. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 183:46, 2009a. ISSN 0067-0049. doi:[10.1088/0067-0049/183/1/46](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/183/1/46).
- Abdo, A.A. et al. *FERMI* OBSERVATIONS OF TeV-SELECTED ACTIVE GALACTIC NUCLEI. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 707(2):1310–1333, 2009b. doi:[10.1088/0004-637x/707/2/1310](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637x/707/2/1310).
- Abdo, A.A. et al. *FERMI* LARGE AREA TELESCOPE FIRST SOURCE CATALOG. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 188:405, 2010. ISSN 0067-0049. doi:[10.1088/0067-0049/188/2/405](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/188/2/405).
- Abdo, A.A. et al. Spectral Properties of Bright Fermi-Detected Blazars in the Gamma-Ray Band. *Astrophysical Journal*, 710(2):1271–1285, 2010. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/710/2/1271](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/710/2/1271).
- Abdo, A.A. et al. Fermi Large Area Telescope Observations of Markarian 421: The Missing Piece of its Spectral Energy Distribution. *Astrophysical Journal*, 736(2):131, 2011. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/736/2/131](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/736/2/131).
- Abdollahi, S. et al. Fermi Large Area Telescope Fourth Source Catalog. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 247(1):33, 2020. doi:[10.3847/1538-4365/ab6bcb](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ab6bcb).

- Abdollahi, S. et al. Incremental Fermi Large Area Telescope Fourth Source Catalog. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 260:53, 2022. ISSN 0067-0049. doi:[10.3847/1538-4365/ac6751](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ac6751).
- Abeyssekara, A. et al. Sensitivity of the high altitude water Cherenkov detector to sources of multi-TeV gamma rays. *Astroparticle Physics*, 50-52:26–32, 2013. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2013.08.002>.
- Abeyssekara, A.U. et al. Observation of the Crab Nebula with the HAWC Gamma-Ray Observatory. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 843(1):39, 2017. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aa7555](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa7555).
- Abeyssekara, A.U. et al. A Search for Spectral Hysteresis and Energy-dependent Time Lags from X-Ray and TeV Gamma-Ray Observations of Mrk 421. *Astrophysical Journal*, 834(1):2, 2017. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/834/1/2](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/834/1/2).
- Abeyssekara, A.U. et al. Multiwavelength Observations of the Blazar BL Lacertae: A New Fast TeV Gamma-Ray Flare. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 856(2):95, 2018. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aab35c](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aab35c).
- Abeyssekara, A.U. et al. Demonstration of stellar intensity interferometry with the four VERITAS telescopes. *Nature Astronomy*, 4:1164–1169, 2020. doi:[10.1038/s41550-020-1143-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-020-1143-y).
- Abraham, J. et al. Properties and performance of the prototype instrument for the Pierre Auger Observatory. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 523(1):50–95, 2004. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2003.12.012>.
- Abu-Zayyad, T. et al. The surface detector array of the Telescope Array experiment. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 689:87–97, 2012. doi:[10.1016/j.nima.2012.05.079](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2012.05.079).
- Acciari, V.A. et al. TeV and Multi-wavelength Observations of Mrk 421 in 2006-2008. *Astrophysical Journal*, 738(1):25, 2011a. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/738/1/25](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/738/1/25).
- Acciari, V.A. et al. Multiwavelength Observations of the Very High Energy Blazar 1ES 2344+514. *Astrophysical Journal*, 738(2):169, 2011b. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/738/2/169](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/738/2/169).

- Acciari, V.A. et al. Measurement of the extragalactic background light using MAGIC and Fermi-LAT gamma-ray observations of blazars up to $z = 1$. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 486(3):4233–4251, 2019. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stz943](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz943).
- Acciari, V.A. et al. First detection of VHE gamma-ray emission from TXS 1515-273, study of its X-ray variability and spectral energy distribution. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 507(1):1528–1545, 2021a. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stab1994](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab1994).
- Acciari, V.A. et al. Multiwavelength variability and correlation studies of Mrk 421 during historically low X-ray and γ -ray activity in 2015-2016. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 504(1):1427–1451, 2021b. doi:[10.1093/mnras/staa3727](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa3727).
- Acciari, V.A. et al. Investigating the Blazar TXS 0506+056 through Sharp Multiwavelength Eyes During 2017-2019. *Astrophysical Journal*, 927(2):197, 2022. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/ac531d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac531d).
- Acharyya, A. et al. Monte Carlo studies for the optimisation of the Cherenkov Telescope Array layout. *Astroparticle Physics*, 111:35–53, 2019. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2019.04.001>.
- Ackermann, M. et al. The First Fermi-LAT Catalog of Sources above 10 GeV. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 209(2):34, 2013. doi:[10.1088/0067-0049/209/2/34](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/209/2/34).
- Adams, C. et al. Detection of the Crab Nebula with the 9.7 m prototype Schwarzschild-Couder telescope. *Astroparticle Physics*, 128:102562, 2021. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2021.102562>.
- Adams, C. B. et al. The throughput calibration of the VERITAS telescopes. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 658:A83, 2022. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202142275](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202142275).
- Agudo, I. et al. POLAMI: Polarimetric Monitoring of AGN at Millimetre Wavelengths – I. The programme, calibration and calibrator data products. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 474(2):1427–1435, 2017. ISSN 0035-8711. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stx2435](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx2435).
- Aharonian, F. et al. Construction and on-site performance of the LHAASO WFCTA camera. *European Physical Journal C*, 81(7):657, 2021. doi:[10.1140/epjc/s10052-021-09414-z](https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-021-09414-z).

- Aharonian, F. et al. Detection of TeV gamma-rays from the BL Lac 1ES 1959+650 in its low states and during a major outburst in 2002. *A&A*, 406(1):L9–L13, 2003. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:20030838](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20030838).
- Ahnen, M. et al. Performance of the MAGIC telescopes under moonlight. *Astroparticle Physics*, 94:29–41, 2017. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2017.08.001>.
- Ahnen, M.L. et al. Multiband variability studies and novel broadband SED modeling of Mrk 501 in 2009. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 603:A31, 2017. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201629540](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201629540).
- Ahnen, M.L. et al. Extreme HBL behavior of Markarian 501 during 2012. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 620:A181, 2018. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201833704](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833704).
- Albert, A. et al. Science Case for a Wide Field-of-View Very-High-Energy Gamma-Ray Observatory in the Southern Hemisphere. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1902.08429, 2019. doi:[10.48550/arXiv.1902.08429](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1902.08429).
- Albert, J. et al. Unfolding of differential energy spectra in the MAGIC experiment. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 583(2):494–506, 2007a. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2007.09.048>.
- Albert, J. et al. Discovery of very high energy -ray emission from the low-frequency-peaked BL lacertae object BL lacertae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 666(1):L17–L20, 2007b. doi:[10.1086/521550](https://doi.org/10.1086/521550).
- Albert, J. et al. Implementation of the random forest method for the imaging atmospheric cherenkov telescope magic. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 588(3):424–432, 2008. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2007.11.068>.
- Aleksić, J. et al. Gamma-ray Excess from a Stacked Sample of High- and Intermediate-frequency Peaked Blazars Observed with the MAGIC Telescope. *Astrophysical Journal*, 729(2):115, 2011. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/729/2/115](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/729/2/115).
- Aleksić, J. et al. The simultaneous low state spectral energy distribution of 1ES 2344+514 from radio to very high energies. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 556:A67, 2013. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201220714](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201220714).

- Aleksić, J. et al. First broadband characterization and redshift determination of the VHE blazar MAGIC J2001+439. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 572:A121, 2014. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201424254](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201424254).
- Aleksić, J. et al. The 2009 multiwavelength campaign on Mrk 421: Variability and correlation studies. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 576:A126, 2015a. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201424216](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201424216).
- Aleksić, J. et al. Multiwavelength observations of Mrk 501 in 2008. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 573:A50, 2015b. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201322906](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201322906).
- Aleksić, J. et al. Measurement of the Crab Nebula spectrum over three decades in energy with the MAGIC telescopes. *Journal of High Energy Astrophysics*, 5:30–38, 2015c. doi:[10.1016/j.jheap.2015.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jheap.2015.01.002).
- Aleksić, J. et al. The major upgrade of the MAGIC telescopes, Part II: A performance study using observations of the Crab Nebula. *Astroparticle Physics*, 72:76–94, 2016. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2015.02.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2015.02.005).
- Alexander, T. Improved AGN light curve analysis with the z-transformed discrete correlation function. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1302.1508, 2013.
- Aliu, E. et al. Improving the performance of the single-dish Cherenkov telescope MAGIC through the use of signal timing. *Astroparticle Physics*, 30(6):293–305, 2009. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2008.10.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2008.10.003).
- Anchordoqui, L. et al. High energy physics in the atmosphere: phenomenology of cosmic ray air showers. *Annals of Physics*, 314(1):145–207, 2004. ISSN 0003-4916. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aop.2004.07.003>.
- Arakawa, M. et al. Detection of Small Flares from the Crab Nebula with Fermi-LAT. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 897(1):33, 2020. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/ab9368](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab9368).
- Arqueros, F., Blanco, F. and Rosado, J. Analysis of the fluorescence emission from atmospheric nitrogen by electron excitation, and its application to fluorescence telescopes. *NJP*, 11(6):065011, 2009a. ISSN 13672630. doi:[10.1088/1367-2630/11/6/065011](https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/11/6/065011).

- Arqueros, F., Blanco, F. and Rosado, J. Analysis of the fluorescence emission from atmospheric nitrogen by electron excitation, and its application to fluorescence telescopes. *New Journal of Physics*, 11(6):065011, 2009b. doi:[10.1088/1367-2630/11/6/065011](https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/11/6/065011).
- Astropy Developers. Astropy: ECSV Format, <https://docs.astropy.org/en/stable/io/ascii/ecsv.html>.
- Atwood, W.B. et al. The Large Area Telescope on the Fermi Gamma-Ray Space Telescope Mission. *Astrophysical Journal*, 697(2):1071–1102, 2009. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/697/2/1071](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/697/2/1071).
- Ave, M. et al. Measurement of the pressure dependence of air fluorescence emission induced by electrons. *Astroparticle Physics*, 28(1):41–57, 2007. ISSN 09276505. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2007.04.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2007.04.006).
- Bai, J.M. and Lee, M.G. Radio/X-Ray Offsets of Large-Scale Jets Caused by Synchrotron Time Lags. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 585(2):L113–L116, 2003. doi:[10.1086/374304](https://doi.org/10.1086/374304).
- Baloković, M. et al. Multiwavelength Study of Quiescent States of Mrk 421 with Unprecedented Hard X-Ray Coverage Provided by NuSTAR in 2013. *Astrophysical Journal*, 819(2):156, 2016. doi:[10.3847/0004-637X/819/2/156](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/819/2/156).
- Benbow, W. The VERITAS Blazar Key Science Project. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:0908.1412, 2009.
- Bernlöhr, K. Simulation of imaging atmospheric Cherenkov telescopes with CORSIKA and sim_telarray. *Astroparticle Physics*, 30(3):149–158, 2008. ISSN 09276505. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2008.07.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2008.07.009).
- Bertaina, M.E. An overview of the JEM-EUSO program and results. *PoS, ICRC2021*: 406, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0406](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0406).
- Bhatta, G., Mohorian, M. and Bilinsky, I. Hard X-ray properties of NuSTAR blazars. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 619:A93, 2018. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201833628](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833628).
- Blanch, O. MAGIC measures high flux state from the blazar 1ES0647+250. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 14268:1, 2020.

- Bock, R.K. et al. Methods for multidimensional event classification: A case study using images from a cherenkov gamma-ray telescope. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 516:511–528, 2004. ISSN 01689002. doi:[10.1016/J.NIMA.2003.08.157](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NIMA.2003.08.157).
- Boháčová, M. Study of the air fluorescence by airfly. *Nuclear Physics B - Proceedings Supplements*, 190:266–271, 2009. ISSN 0920-5632. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nuclphysbps.2009.03.098>. Proceedings of the Cosmic Ray International Seminars.
- Bose, D. et al. Galactic and extragalactic sources of very high energy gamma rays. *European Physical Journal Special Topics*, 231(1):27–66, 2022. doi:[10.1140/epjs/s11734-022-00434-8](https://doi.org/10.1140/epjs/s11734-022-00434-8).
- Böttcher, M. and Chiang, J. X-Ray Spectral Variability Signatures of Flares in BL Lacertae Objects. *Astrophysical Journal*, 581(1):127–142, 2002. doi:[10.1086/344155](https://doi.org/10.1086/344155).
- Böttcher, M. et al. Leptonic and Hadronic Modeling of Fermi-detected Blazars. *Astrophysical Journal*, 768(1):54, 2013. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/768/1/54](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/768/1/54).
- Breeveld, A.A. et al. An Updated Ultraviolet Calibration for the Swift/UVOT. In McEnery, J.E., Racusin, J.L. and Gehrels, N., editors, *Gamma Ray Bursts 2010*, volume 1358 of *American Institute of Physics Conference Series*, pages 373–376, 2011. doi:[10.1063/1.3621807](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3621807).
- Breiman, L. *Machine Learning*, 45(1):5–32, 2001, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1010933404324>.
- Bretz, T. and Dorner, D. MARS - CheObs ed. – A flexible Software Framework for future Cherenkov Telescopes. In Leroy, C. et al, editors, *Astroparticle, Particle and Space Physics, Detectors and Medical Physics Applications*, pages 681–687, 2010. doi:[10.1142/9789814307529_0111](https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814307529_0111).
- Brown, T.M. et al. Las Cumbres Observatory Global Telescope Network. *The Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 125(931):1031, 2013. doi:[10.1086/673168](https://doi.org/10.1086/673168).
- Bulgarelli, A. et al. The On-Site Analysis of the Cherenkov Telescope Array . *PoS, ICRC2015:763*, 2016. doi:[10.22323/1.236.0763](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.236.0763).

- Burrows, D.N. et al. The Swift X-Ray Telescope. In Flanagan, K.A. and Siegmund, O.H.W., editors, *X-Ray and Gamma-Ray Instrumentation for Astronomy XIII*, volume 5165 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, pages 201–216, 2004. doi:[10.1117/12.504868](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.504868).
- Buson, S. and de Menezes, R. Fermi-LAT detection of continued enhanced gamma-ray activity from BL Lac. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 14777:1, 2021.
- Bühler, R. and Blandford, R. The surprising crab pulsar and its nebula: a review. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 77(6):066901, 2014. doi:[10.1088/0034-4885/77/6/066901](https://doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/77/6/066901).
- Carmona, E. et al. Monte Carlo Simulation for the MAGIC-II System. In *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, volume 3 of *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, pages 1373–1376, 2008.
- Carosi, A., López-Oramas, A. and Longo, F. The Cherenkov Telescope Array transient and multi-messenger program. *PoS, ICRC2021*:736, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0736](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0736).
- Casolino, M. et al. The JEM-EUSO instrument. 40:19–44, 2015. doi:[10.1007/s10686-014-9418-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10686-014-9418-x).
- Celotti, A. and Ghisellini, G. The power of blazar jets. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 385(1):283–300, 2008. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12758.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12758.x).
- Cerruti, M. et al. A hadronic origin for ultra-high-frequency-peaked BL Lac objects. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 448(1):910–927, 2015. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stu2691](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu2691).
- Champion, C. et al. TiCkS: A Flexible White-Rabbit Based Time-Stamping Board. In *16th International Conference on Accelerator and Large Experimental Physics Control Systems*, page TUPHA090, Barcelona, Spain, 2017. doi:[10.18429/JACoW-ICALEPCS2017-TUPHA090](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-ICALEPCS2017-TUPHA090).
- Connolly, S.D. A Python Code for the Emmanoulopoulos et al. [arXiv:1305.0304] Light Curve Simulation Algorithm. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1503.06676, 2015.
- Contreras, J. et al. Data model issues in the Cherenkov Telescope Array project. *PoS, ICRC2015*:960, 2016a. doi:[10.22323/1.236.0960](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.236.0960).

- Contreras, J.L. et al. Feasibility of VHE gamma ray detection by an array of imaging atmospheric Cherenkov telescopes using the fluorescence technique. *PoS, ICRC2015*: 993, 2016b, <https://doi.org/10.22323/1.236.0993>.
- Cortina, J. Status of the Large Size Telescopes of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. In *Proceedings of 36th International Cosmic Ray Conference — PoS(ICRC2029)*, volume 358, page 653, 2019. doi:[10.22323/1.358.0653](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.358.0653).
- Cortina, J. and CTA LST Collaboration. Detection of very-high-energy gamma-ray emission from BL Lac with the LST-1. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 14783:1, 2021.
- Costamante, L. and Ghisellini, G. TeV candidate BL Lac objects. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 384:56–71, 2002. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:20011749](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20011749).
- Costamante, L. et al. Extreme synchrotron BL Lac objects. Stretching the blazar sequence. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 371:512–526, 2001. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:20010412](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20010412).
- CTA Consortium. *Science with the Cherenkov Telescope Array*. WORLD SCIENTIFIC, 2019. doi:[10.1142/10986](https://doi.org/10.1142/10986).
- Dazzi, F. et al. The Stereoscopic Analog Trigger of the MAGIC Telescopes. *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 68(7):1473–1486, 2021. doi:[10.1109/TNS.2021.3079262](https://doi.org/10.1109/TNS.2021.3079262).
- De Lotto, B. and MAGIC Collaboration. The MAGIC telescopes: performance, results and future perspectives. In *Journal of Physics Conference Series*, volume 375 of *Journal of Physics Conference Series*, page 052021, 2012. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/375/1/052021](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/375/1/052021).
- de Naurois, M. *Very High Energy astronomy from H.E.S.S. to CTA. Opening of a new astronomical window on the non-thermal Universe*. PhD thesis, Ecole Polytechnique, 2000.
- de Naurois, M. and Mazin, D. Ground-based detectors in very-high-energy gamma-ray astronomy. *Comptes Rendus Physique*, 16(6):610–627, 2015. ISSN 1631-0705. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crhy.2015.08.011>. Gamma-ray astronomy / Astronomie des rayons gamma.

- de Souza, V., Barbosa, H. and Dobrigkeit, C. A Monte Carlo method to generate fluorescence light in extensive air showers. *Astroparticle Physics*, 22(3-4):263–273, 2004. ISSN 09276505. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2004.07.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2004.07.006).
- Deil, C. et al. Gammapy - A prototype for the CTA science tools. In *35th International Cosmic Ray Conference (ICRC2017)*, volume 301 of *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, page 766, 2017.
- Deil, C. et al. Data formats for gamma-ray astronomy. 2018. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.1409831](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1409831).
- Dermer, C.D. and Schlickeiser, R. Model for the High-Energy Emission from Blazars. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 416:458, 1993. doi:[10.1086/173251](https://doi.org/10.1086/173251).
- Dermer, C.D., Finke, J.D. and Menon, G. Black-Hole Engine Kinematics, Flares from PKS 2155-304, and Multiwavelength Blazar Analysis. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:0810.1055, 2008.
- Dimitrakoudis, S. et al. The time-dependent one-zone hadronic model. First principles. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 546:A120, 2012. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201219770](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201219770).
- Doering, M. et al. Measurement of the Cherenkov light spectrum and of the polarization with the HEGRA-IACT-system. *arXiv e-prints*, art. astro-ph/0107149, 2001.
- Domingo-Santamaría, E. et al. The DISP analysis method for point-like or extended gamma source searches/studies with the MAGIC Telescope. In *29th International Cosmic Ray Conference (ICRC29), Volume 5*, volume 5 of *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, page 363, 2005.
- Domínguez, A. et al. Extragalactic background light inferred from AEGIS galaxy-SED-type fractions. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 410(4): 2556–2578, 2011. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17631.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17631.x).
- Donath, A. et al. Gammapy: Python toolbox for gamma-ray astronomy. 2022. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.6552377](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6552377).
- Dumm, J. Highlights from the VERITAS Blazar Program. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1308.0287, 2013.
- Edelson, R.A. and Krolik, J.H. The Discrete Correlation Function: A New Method for Analyzing Unevenly Sampled Variability Data. *Astrophysical Journal*, 333:646, 1988. doi:[10.1086/166773](https://doi.org/10.1086/166773).

- Emmanoulopoulos, D., McHardy, I.M. and Papadakis, I.E. Generating artificial light curves: revisited and updated. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 433(2):907–927, 2013. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stt764](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt764).
- Falomo, R. and Kotilainen, J.K. Optical imaging of the host galaxies of X-ray selected BL Lacertae objects. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 352:85–102, 1999.
- Fidalgo, D. et al. Data processing activities at the MAGIC site . *PoS*, ICRC2015:742, 2016. doi:[10.22323/1.236.0742](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.236.0742).
- Fioretti, V. et al. Real-Time Analysis sensitivity evaluation of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. *PoS*, ICRC2015:699, 2016. doi:[10.22323/1.236.0699](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.236.0699).
- Fitzpatrick, E.L. Correcting for the Effects of Interstellar Extinction. *The Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 111(755):63–75, 1999. doi:[10.1086/316293](https://doi.org/10.1086/316293).
- Foffano, L. et al. Monitoring the pointing of the Large Size Telescope prototype using star reconstruction in the Cherenkov camera. *PoS*, ICRC2021:712, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0712](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0712).
- Fomin, V.P. et al. New methods of atmospheric Cherenkov imaging for gamma-ray astronomy. I. The false source method. *Astroparticle Physics*, 2:137–150, 1994. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:[10.1016/0927-6505\(94\)90036-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-6505(94)90036-1).
- Franceschini, A., Rodighiero, G. and Vaccari, M. Extragalactic optical-infrared background radiation, its time evolution and the cosmic photon-photon opacity. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 487(3):837–852, 2008. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:200809691](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:200809691).
- Furniss, A. et al. First NuSTAR Observations of Mrk 501 within a Radio to TeV Multi-Instrument Campaign. *Astrophysical Journal*, 812(1):65, 2015. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/812/1/65](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/812/1/65).
- Gaisser, T.K. and Hillas, A.M. Reliability of the Method of Constant Intensity Cuts for Reconstructing the Average Development of Vertical Showers. In *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, volume 8 of *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, page 353, 1977, <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1977ICRC....8..353G>.
- Garcia, E., Vuillaume, T. and Nickel, L. The lstMCpipe library. In *32th Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems*, 2022.

- Gaug, M. et al. The IFAE/UAB Raman LIDAR for the CTA-North. 2019a. doi:[10.1051/epjconf/201919702005](https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201919702005).
- Gaug, M. et al. Using Muon Rings for the Calibration of the Cherenkov Telescope Array: A Systematic Review of the Method and Its Potential Accuracy. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 243(1):11, 2019b. doi:[10.3847/1538-4365/ab2123](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ab2123).
- Ghisellini, G., Tavecchio, F. and Ghirlanda, G. Jet and accretion power in the most powerful fermi blazars. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 399(4): 2041–2054, 2009. ISSN 1365-2966. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15397.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15397.x).
- Ghisellini, G. et al. General physical properties of bright Fermi blazars. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 402(1):497–518, 2010. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15898.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15898.x).
- Ghisellini, G. et al. The Fermi blazar sequence. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 469(1):255–266, 2017. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stx806](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx806).
- Giommi, P. et al. X-ray spectra, light curves and SEDs of blazars frequently observed by Swift. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 507(4):5690–5702, 2021. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stab2425](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab2425).
- Greisen, K. Progress in Cosmic Ray Physics. *JG Wilson, Amsterdam, Netherlands*, 3, 1956.
- Gress, O. et al. Tunka-HiSCORE - A new array for multi-TeV γ -ray astronomy and cosmic-ray physics. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. Phys. Res. Sect. A Accel. Spectrometers, Detect. Assoc. Equip.*, 732:290–294, 2013. ISSN 01689002. doi:[10.1016/j.nima.2013.06.034](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2013.06.034).
- Gueta, O. The Cherenkov Telescope Array: layout, design and performance. *Proceedings of 37th International Cosmic Ray Conference — PoS(ICRC2021)*, ICRC2021: 885, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0885](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0885).
- Halzen, F. and Hooper, D. High energy neutrinos from the tev blazar 1es 1959+650. *Astroparticle Physics*, 23(6):537–542, 2005. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2005.03.007>.
- Hanski, M.T., Takalo, L.O. and Valtaoja, E. Correlated radio and optical variations in a sample of AGN. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 394:17–31, 2002. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:20020988](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20020988).

- Healey, S.E. et al. CRATES: An All-Sky Survey of Flat-Spectrum Radio Sources. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 171(1):61, 2007. doi:[10.1086/513742](https://doi.org/10.1086/513742).
- Heck, D. et al. CORSIKA: A Monte Carlo code to simulate extensive air showers. 1998. doi:[10.5445/IR/270043064](https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/270043064). 51.02.03; LK 01; Wissenschaftliche Berichte, FZKA-6019.
- HI4PI Collaboration et al. HI4PI: A full-sky H I survey based on EBHIS and GASS. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 594:A116, 2016. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201629178](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201629178).
- Hillas, A. Cerenkov light images of EAS produced by primary gamma. In *19th International Cosmic Ray Conference (ICRC19), Volume 3*, volume 3, 1985.
- Hillas, A.M. et al. The Spectrum of TeV Gamma Rays from the Crab Nebula. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 503(2):744–759, 1998. doi:[10.1086/306005](https://doi.org/10.1086/306005).
- Hinton, J. The Southern Wide-field Gamma-ray Observatory: Status and Prospects. *PoS, ICRC2021:023*, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0023](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0023).
- Hoffmann, D. and Houles, J. Prototyping a 10 gigabit-ethernet event-builder for the CTA camera server. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 396(1):012024, 2012. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/396/1/012024](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/396/1/012024).
- Holder, J. et al. The first VERITAS telescope. *Astroparticle Physics*, 25(6):391–401, 2006. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2006.04.002>.
- Holder, J. et al. Status of the VERITAS Observatory. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 1085(1):657–660, 2008. doi:[10.1063/1.3076760](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3076760).
- Holmes, S. et al. PIRATE: A Remotely Operable Telescope Facility for Research and Education. *The Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 123(908):1177, 2011. doi:[10.1086/662148](https://doi.org/10.1086/662148).
- Huege, T. and Falcke, H. Radio emission from cosmic ray air showers - coherent geosynchrotron radiation. *A&A*, 412(1):19–34, 2003. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:20031422](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20031422).
- Hufnagel, B.R. and Bregman, J.N. Optical and Radio Variability in Blazars. *Astrophysical Journal*, 386:473, 1992. doi:[10.1086/171033](https://doi.org/10.1086/171033).
- Kamata, K. and Nishimura, J. The Lateral and the Angular Structure Functions of Electron Showers. *Progress of Theoretical Physics Supplement*, 6:93–155, 1958. ISSN 0375-9687. doi:[10.1143/PTPS.6.93](https://doi.org/10.1143/PTPS.6.93).

- Kapanadze, B. Optical R-band variability of seven X-ray-selected BL Lacertae objects. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 398(2):832–840, 2009. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.14976.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.14976.x).
- Kapanadze, B. The Highest Historical 0.3-10 keV State of the TeV Source 1ES 0647+250. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 13324:1, 2019.
- Kapanadze, B. Another Strong X-Ray flare in the TeV-Detected Blazar 1ES 0647+250. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 14264:1, 2020.
- Kapanadze, B. et al. The X-ray behaviour of the high-energy peaked BL Lacertae source PKS 2155-304 in the 0.3-10 keV band. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 444(2):1077–1094, 2014. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stu1504](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu1504).
- Kapanadze, B. et al. The second strong X-ray flare and multifrequency variability of 1ES 1959+650 in 2016 January-August. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 473(2):2542–2564, 2018. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stx2492](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx2492).
- Karle, A. et al. Design and performance of the angle integrating Čerenkov array AIRO-BICC. *Astroparticle Physics*, 3(4):321–347, 1995. ISSN 09276505. doi:[10.1016/0927-6505\(95\)00009-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-6505(95)00009-6).
- Kiehlmann, S., Lindfors, E. and Larionov, V. Optical flare of the TeV blazar 1ES 0647+250. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 6726:1, 2014.
- Kildea, J. et al. The Whipple Observatory 10m gamma-ray telescope, 1997–2006. *Astroparticle Physics*, 28(2):182–195, 2007. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2007.05.004>.
- Kintscher, T. et al. IceCube Search for Neutrinos from 1ES 1959+650: Completing the Picture. In *Proceedings of 35th International Cosmic Ray Conference — PoS(ICRC2017)*, volume 301, page 969, 2017. doi:[10.22323/1.301.0969](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.301.0969).
- Knödlseher, J. et al. ctools 1.7.4. 2021. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4727876](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727876).
- Kobayashi, Y. et al. Camera Calibration of the CTA-LST prototype. *PoS, ICRC2021*: 720, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0720](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0720).
- Konigl, A. Relativistic jets as X-ray and gamma-ray sources. , 243:700–709, 1981. doi:[10.1086/158638](https://doi.org/10.1086/158638).

- Konopelko, A. et al. Detection of gamma rays above 1 tev from the crab nebula by the second hegra imaging atmospheric cherenkov telescope at la palma. *Astroparticle Physics*, 4(3):199–215, 1996. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-6505\(95\)00044-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-6505(95)00044-5).
- Kotilainen, J.K. et al. The host galaxy of the BL Lacertae object 1ES 0647+250 and its imaging redshift. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 534:L2, 2011. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201117800](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201117800).
- Kreter, M. et al. On the Detection Potential of Blazar Flares for Current Neutrino Telescopes. *Astrophysical Journal*, 902(2):133, 2020. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/abb5b1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abb5b1).
- Kunkel, L. et al. BL Lac reaches a new optical all-time maximum. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 14820:1, 2021.
- Lamanna, G. Cherenkov Telescope Array Data Management . *PoS*, ICRC2015:947, 2016. doi:[10.22323/1.236.0947](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.236.0947).
- Lessard, R. et al. A new analysis method for reconstructing the arrival direction of TeV gamma rays using a single imaging atmospheric Cherenkov telescope. *Astroparticle Physics*, 15(1):1–18, 2001. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-6505\(00\)00133-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-6505(00)00133-X).
- Levinson, A. Implications of VHE emission in Gamma-Ray AGN. *PoS*, BLAZARS2008:002, 2009. doi:[10.22323/1.063.0002](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.063.0002).
- LHAASO Collaboration et al. Peta-electron volt gamma-ray emission from the Crab Nebula. *Science*, 373:425–430, 2021. doi:[10.1126/science.abg5137](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abg5137).
- Li, T.P. and Ma, Y.Q. Analysis methods for results in gamma-ray astronomy. *Astrophysical Journal*, 272:317–324, 1983. doi:[10.1086/161295](https://doi.org/10.1086/161295).
- Lindfors, E.J. et al. Optical and radio variability of the northern VHE gamma-ray emitting BL Lacertae objects. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 593:A98, 2016. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201628420](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201628420).
- Lioudakis, I. et al. Multiwavelength cross-correlations and flaring activity in bright blazars. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 480(4):5517–5528, 2018. doi:[10.1093/mnras/sty2264](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty2264).

- Lioudakis, I. et al. Probing Blazar Emission Processes with Optical/Gamma-Ray Flare Correlations. *Astrophysical Journal*, 880(1):32, 2019. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/ab26b7](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab26b7).
- López-Coto, R. et al. lstchain: An Analysis Pipeline for LST-1, the First Prototype Large-Sized Telescope of CTA. In Ruiz, J.E., Pierfederici, F. and Teuben, P., editors, *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, volume 532 of *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, page 357, 2022.
- López-Coto, R. et al. Physics Performance of the Large Size Telescope prototype of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. In *Proceedings, 37th International Cosmic Ray Conference*, volume 395, page 806, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0806](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0806).
- Ma, X.H. et al. Chapter 1 LHAASO Instruments and Detector technology. *Chinese Physics C*, 2022, Vol. 46, Issue 3, Pages: 030001-030001-35, 46:030001–030001–35, 2022. ISSN 16741137. doi:[10.1088/1674-1137/AC3FA6](https://doi.org/10.1088/1674-1137/AC3FA6).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. Multi-wavelength characterization of the blazar S5 0716+714 during an unprecedented outburst phase. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 619:A45, 2018. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201832677](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201832677).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. A fast, very-high-energy flare from BL Lacertae during a period of multi-wavelength activity in June 2015. *A&A*, 623:A175, 2019. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201834010](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201834010).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. Testing two-component models on very high-energy gamma-ray-emitting BL Lac objects. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 640:A132, 2020a. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202037811](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202037811).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. Broadband characterisation of the very intense TeV flares of the blazar 1ES 1959+650 in 2016. *A&A*, 638:A14, 2020b. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201935450](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935450).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. Studying the long-term spectral and temporal evolution of 1ES 1959+650. *PoS, ICRC2021*:858, 2021a. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0858](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0858).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. Investigation of the correlation patterns and the Compton dominance variability of Mrk 421 in 2017. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 655:A89, 2021b. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202141004](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202141004).
- MAGIC Collaboration et al. Long-term multi-wavelength study of 1ES 0647+250. *A&A*, 670:A49, 2023. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202244477](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202244477).

- Maier, G. and Holder, J. Eventdisplay: An Analysis and Reconstruction Package for Ground-based Gamma-ray Astronomy. *PoS*, ICRC2017:747, 2017. doi:[10.22323/1.301.0747](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.301.0747).
- Mannheim, K. The proton blazar. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 269:67–76, 1993.
- Maraschi, L. and Tavecchio, F. The Jet-Disk Connection and Blazar Unification. *Astrophysical Journal*, 593:667–675, 2003. doi:[10.1086/342118](https://doi.org/10.1086/342118).
- Maraschi, L., Ghisellini, G. and Celotti, A. A Jet Model for the Gamma-Ray-emitting Blazar 3C 279. , 397:L5, 1992. doi:[10.1086/186531](https://doi.org/10.1086/186531).
- Martinez, S. et al. Monte Carlo simulation of the HEGRA cosmic ray detector performance. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 357(2-3):567–579, 1995. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:[10.1016/0168-9002\(94\)01541-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002(94)01541-4).
- Mattox, J.R. et al. The Likelihood Analysis of EGRET Data. *Astrophysical Journal*, 461:396, 1996. doi:[10.1086/177068](https://doi.org/10.1086/177068).
- Max-Moerbeck, W. et al. Time correlation between the radio and gamma-ray activity in blazars and the production site of the gamma-ray emission. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 445(1):428–436, 2014a. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stu1749](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu1749).
- Max-Moerbeck, W. et al. A method for the estimation of the significance of cross-correlations in unevenly sampled red-noise time series. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 445(1):437–459, 2014b. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stu1707](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu1707).
- Mazin, D. Status and results of the prototype LST of CTA. In *Proceedings of 37th International Cosmic Ray Conference — PoS(ICRC2021)*, volume 395, page 872, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0872](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0872).
- Meisner, A.M. and Romani, R.W. Imaging Redshift Estimates for BL Lacertae Objects. *Astrophysical Journal*, 712(1):14–25, 2010. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/712/1/14](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/712/1/14).
- Miller, H.R. and McGimsey, B.Q. Photoelectric intraday observations of BL Lacertae, 3C 66 A, B2 1652+39, and 3C 371. , 220:19–24, 1978. doi:[10.1086/155878](https://doi.org/10.1086/155878).
- Mirzoyan, R. MAGIC detection of an increased activity from BL Lacertae at very-high-energy gamma rays. *The Astronomer’s Telegram*, 12724:1, 2019a.

- Mirzoyan, R. MAGIC detection of increased flux from 1ES 0647+250 at very-high-energy gamma rays. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 13331:1, 2019b.
- Moralejo, A. et al. MARS, the MAGIC Analysis and Reconstruction Software. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:0907.0943, 2009.
- Morcuende, D. and Rosado, J. ShowerModel. 2021. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.5589819](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5589819).
- Morcuende, D. et al. A Monte Carlo study of the relevance of fluorescence radiation in VHE gamma ray observations with Cherenkov telescopes. *Proc. Sci.*, 2017, <https://pos.sissa.it/301/839/pdf>.
- Morcuende, D. et al. Relevance of the fluorescence radiation in vhe gamma-ray observations with the cherenkov technique. *Astroparticle Physics*, 107:26–34, 2019. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2018.11.003>.
- Muriel, H. et al. The BL-Lac gamma-ray blazar PKS 0447-439 as a probable member of a group of galaxies at $z = 0.343$. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 574:A101, 2015. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201425050](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201425050).
- Nalewajko, K., Sikora, M. and Begelman, M.C. Reconciling Models of Luminous Blazars with Magnetic Fluxes Determined by Radio Core-shift Measurements. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 796(1):L5, 2014. doi:[10.1088/2041-8205/796/1/L5](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/796/1/L5).
- Nandikotkur, G. et al. Does the Blazar Gamma-Ray Spectrum Harden with Increasing Flux? Analysis of 9 Years of EGRET Data. *Astrophysical Journal*, 657(2):706–724, 2007. doi:[10.1086/510795](https://doi.org/10.1086/510795).
- Nasa High Energy Astrophysics Science Archive Research Center. HEASoft: Unified Release of FTOOLS and XANADU. Astrophysics Source Code Library, record ascl:1408.004, 2014.
- Nerling, F. et al. Universality of electron distributions in high-energy air showers-Description of Cherenkov light production. *Astroparticle Physics*, 24:421–437, 2006. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2005.09.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2005.09.002).
- Nieto, D. et al. Exploring deep learning as an event classification method for the Cherenkov Telescope Array. *PoS, ICRC2017*:809, 2017. doi:[10.22323/1.301.0809](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.301.0809).
- Nievas Rosillo, M. et al. Hunting extreme BL Lacertae blazars with Fermi-Large Area Telescope. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 512(1):137–159, 2022. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stac491](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac491).

- Nigro, C. et al. Towards open and reproducible multi-instrument analysis in gamma-ray astronomy. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 625:A10, 2019. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201834938](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201834938).
- Nilsson, K. et al. Long-term optical monitoring of TeV emitting blazars. I. Data analysis. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 620:A185, 2018. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201833621](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833621).
- Nishiyama, T. et al. Detection of a new TeV gamma-ray source of BL Lac object 1ES 1959+650. In *26th International Cosmic Ray Conference*, 1999.
- Noethe, M. et al. Prototype Open Event Reconstruction Pipeline for the Cherenkov Telescope Array. *PoS, ICRC2021*:744, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0744](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0744).
- Nozaki, S. et al. Calibration and performance of the readout system based on switched capacitor arrays for the Large-Sized Telescope of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. In Evans, C.J., Bryant, J.J. and Motohara, K., editors, *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VIII*, volume 11447, pages 64 – 77. International Society for Optics and Photonics, SPIE, 2020a. doi:[10.1117/12.2560018](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2560018).
- Nozaki, S. et al. The readout system based on the ultra-fast waveform sampler DRS4 for the large-sized telescope of the cherenkov telescope array. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1468(1):012104, 2020b. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/1468/1/012104](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1468/1/012104).
- Nöthe, M. et al. pyirf. 2022. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7362244](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7362244).
- Ohm, S., van Eldik, C. and Egberts, K. γ /hadron separation in very-high-energy gamma-ray astronomy using a multivariate analysis method. *Astroparticle Physics*, 31:383–391, 2009. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:[10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2009.04.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2009.04.001).
- Otero-Santos, J. et al. Quasi-periodic behaviour in the optical and γ -ray light curves of blazars 3C 66A and B2 1633+38. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 492(4):5524–5539, 2020. doi:[10.1093/mnras/staa134](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa134).
- Padovani, P. and Giommi, P. The Connection between X-Ray– and Radio-selected BL Lacertae Objects. *Astrophysical Journal*, 444:567, 1995. doi:[10.1086/175631](https://doi.org/10.1086/175631).
- Paiano, S. et al. On the Redshift of TeV BL Lac Objects. *Astrophysical Journal*, 837(2):144, 2017. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/837/2/144](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/837/2/144).
- Palatiello, M. et al. Performance of the INFN Camera calibration device of the first Large Size Telescope in the Cherenkov Telescope Array. *PoS, ICRC2019*:757, 2019. doi:[10.22323/1.358.0757](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.358.0757).

- Parsons, R. and Hinton, J. A Monte Carlo template based analysis for air-Cherenkov arrays. *Astroparticle Physics*, 56:26–34, 2014. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2014.03.002>.
- Pedregosa, F. et al. Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12:2825–2830, 2011.
- Perlman, E.S. et al. The Einstein Slew Survey Sample of BL Lacertae Objects. , 104: 251, 1996. doi:[10.1086/192300](https://doi.org/10.1086/192300).
- Perlman, E.S. et al. Intrinsic Curvature in the X-Ray Spectra of BL Lacertae Objects. *Astrophysical Journal*, 625(2):727–740, 2005. doi:[10.1086/429688](https://doi.org/10.1086/429688).
- Peterson, B.M. et al. On Uncertainties in Cross-Correlation Lags and the Reality of Wavelength-dependent Continuum Lags in Active Galactic Nuclei. *The Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 110(748):660–670, 1998. doi:[10.1086/316177](https://doi.org/10.1086/316177).
- Peterson, B.M. et al. Central Masses and Broad-Line Region Sizes of Active Galactic Nuclei. II. A Homogeneous Analysis of a Large Reverberation-Mapping Database. *Astrophysical Journal*, 613(2):682–699, 2004. doi:[10.1086/423269](https://doi.org/10.1086/423269).
- Petropoulou, M., Vasilopoulos, G. and Giannios, D. The TeV emission of Ap Librae: a hadronic interpretation and prospects for CTA. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 464(2):2213–2222, 2017. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stw2453](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw2453).
- Petropoulou, M. et al. Multi-epoch Modeling of TXS 0506+056 and Implications for Long-term High-energy Neutrino Emission. *Astrophysical Journal*, 891(2):115, 2020a. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/ab76d0](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab76d0).
- Petropoulou, M. et al. Comprehensive Multimessenger Modeling of the Extreme Blazar 3HSP J095507.9+355101 and Predictions for IceCube. *Astrophysical Journal*, 899(2):113, 2020b. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aba8a0](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aba8a0).
- Pian, E. et al. BeppoSAX Observations of Unprecedented Synchrotron Activity in the BL Lacertae Object Markarian 501. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 492(1): L17–L20, 1998. doi:[10.1086/311083](https://doi.org/10.1086/311083).
- Piner, B.G. and Edwards, P.G. First-epoch VLBA Imaging of 20 New TeV Blazars. *Astrophysical Journal*, 797(1):25, 2014. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/797/1/25](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/797/1/25).

- Piner, B.G. and Edwards, P.G. Multi-epoch VLBA Imaging of 20 New TeV Blazars: Apparent Jet Speeds. *Astrophysical Journal*, 853:68, 2018. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aaa425](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aaa425).
- Piron, F. et al. Temporal and spectral gamma-ray properties of Mkn 421 above 250 GeV from CAT observations between 1996 and 2000. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 374(3):895–906, 2001. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361:20010798](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20010798).
- Planck Collaboration et al. Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 641:A6, 2020. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201833910](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833910).
- Poole, T.S. et al. Photometric calibration of the Swift ultraviolet/optical telescope. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 383(2):627–645, 2008. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12563.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12563.x).
- Poutanen, J., Zdziarski, A.A. and Ibragimov, A. Superorbital variability of X-ray and radio emission of Cyg X-1 - II. Dependence of the orbital modulation and spectral hardness on the superorbital phase. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 389(3):1427–1438, 2008. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13666.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13666.x).
- Prandini, E. et al. Constraining blazar distances with combined Fermi and TeV data: an empirical approach. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 405(1):L76–L80, 2010. doi:[10.1111/j.1745-3933.2010.00862.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3933.2010.00862.x).
- Prandini, E. et al. TeV blazars and their distance. In *Cosmic Radiation Fields: Sources in the early Universe (CRF 2010)*, page 12, 2011. doi:<https://doi.org/10.22323/1.121.0012>. ArXiv e-print: 1101.5005.
- Prandini, E., Bonnoli, G. and Tavecchio, F. Estimating the redshift of PKS 0447-439 through its GeV-TeV emission. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 543:A111, 2012. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201118289](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201118289).
- Pushkarev, A.B. et al. MOJAVE: Monitoring of Jets in Active galactic nuclei with VLBA Experiments. IX. Nuclear opacity. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 545:A113, 2012. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201219173](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201219173).
- Raiteri, C.M. et al. The dual nature of blazar fast variability: Space and ground observations of S5 0716+714. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 501(1):1100–1115, 2021. doi:[10.1093/mnras/staa3561](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa3561).

- Ramakrishnan, V. et al. Locating the γ -ray emission site in Fermi/LAT blazars - II. Multifrequency correlations. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 456 (1):171–180, 2016. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stv2653](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv2653).
- Reininghaus, M. and Ulrich, R. CORSIKA 8 - Towards a modern framework for the simulation of extensive air showers. In *European Physical Journal Web of Conferences*, volume 210 of *European Physical Journal Web of Conferences*, page 02011, 2019. doi:[10.1051/epjconf/201921002011](https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201921002011).
- Richards, J.L. et al. Blazars in the Fermi Era: The OVRO 40 m Telescope Monitoring Program. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 194(2):29, 2011. doi:[10.1088/0067-0049/194/2/29](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/194/2/29).
- Roming, P.W.A. et al. The Swift Ultra-Violet/Optical Telescope. *Space Science Reviews*, 120(3-4):95–142, 2005. doi:[10.1007/s11214-005-5095-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-005-5095-4).
- Rosado, J., Blanco, F. and Arqueros, F. On the absolute value of the air-fluorescence yield. *Astroparticle Physics*, 55:51–62, 2014. ISSN 09276505. doi:[10.1016/j.astropartphys.2014.02.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2014.02.003).
- Sailer, S. *The FlashCam camera for CTA: trigger verification and fluorescence light detection capabilities*. PhD thesis, Heidelberg University, 2020.
- Saito, T., Delgado, C. and Blanch, O. Commissioning of the camera of the first Large Size Telescope of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. In *Proceedings of 37th International Cosmic Ray Conference — PoS(ICRC2021)*, volume 395, page 718, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0718](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0718).
- Sakurai, S., Depaoli, D. and López-Coto, R. The calibration of the first Large-Sized Telescope of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. *Proceedings of 36th International Cosmic Ray Conference — PoS(ICRC2019)*, 2019.
- Sbarufatti, B., Treves, A. and Falomo, R. Imaging Redshifts of BL Lacertae Objects. *Astrophysical Journal*, 635(1):173–179, 2005. doi:[10.1086/497022](https://doi.org/10.1086/497022).
- Scarpa, R. et al. The Hubble Space Telescope Survey of BL Lacertae Objects. I. Surface Brightness Profiles, Magnitudes, and Radii of Host Galaxies. *Astrophysical Journal*, 532(2):740–815, 2000. doi:[10.1086/308618](https://doi.org/10.1086/308618).
- Schachter, J.F. et al. The Einstein Slew Survey Catalog. pages 441–451, 1992. doi:[10.1007/978-94-011-2472-0_56](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-2472-0_56).

- Schachter, J.F. et al. Ten New BL Lacertae Objects Discovered by an Efficient X-Ray/Radio/Optical Technique. *ApJ*, 412:541, 1993. ISSN 0004-637X. doi:[10.1086/172942](https://doi.org/10.1086/172942).
- Schellart, P. *Measuring radio emission from air showers with LOFAR*. PhD thesis, 2015, <https://repository.ubn.ru.nl/handle/2066/138600>.
- Schlafly, E.F. and Finkbeiner, D.P. Measuring Reddening with Sloan Digital Sky Survey Stellar Spectra and Recalibrating SFD. *Astrophysical Journal*, 737(2):103, 2011. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/737/2/103](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/737/2/103).
- Schleicher, B. et al. Fractional Variability—A Tool to Study Blazar Variability. *Galaxies*, 7(2):62, 2019. doi:[10.3390/galaxies7020062](https://doi.org/10.3390/galaxies7020062).
- Servillat, M. et al. Towards a provenance management system for astronomical observatories. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 244–249. Springer International Publishing, 2021. doi:[10.1007/978-3-030-80960-7_20](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80960-7_20).
- Servillat, M. et al. IVOA Provenance Data Model, 2020, <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/ProvenanceDM>.
- Shaw, M.S. et al. Spectroscopy of The Largest Ever Gamma-ray Selected BL Lac Sample. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 764:135, 2013. doi:[10.1088/0004-637X/764/2/135](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/764/2/135).
- Shilon, I. et al. Application of deep learning methods to analysis of imaging atmospheric cherenkov telescopes data. *Astroparticle Physics*, 105:44–53, 2019. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:[10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2018.10.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2018.10.003).
- Sitarek, J. et al. Analysis techniques and performance of the domino ring sampler version 4 based readout for the magic telescopes. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 723:109–120, 2013. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2013.05.014>.
- Smith, A.G. et al. The Longer Optical Time Scales of a Large Sample of Quasars. , 105:437, 1993. doi:[10.1086/116442](https://doi.org/10.1086/116442).
- Steele, I.A. et al. The Liverpool Telescope: performance and first results. In Oschmann, Jacobus M., J., editor, *Ground-based Telescopes*, volume 5489 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, pages 679–692, 2004. doi:[10.1117/12.551456](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.551456).

- Tamm, I. and Frank, I. Coherent radiation of fast electrons in a medium. In *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, volume 14, pages 107–112, 1937.
- Tanimori, T. et al. Detection of gamma rays of up to 50 tev from the crab nebula. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 492(1):L33–L36, 1998. doi:[10.1086/311077](https://doi.org/10.1086/311077).
- Tavecchio, F. and Ghisellini, G. On the magnetization of BL Lac jets. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 456(3):2374–2382, 2016. doi:[10.1093/mnras/stv2790](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv2790).
- Tavecchio, F., Maraschi, L. and Ghisellini, G. Constraints on the Physical Parameters of TeV Blazars. *Astrophysical Journal*, 509(2):608–619, 1998. doi:[10.1086/306526](https://doi.org/10.1086/306526).
- Tavecchio, F. et al. On the origin of the γ -ray emission from the flaring blazar PKS 1222+216. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 534:A86, 2011. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/201117204](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201117204).
- Tejedor, L.A. et al. A trigger interface board for the large and medium sized telescopes of the cherenkov telescope array. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 1027:166058, 2022. ISSN 0168-9002. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2021.166058>.
- Terasranta, H. et al. Ten years monitoring of extragalactic radio sources at 22, 37 and 87 GHz. , 94:121–173, 1992.
- The Pierre Auger Collaboration. The Pierre Auger Cosmic Ray Observatory. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1502.01323, 2015.
- Thorne, J. et al. Agn unification diagram, 2022. Was originally created to be included in the introduction of Thorne J. E., et al., 2022, MNRAS, 509, 4940.
- Tluczykont, M. et al. The HiSCORE concept for gamma-ray and cosmic-ray astrophysics beyond 10 TeV. *Astroparticle Physics*, 56:42–53, 2014. ISSN 0927-6505. doi:[10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2014.03.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2014.03.004).
- Tornikoski, M. et al. Correlated radio and optical variations in a sample of active galactic nuclei. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 289:673–710, 1994.
- Tramacere, A. et al. Radio- γ -ray response in blazars as a signature of adiabatic blob expansion. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 658:A173, 2022. doi:[10.1051/0004-6361/202142003](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202142003).

- Trimble, V. The Distance to the Crab Nebula and NP 0532. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 85:579, 1973. doi:[10.1086/129507](https://doi.org/10.1086/129507).
- Unger, M. et al. Reconstruction of longitudinal profiles of ultra-high energy cosmic ray showers from fluorescence and Cherenkov light measurements. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. Phys. Res. Sect. A Accel. Spectrometers, Detect. Assoc. Equip.*, 588(3):433–441, 2008. ISSN 01689002. doi:[10.1016/j.nima.2008.01.100](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2008.01.100).
- Urry, C.M. and Padovani, P. Unified Schemes for Radio-Loud Active Galactic Nuclei. *The Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 107:803, 1995. doi:[10.1086/133630](https://doi.org/10.1086/133630).
- Valverde, J. et al. A Decade of Multiwavelength Observations of the TeV Blazar 1ES 1215+303: Extreme Shift of the Synchrotron Peak Frequency and Long-term Optical-Gamma-Ray Flux Increase. *Astrophysical Journal*, 891(2):170, 2020. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/ab765d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab765d).
- Vaughan, S. et al. On characterizing the variability properties of X-ray light curves from active galaxies. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 345(4):1271–1284, 2003. doi:[10.1046/j.1365-2966.2003.07042.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2966.2003.07042.x).
- Vuillaume, T. et al. *ps²chitt!* A Python package for the modelling of atmospheric Showers and Cherenkov Imaging Terrestrial Telescopes. *PoS, ICRC2017:772*, 2017. doi:[10.22323/1.301.0772](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.301.0772).
- Vuillaume, T., Garcia, E. and Nickel, L. *lstMCpipe*. 2022. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.6460727](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6460727).
- Wang, Y. et al. Systematic Investigation of X-Ray Spectral Variability of TeV Blazars during Flares in the RXTE Era. *Astrophysical Journal*, 867(1):68, 2018. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aae307](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aae307).
- Weaver, Z.R. et al. Multiwavelength variability of BL lacertae measured with high time resolution. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 900(2):137, 2020. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aba693](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aba693).
- Weekes, T.C. et al. Observation of TeV Gamma Rays from the Crab Nebula Using the Atmospheric Cerenkov Imaging Technique. *Astrophysical Journal*, 342:379, 1989. doi:[10.1086/167599](https://doi.org/10.1086/167599).
- White, R. et al. The Small-Sized Telescopes for the Southern Site of the Cherenkov Telescope Array. *PoS, ICRC2021:728*, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.395.0728](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.395.0728).

- Wood, M. et al. Fermipy: An open-source Python package for analysis of Fermi-LAT Data. In *35th International Cosmic Ray Conference (ICRC2017)*, volume 301 of *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, page 824, 2021. doi:[10.22323/1.301.0824](https://doi.org/10.22323/1.301.0824).
- Xue, Y., Yuan, F. and Cui, W. X-Ray Spectral Variability of TeV Blazars during Rapid Flares. *Astrophysical Journal*, 647(1):194–200, 2006. doi:[10.1086/505381](https://doi.org/10.1086/505381).
- Zanin, R. et al. MARS, The MAGIC Analysis and Reconstruction Software. In *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, volume 33 of *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, page 2937, 2013.
- Zhang, B.K. et al. Correlation Investigation of Radio and Optical Variations in a Large Sample of Fermi Blazars. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 231(2):14, 2017. doi:[10.3847/1538-4365/aa7ed9](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/aa7ed9).
- Zhang, S.S. et al. Properties and performance of two wide field of view Cherenkov/fluorescence telescope array prototypes. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. Phys. Res. Sect. A Accel. Spectrometers, Detect. Assoc. Equip.*, 629(1):57–65, 2011. ISSN 01689002. doi:[10.1016/j.nima.2010.11.120](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2010.11.120).